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DR. P. S. AITHAL

DR. LAVEENA D'MELLO

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Website: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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Paper 1

ESSENTIAL INFRASTRUCTURES FOR WORLD-CLASS UNIVERSITIES

P. S. Aithal¹ & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal^{2*}

¹Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : shubhraaithal@gmail.com

Abstract:

Higher education institutions including universities finding more challenges due to enhanced competitions worldwide. Innovations in higher education model are finding importance than ever before due to enhanced higher education institutions and the advancement in technology adopted mass education opportunities. After privatization of higher education, there is an enhanced competition between universities to attract students globally. Universities are competing with each other in terms of their physical and intellectual assets. In this paper, it is postulated that the six essential infrastructures to be developed by a university for accelerated growth as world-class university are (1) Physical infrastructure, (2) Digital infrastructure, (3) Innovative academic & training Infrastructure for confidence building, (4) Intellectual property infrastructure, (5) Emotional infrastructure, and (6) Networked infrastructure. We have determined the primary focus of these infrastructures along with their essential objectives, components, and the procedure of developing them to the optimum level.

Keywords : World-class universities, Essential assets, Physical infrastructure, Digital infrastructure, Academic & training Infrastructure, Intellectual property infrastructure, Emotional infrastructure, Networked infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Higher Education, being one of the important service industries, plays a major role in the development of the economy of the country. Accordingly, innovations in the higher education model are finding importance than ever before due to enhanced higher education institutions and the advancement in technology adopted mass education opportunities. After privatization of higher education, there is an enhanced competition between universities to attract students globally. Universities are competing with each other in terms of their physical and intellectual assets. In many developed countries, private universities could establish a huge amount of physical infrastructures due to their autonomy and existence since a long time usually more than a hundred years. Compared to public universities which are depending on limited public funding, private universities could invest more funds on developing better infrastructure due to their autonomy in using funds on their accelerated development. World class universities are those universities from both public and private sectors focus both teaching and research which have made name and fame to attract global students for their multidisciplinary degree programmes through their quality & capability to provide world class education in varied areas. Times Higher Education (THE) Magazine, a university ranking agency has identified various parameters as metric to rank universities.

Based on such common parameters called performance indicators and comparison of scores under such parameters, it is announcing world ranking of universities every year. Times Higher Education World University Rankings evaluates more than 1000 world universities based on 13 performance indicators related to teaching, research, citations, international outlook, and industry income to provide the most comprehensive and balanced comparisons and hence is by far the most reliable and the most respected. One of the important parameters which play an effective role in the world ranking of universities and hence World-class universities is time duration of its existence i.e., length of its service to the society and hence its reliability. Many of the world top universities have a common factor of more than 100 years of their existence. Such a long existence and service to society is giving them a special reputation and advantage in the world ranking. The new universities born in the 21st century have a disadvantage of achieving this time based reputation and hence face a greater challenge to enter such university ranking list. However, by means of innovative and differentiated service, new universities can also compete with old universities using re-defining their quality of service, intellectual abilities, research contributions, industry networking, and physical assets to earn special recognition in world higher education scenario. In this paper, we made an attempt in a systematic way to identify such resources both tangible and intangible to accumulate in growing universities to be a world-class university.

2. RELATED WORKS :

There are many scholarly research publications on building and analysing world-class universities. These papers are either resource based analysis or geographic based analysis. This also includes policies, strategies, or contributions of universities globally to higher education and research. Table 1 summarizes the area and focus of various scholarly papers published during last few years in the 21st century.

Table 1 : Review on various scholarly papers published related to world-class universities

S. No.	Area	Focus	Reference
1	World class Universities	Cost and benefits	Altbach, P. (2015) [1]
2	Building world-class universities	Different approaches to a shared goal	Wang, Q., et al. (2013). [2]
3	Quest for building world-class universities in South Korea	Outcomes and consequences	Byun, K.et al. (2013) [3]
4	Building the world-class research universities	A case study of China	Huang, F. (2015). [4]
5	How world-class universities affect global higher education.		Cheng, Y., (2014) [5]
6	Corporate universities	Lessons in building a world-class work force	Kottke, J. L. (1999). [6]
7	Building World Class Universities		Krishnan, R. T. (2005). [7]
8	Third mission ranking for world class universities	Beyond teaching and research	Montesinos, P., et al. (2008). [8]
9	National initiatives for building world-class universities	Comparison between Asian and European experiences	Deng, Q., et al. (2010). [9]

10	An analysis of mobility in global rankings	Making institutional strategic plans and positioning for building world-class universities	Hou, A. Y. C., (2012). [10]
11	Creating world-class universities in Japan	Policy and initiatives	Oba, J. (2008). [11]
12	Creating world-class universities	Implications for developing countries	Lee, J. (2013). [12]
13	India	World-Class Universities	Altbach, P. (2015). [13]
14	World-Class universities	Can Young Universities Achieve World-Class Status?	Salmi, J. (2013). [14]
15	World-Class universities	Successful strategies to be learnt from world-class universities	Bejinaru, R. Et al (2017). [15]

3. OBJECTIVES :

Innovations in higher education model are finding importance than ever before due to enhanced higher education institutions and the advancement in technology adopted mass education opportunities. The objectives this paper are :

- (1) To identify the essential infrastructures for autonomous institutions/ universities to attain Excellency in imparting higher education globally.
- (2) To determine the primary focus of these infrastructures along with their essentials in detail.
- (3) To study each infrastructure in detail and strategies to be followed to develop such infrastructures.
- (4) To discuss how the above Infrastructures help to develop strategies for Survival, Sustainability, Differentiation, and Growth & prosperity.
- (5) To classify necessary and sufficient conditions of developing such infrastructures for all the above strategies towards building World class universities.

4. METHODOLOGY :

The methodology used in this study is called Focus group based Predictive analysis which deals with collection of information related to identified problem from a group of experts in the field and related fields and analysing such information in the context of predicting the future consequences of the identified present problem [16-18].

A simple method called predictive analysis is recently developed to address decision making problems related to predicting the future. Predictive analysis is an analytical method consisting of several techniques to predict future possibilities using present trends. It can be qualitative or quantitative. It is different from predictive analytics in such a way that it will support to predict future. On the other hand, predictive analytics is a method of generating information from historically available dataset to determine and predict future trends and outcomes [19].

Predictive analysis is a method consisting of several techniques to predict future possibilities using present trends. It is different from predictive analytics in such a way that it will support to predict future. On the other hand, predictive analytics is a method of generating

information from historically available dataset to determine and predict future trends and outcomes. A qualitative predictive analysis is used to predict the future possibilities by studying present trends using self-developed predictive analysis model shown in figure 1 [20]. The procedure of predictive analysis of a system or an activity encompasses 4 steps : Collect information on present trends, Develop postulates based on present trends, Generate argument based description, and Predict the future.

Fig. 1 : Predictive Analysis Model to predict future [19]

5. ESSENTIALS FOR WORLD CLASS UNIVERSITIES :

The six infrastructures identified based on our predictive analysis for world class universities are listed in table 2 with their preliminary focus. The block diagram shown in figure 2 depicts the essential components for world class universities.

It is known that ideal systems are hypothetical systems with ideal characteristics. There are many varieties of ideal systems are predicted, analysed, and discussed on possibility of realization of such ideal systems by different authors in their scholarly publications [21- 37]. Table 3 depicts the ideal expected level of essential infrastructure required for attaining global excellence.

Fig. 2 : Block diagram of essential components for world class universities

Table 2 : List of Infrastructures required for attaining excellence and their focus

S. No	Essentials for attaining Excellence	Primary Focus
1	Physical Infrastructure	Comfortability
2	Digital Infrastructure	Openness & Ubiquitous accessibility
3	Innovative academic Infrastructure	Confidence building
4	Intellectual Property Infrastructure	Creating new knowledge & Innovation
5	Emotional Infrastructure	Belongingness & Connectedness of all stakeholders
6	Industry Networked Infrastructure	Industry Interactions for Training, Placement, & entrepreneurship

Table 3 : Ideal Infrastructures required for attaining global excellence

S. No	Essentials for attaining Excellence	Ideal Level of Expectation
1	Physical Infrastructure	Open outdoor natural place without any disturbance
2	Digital Infrastructure	Free access to any & every information in any form
3	Innovative academic Infrastructure	Models and pedagogies to make ideal graduate with unlimited knowledge, skills, experience and hence confidence
4	Intellectual Property Infrastructure	Infinite ability to Creating new knowledge & new innovation (IP) by students & faculties.
5	Emotional Infrastructure	Every stakeholder feels that the organization is of his own and every other stakeholder is his family member.
6	Networked Infrastructure	Perfectly networked with all kind of industries in entire globe for open Placement & entrepreneurship

(1) Physical infrastructure :

Physical infrastructure is required to provide comfortability and safety for the stakeholders for the teaching-learning process. Though a good and safety physical infrastructure at a comfortable location is desired, the ideal education system promotes an Open outdoor place without any disturbance. In reality the Country, Location, Land, Land connectivity, Landscaping, Students feeding area, Supporting industries, Attractive & green buildings, Structure & design of each buildings, Parking facilities, Roads with walking & bicycle path, Admission & Counselling Area, Classrooms, counselling rooms, faculty chambers, Meeting rooms, Laboratories, Studios, Gymnastics, Theatres, Cafeteria, Games & Sports facility, Auditorium, Library/Digital resource centre, Xerox & Printing centre, Hostels, Residents, Shops, Hospital, Student recreation facilities, International student centres, Research Park, etc. are considered essential components. Physical infrastructure provides comfort facilities to the stakeholders. It can be built for (1) minimum requirement with basic facilities to fulfil the objectives of higher education, or (2) for a fair level to satisfy the stakeholders and differentiate to gain competitive advantage, or (3) for a luxurious level to establish monopoly and high impact on stakeholders as mentioned in table 4.

Table 4 : List of Physical infrastructure Requirements for a University

S. No.	Facility	Details of physical infrastructure
Minimum Requirements		
1	Green building	The buildings of the university should be constructed with principle of open environment by using optimum models of water & energy consumption. Use of green energy, harvested water, renewable and recycled resources to produce and provide clean air, water, & food, light, electricity indecently internally in the Campus.
2	Roads with walking, Motoring & bicycle path	Entre Campus buildings should be surrounded by high quality motoring roads and bicycle paths to allow both students and staff to use bicycles or battery based vehicles for commuting inside the campus.
3	Admission & Counselling Area	Adequate amount of Admission & Counselling Area is required to conduct admission tests/ personal interviews.
4	Classrooms	Classrooms of different size with comfortable seating arrangements and teaching-learning facilities should be available to accommodate 120, 80, 60, 40, & 12 students.
5	Counselling rooms	Student counselling rooms of different size with comfortable seating arrangements and teaching-learning facilities should be available to accommodate 20, 12, & 5 students.
6	Strong Room	Strong Room of adequate size to accommodate confidential documents & question papers for examination sections.
10	Faculty chambers	Adequate number of well equipped faculty chambers to accommodate all permanent faculty members, visiting faculty members, part-time faculty members, Research scholars, etc.
11	Meeting rooms	Meeting rooms of sufficient size for 10 to 20 Participants with furniture and Electronic communication/presentation facilities.
12	Laboratories	State-of-the art laboratories along with advanced super specialty research centres in selected scientific and technological areas.
13	Computer Centre	1: 4 :: Computer: Student Ratio
14	Cafeteria	Clean, neat, and adequate in size
15	Dining Room	For 10 People, 30 people, and 90 people size.
18	Games & Sports facility	Indoor Stadium of sufficient size to accommodate variety of games.
19	Auditorium	One auditorium of sufficient size.
20	Library/Digital resource centre	Adequate in size with reading rooms, stock areas for books & Journals with online information access facility.

21	Xerox & Printing centre	Student amenity (40 Sq. M.)
22	Hostels	For at least 60 % students
23	Parking	Adequate to fulfil the requirements of all stakeholders
24	Office Rooms	Adequate to fulfil the requirement of all staff members
25	Exhibition Hall	Adequate in number to fulfil the requirement of all co-curricular activities
26	Guest House	Adequate for university requirement
Fair Requirements		
27	Faculty Residents	2 – 3 Bedrooms
28	Shops	For students and staff to purchase essential items
29	Hospital	A modern round the clock functioning hospital with inpatient and outpatient facility
30	Student recreation facilities	Adequate with modern touch
31	Yoga & Meditation Centre	Adequate with traditional touch
32	Faculty Cubicals	Adequate in number to fulfil the demand
33	Departmental Libraries	Adequate in size with reference books & online digital information resources
34	Students Waiting Room (Male)	Adequate in size
35	Student Waiting Room (Female)	Adequate in size
36	Faculty & Staff Quarters	Adequate in number (1-2 Bedrooms)
37	Guest Hostels	Star hotel type with accommodation, food, and recreation facility
38	Research Scholars Hostels	Adequate in numbers with contemporary facilities
Luxury Requirements		
39	Central Air Conditioned High Tech Buildings	With modern clean-green environmental concept
40	Faculty Chamber with attached washroom for each faculty	Ambient & adequate in number
41	Studios	Modern studio with optimum sound control & recording facilities
42	Gymnastics	With sufficient size & modern facilities
43	International student centres	With contemporary student amenities
44	Research park	With in-house industry R & D units & collaboration
45	International Student Hostels	Adequate in size & number with aesthetically built modern facilities
46	High Tech Playgrounds	Adequate
47	Swimming Pool	Modern type with multiple user facilities
48	Shopping Complex	Adequate
49	Stadium	Modern type
50	Indoor Stadium	Modern type
51	Botanical Park	Natural type

Even though, an appropriate physical infrastructure with adequate facilities is essential to attract admissions of students, it cannot offer a competitive advantage to the university continuously over a long time because competitors can also develop better infrastructure with more luxurious facilities to attract students and teachers to the system quickly by finding an appropriate investor. Physical infrastructure

(2) Digital Infrastructure :

The digital infrastructure helps all stakeholders to simplify their job and to make their contribution effective. All information related to the HEI including about the organization, about academic programmes, about admissions, about academics, examinations & evaluations, about faculty & research, about industry collaborations & placements, about student activities, etc. are ubiquitously available globally through digital infrastructure. The various supporting facilities to enhance the effectiveness of the services and to minimize the time spent to avail such services by different stakeholders. The following table 5 lists various types of digital infrastructure required for a university to be considered as world-class university.

Table 5 : Lists various types of digital infrastructure required for a university

S. No.	Types of digital infrastructure	Details of digital infrastructure & its usage
1	Internet usage	Connecting external world to the stakeholders through an electronic device.
2	Website	For providing institutional information to the publics
3	WhatsApp groups of stakeholders	For vertical and horizontal communication between Stakeholders
4	Google Blogs & Google sites for every course	To provide course information and day to day progress of the students who enrolled to the course to stakeholders and publics.
5	Wi-Fi Campus	To access online ubiquitous information in the campus and classes.
6	Online Study material	Development of study materials both in audio, video, and text form as per the curriculum and providing them to concerned students online as additional support to classroom teaching – learning process. The study material in the form of PDF book to be stored in smart phone, tablet, or laptop computer will help ubiquitous reference for the covered portion of the course subjects.
7	Digital Library	Developing and updating digital library and providing digital library membership to every stakeholder of the university for ubiquitous access of books, periodicals, study materials, magazines, annual/year books of organizations, journals in digital form is the responsibility of University digital library. For this purpose, the University digital library can collaborate national digital library and Global digital libraries.
8	Digital Publication	The university should have its own publication for books, newsletters, magazines, journals,

		proceedings, and printing question papers for examinations. Online digital publication as open access publication globally is the best practice.
9	Paperless office	By developing academic administrative software the university should provide online office environment to cater the services of stakeholders.
10	Paperless exams	Adopting digital examination system eliminates the wastage of papers in examination process.
11	Online Evaluation	Automated & digitized online evaluation system eliminates the wastage of time of evaluators & speed up the evaluation process.
12	Website based result announcement	Ubiquitous reachability.
13	NAD markscards Facility	A convenient and completely secure <i>digital academic depository</i> solution.
14	Online admission test	A ubiquitous facility for global admission
15	Education ERP	To integrate various departments of the university for timely exchange & access of information.
16	Plagiarism software facility	A software facility available to every stakeholder to check plagiarism content in the documents.
17	Online digital magazine & Student publication	In online digital format through University publication.
18	Online placement (Project, internship, & final)	Online ubiquitous support.
19	Video documentation of each course & each College	For open information access from globally
20	Video documentation in U-Tube	For open information access from globally
21	Facebook and Twitter based promotions	Information access & Brand building promotions
22	Use of ICCT underlying technologies like AI, BA, CC, DS, MB, OC, VR & AR	Adopting present technologies in automating the services
23	Studio for video online classes	Studio for digitization of sound and scene
24	Video conference facility	For global information exchange in digital format
25	Online open Publication system	For exchange of new knowledge generated to everybody through open excess system

(3) Innovative academic Infrastructure :

Academic infrastructure is the most important infrastructure among all. It is the main purpose of the education system and decides the quality of teaching-learning process. An innovative academic infrastructure also decides the quality of the output students of the university. Table 6 lists various components of innovative academic infrastructure required for a university for growth and prosper.

Table 6 : Lists various components of innovative academic infrastructure required for a university

S. No.	Types of Innovative academic infrastructure	Details of innovative academic infrastructure & its usage
1	Industry oriented curriculum	To meet the present and future demands of the industry
2	Employability skill focussed curriculum	For increasing employability of the graduates
3	Speciality & super speciality professional courses	Students can go deep in a specified subjects based on their interest and hence further growth in such areas are possible.
4	Experienced committed faculty	Experienced and committed faculty is the asset of the organization and are the motivators of students to involve in research to create new knowledge or to do innovations.
5	Session wise teaching plan	Systematic planning in teaching and learning process is required which includes session wise teaching plan and following such teaching plan.
6	Study books prepared as per the syllabus,	To provide equal amount of essential information to all the students in a class it is essential to provide study books prepared as per the syllabus of the subject.
7	Question bank	Question bank is a book containing all possible questions prepared as per the examination pattern. Such question bank eliminates the chance of asking questions out of the syllabus.
8	QB answers as assignments	The students are encouraged to work more by answering all question bank questions in the form of assignments. Periodic assignment submission with due date and offering internal marks systematically will enhances the responsibility of doing their work in right time.
9	Make-up exams	Students should be given enough opportunities to show their talents. Similarly, due to different reasons, if a student fail to take an exam or fail to perform well in the exam he should be given another opportunity without loss a year and so.
10	Value added employability skills enhancement Papers	Apart from core and elective papers in each semester, the university should identify some general skills required based on professional requirement and enhancing employability of the students. These skill development based value added papers should be offered as separate papers and taught by industry or professional people in the field.
11	Experimental learning pedagogy	The teaching – learning pedagogy should contain substantial amount of experimental learning part related to their specialization trough either real

		environment or virtual environment.
12	Co-curricular & extracurricular activities	These activities supports all-round development of students and enhances their competency and confidence in facing any challenges.
13	Earn while learn facility & flexibility	Earn while learn model has dual objectives : it gives working skills for a student with responsibility and it also supports financial needs of a student so that he need not depend on his parents for his pocket money.
14	Multi-skill development & certification opportunities	The university, by using its academic autonomy, should design the UG & PG courses in such a way that students should be offered many opportunities in all areas of STEAM for multi-skill development. Additional certificate programmes across the field may be offered.
15	Provision of optimum utilization of time to develop liberal arts skills	The regular class times should be planned optimally in order to provide sufficient time for liberal arts skills training so that students develop additional skills with them by involving in inculcating cultural and traditional skills which enhances their design thinking ability.
16	Provision of opportunities to develop & utilize Research & innovative thinking skills.	The UG & PG curriculum should be designed in such a way that there must be enough research components which allows students to work for their projects independently under the guidance of their research guide either individually or in a team. Such effort enhances the innovative ability of students and increases their competency and confidence.
17	Academic activity to build confidence	Academic support to raise knowledge, skills, attitude, and experience based competency to improve confidence in doing innovation.
18	Co-curricular activities to mould good character for social benefit	Co-curricular actives in teams or groups related to social work and social contribution also moulds good character and team working skills of the students and incorporates collective responsibility in them.
19	Special training in Event management & disaster management training	Irrespective of specialization and type of Course, every student at UG level get special training on event management & disaster management training as a part of their curriculum to prepare them in public program execution and to face natural calamities.
20	Compulsory Environmental Science Education	To create awareness to carry the clean, green, and peace environment to the next generation.

(4) Intellectual property infrastructure :

The university can prosper for longer time and establish name and fame at international level only if it focuses on enhancing intellectual property infrastructure. A research university by

objective has opportunity to contribute intellectual property of the country by focussing research and innovation leading to new knowledge creation. A list of various components of intellectual property infrastructure required for a university is shown in table 7.

Table 7: Lists various components of intellectual property infrastructure required for a university

S. No.	Types of intellectual property infrastructure	Details of intellectual property infrastructure & its generation
1	Research oriented experienced faculty members	Research oriented faculty members are usually research inclined. They motivate students and other faculty members to involve in research and innovation which adds intellectual property infrastructure of the university.
2	API based faculty compensation	Developing and implementing an Academic Performance Indicator (API) score based faculty compensation system stimulates faculty interest in participating research & publication activities. API based compensation creates healthy competition among the faculty members for accelerated IP contribution.
3	Targeted research	The university identifies some emerging areas in different subjects and supports the expert faculties in those areas to do research and to publish papers as well as patents. This is called targeted research and the university can create IPR as well as international brand through such efforts.
4	Atomic Research centres for each faculty	This is an innovative idea and best practice to be followed by Universities. Here, each faculty member identifies one or more area of research interest and develop an atomic research centre in his/her coordinate-ship. The centre develops the objective of the proposed research centre, methodology, and Expected outcome along with list of working papers, list of published papers in journals & proceedings. The centre may contain a list of researchers including coordinator, internal collaborators, and student members.
5	More Ph.D. & post doctoral research scholars	The university must admit more research scholars within its capacity of support. The university should use its autonomy to appoint more research professors (might be retired from regular services) only for guiding research scholars. University should also develop post doctoral research programmes to keep the doctoral graduates in sustained research contribution.
6	More Faculty members with Ph.D.	The university should implement a policy of increasing number of Ph.D. degree holders in its faculty group. In addition to serving as teaching faculty, the Ph.D. degree holders also available for guiding the research scholars for Ph.D. programmes.
7	Faculty encouragement for Book Publications, Research Publications,	In order to improve the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of the university, the university should have the policy to encourage IPR contributors who are none other than UG

	and Patents	& PG Students, Research scholars, and Faculty members. Based on implementing conducive policies to encourage research and publications at all above levels university can enhance its IPR infrastructure. Varieties incentives and supporting schemes will help such a mission.
8	More conferences (At least two conferences per year per College)	Organizing research paper presentation conferences periodically keeps students, research scholars and faculty members create an opportunity to keep up targets and to compare them with other colleagues through networking.
9	Student involvement in Research	Students are the most important resources in the university system and if guided properly can do innovations by developing patentable inventions. Similarly, through systematic research, they can also come out with scholarly publishable results. By involving students at the graduate and postgraduate level, the university can boost its IPR infrastructure.
10	Industry collaboration & Consultation	Supports collaboration based research so that the university can create IPR along with industry personnel. This also gives the opportunity to use industry research facilities by university personnel. Further collaborative research leads to more patents & publications.
11	University Incubation centres	University Incubation centres supports students to plan to start their own business after graduation. Any ideas developed during project work or internship period can be nurtured and supported as a business proposal to initiate self employment.
12	University Publication through its own press	Many universities start own publication press to speed up their scholarly publications. This also simplifies or decreases the cost of publications and encourages the faculty members to make use of their press for publication of new knowledge created. Presently, digital and online publications are prevailing and considered as one of the most important strategies of world-class universities.
13	University publications & Citation service	As a facility to researchers, universities have started citation services to their faculty members and the stakeholders including public. This will further help researchers to enhance quality publications.
14	Compulsory patent claim for UG & PG projects in Professional subject areas	By fixing the target for UG & PG students for internship and continuously guiding & monitoring them for planning and applying for patents for their invention certainly improves the result.
15	Faculty Ranking (Annual) system	Announcement of annual faculty ranking based on API and grading them under different levels develops competitive spirit among them and faculty members continuously strive for excellence. In such cases, faculty monitoring at every stage can be reduced.

(5) Emotional infrastructure :

Creating a sense of belongingness with the organization essential for all stakeholders is essential. The major elements of emotional infrastructure are listed in table 8.

Table 8 : Lists various types of emotional infrastructure required for a university

S. No.	Types of emotional infrastructure	Details of emotional infrastructure & its generation
1	Acceptable leader as role-model	University must develop leaders who have shared vision of developing the university in a planned manner. The leader himself must be all-rounder and role-model in terms of motivating & target setting to others.
2	Trust among stakeholders and outsiders	University system should develop trust (self & mutual) among all stakeholders based on their commitment and contribution to the system.
3	Institutional values (Core values)	For example, (1) Team Work, (2) Respect, (3) Responsibility, (4) Ethics, (5) Etiquette, (6) Social service, (7) Character, Commitment, Competency, & Confidence, (8) Tech-savviness & Scientific thinking, (9) Quest for excellence, (10) Continuous improvement, and (11) Promotion of Open systems.
4	Institutional Rituals & Tradition	The objectives, values, rituals, and the tradition cultivated by the seniors of the institution from several years should be carried to further as an institutional culture to involve every stakeholder in strong emotional bondage. This improves the commitment of stakeholders to fulfill their responsibility towards organizational development.
5	Create rich communication channels	Information related to day-to-day activities, subject, and course based information, Information related to the evaluation of students & teachers should be openly available to respective stakeholders. Through the open system model, the university should try to provide the right information at the right time to its stakeholders. This enables the stakeholders to make an optimum decision towards the growth of the university. By using various features of Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), through a properly designed website and internal communication system, University can achieve this.
6	Alternative strategy & Support network	Stakeholder service is very important in gaining emotional support to the university. Thus to provide continuous services which are promised in the beginning must be provided in any situation. Accordingly, the university should think of an alternative strategy to fulfill promises. College facilities, Hostel facilities, food & drinking water

		facilities, transportation facilities, quality faculty members to cover the syllabus, conducting exams and announcement of results in time are very essential in an academic environment and require alternative strategy [38] and support network.
7	Set vision in every student	Goal setting in every student by creating awareness about opportunities is a major responsibility among students. The university system should motivate every student and identify the best among them and support to set a vision to prosper.
8	Safety & Security	The university should give priority in providing the hassle free ambience to every student. The safety and security are prime factors in the university campus for every stakeholder.
9	Search for proximity (Local friends. Local food, local culture)	Students usually search for proximity during the first year of their study. Seeking local friends, local food, local cultures are the common expectations among the students. University has the responsibility in creating such an environment to keep students not to feel loneliness.
10	Comfortability but need not luxury	The university should establish all facilities towards students basic needs and focus on providing students wants to ensure a certain level of comfortability in their campus life.
11	Legacy of the system	The university should carry further the traditions, cultures, and hence the legacy of the system by arranging the required number of such programmes, festivals, and other descent entertainment programs. The university also maintains organizational hierarchy in a dignified way.
12	Respect & perception about organization	The legacy of the system should be maintained in such a way that every individual stakeholder of a system should show positive perception about the university and respect heartily as their alma-matter.
13	Openness in terms of information	As a part of the emotional infrastructure of the university, it has to maintain openness and transparency in doing business. Openness & transparency in the admission process, academic teaching-learning processes, examination and evaluation system, research & publications, and investments & profitability are important.
14	Ability of the institution to fulfil the promises	One of the major challenges of higher education institutions is their inability to fulfil their own promises. Using autonomy of the university if it can solve its failures it can establish a good name in a short span of time.
15	Accountability measures	The university should adopt a system to check the accountability of every stakeholder and both

		positive incentives and negative punishments should be incorporated in the annual evaluation process.
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(6) Networked infrastructure :

Connecting with the industry, with the alumni, with other higher education & research institutions creates synergy for collective development. By means of properly planned collaborations and implementing the objective of collaboration leads to positive-sum game. Organizations which focus on effective networking can encash more opportunities for self and mutual developments along with their brand image. Collaboration and partnership with local, national, and global agencies can be used to support other infrastructures like innovative academic infrastructure, intellectual property infrastructure, and emotional infrastructure. Table 9 lists various components of networked infrastructure required for a university.

Table 9 : Lists various types of networked infrastructure required for a university

S. No.	Types of Networked infrastructure	Details of networked infrastructure & its creation
1	Collaborations – Horizontal, Vertical & Diversified	Student progress should be planned and implemented to support industries, further education institutions, and for the social upliftment based on collaborating and involving with these institutions. University should create a situation where the industries, other educational-research institutions, and the whole society feel emotionally the importance and contribution of the university to society.
2	Alumni association & Networks	Keeping the alumni with their alma-matter, involving them in university progress, involving them in resource mobilization, and using their services as mentors to existing students is an effective strategy to enhance the emotional infrastructure of the university.
3	Industry integrated collaborations	Industry integrated collaboration by updating syllabus of study as per industry requirement, providing industry skills by involving industry experts, supporting industry projects through industry internship, etc.
4	Academic Integrated Collaborations	Collaborating with other academic institutions which have developed their core competency in related academic areas by creating synergy so that students can opt their subject in different universities / institutions to get dual degrees or to complete research internships etc.
5	Research Collaborations	Research collaborations between neighbouring organizations strengthen networking among the stakeholders.
6	Consultancy Collaborations	The faculty members, based on their professional specialization, should be encouraged to work as

		consultants in industries. This will improve industry-institute relationship and networking leading to enhanced synergy.
7	Placement Collaborations	The university should develop networking with local, national, and international companies of many industry sectors both for training the students during the internship and to provide campus job placement services to ensure that the graduates of the university are employable.
8	Collaborations for student - Earn While Learn model	As a new trend in higher education, the university should encourage the students to work during their free time to get working experience and at least to earn their pocket money through earn while learn model.
9	Collaborations with NGOs & Social service Organizations	The university should also work in close with various NGOs & social service organizations using its students and staff members. Such collaboration and networking with NGOs provide social service and fieldwork opportunities to the students of the university.
10	Membership with National & International Accreditation bodies for Quality & Credibility	The university should also improve its quality service by means of educational innovations and best practices. The quality and credibility of the organization can be verified by its recognition by national and international accreditation bodies.

6. INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES :

6.1 How to develop Physical Infrastructure :

Physical infrastructure can be developed to any extent by investing in huge financial investment. By identifying investors as partners, a university in the private sector can create large and essential infrastructure. But due to preset heavy competition in the higher education service business, huge investment by means of borrowing money from lenders/banks with high annual interest is not viable. Many organizations in HEIs/universities have identified political leaders/Bureaucrats as partners for the investment of unaccounted money. Creating huge attractive infrastructure can support brand building initially, but the competitors can also follow such investment model and compete for the institution so that in larger scale this infrastructure may not give any differentiation advantage. Physical infrastructure should support both academic and research activities of various schools and departments of the universities. In public universities, the physical infrastructure investment is done by the government through various independent authorities whereas, in private universities, the decision is taken by sponsoring organization. Since the physical infrastructure can add value but in long term, it may not create differentiation due to the fact that any competitor university can also develop huge infrastructure during a small interval of time as a counter strategy. The list of physical infrastructure given in table 4 can be developed by any university within one or two years if they get suitable investment partner.

6.2. How to develop Digital Infrastructure :

Digital infrastructure includes a paperless office system using automatic learning management system which includes digital information processing of all teaching, learning, examination, and evaluation activities. All the stakeholders get online information from both push and pull format. The university website centered admission process, payment of all fees by the students and faculty compensation are in digital payment format. Digital infrastructure of a university can be improved by implementing educational ERP/LMS, Having a dynamic website, Online teaching systems, paperless environment, computerized examination and evaluation system, Digitized marks cards/credit score cards, online e-placement supporting systems, online alumni networking, etc. The university needs one to two years to digitize its infrastructure either by its own efforts or by outsourcing digitization work for an internationally experiences information technology enabled services organization.

6.3. How to develop Innovative academic Infrastructure :

Innovative academic infrastructure can be developed by means of various innovative academic activities for creating innovators by means of Planning, Implementation, Evaluation, Feedback, & Self-study report. The following steps may be helpful for developing innovative academic infrastructure :

- (1) Institutional SWOC analysis.
- (2) Developing best practices by doing ABCD analysis.
- (3) Developing future strategy through predictive analysis.
- (4) Creating & retaining a strong faculty base through faculty performance analysis.
- (5) Using appropriate industry experts in curriculum design & implementation.
- (6) Developing leaders as role models through commitment & multi-tasking analysis.
- (7) Developing students by offering confidence building education model through student integrated development model.
- (8) Growth & expansion of the university through environmental analysis.

To optimize the academic infrastructure, the university needs 3 to 5 years time once it decides to invest in innovative academic structure. The academic infrastructure should provide unique teaching-learning model developed by the university as student integrated development model [39] to enhance their employability and innovability.

6.4 How to develop Intellectual property Infrastructure :

Development of intellectual property infrastructure is one of the biggest challenges for a university. A university can enhance its intellectual property infrastructure by implementing many strategies which include :

- (1) Involving all stakeholders in research, innovation, & documentation in the form of scholarly publication.
- (2) Developing a culture of innovative thinking through research & contribution to society.
- (3) Promoting institutional research in a systematic manner with high performance and output but low cost.
- (4) Having collaboration with many universities and research centres locally and globally to enhance joint research and publications.
- (5) Inviting industry as a partner to support their research & development activities and intern gaining in IR infrastructure.
- (6) Focusing equally on Research programmes leading M.Phil., M.Sc./M.Tech./M.S.(By research), Ph.D., Postdoctoral certificates, Postdoctoral degrees like D.Sc., D.Litt., etc. with compulsory Journal publication & patents/ copyrights.

(7) Encouraging faculty members through incentives to bid for government & industry funded research projects.

(8) Through university policy, motivating faculty members through faculty ranking based on research based API scores and subsequent additional incentives.

Since developing intellectual property infrastructure is long term activity and depends on many factors, universities take a long time to establish in this area, usually 10 to 15 years to reach substantial amount even if they are fully focused on such activities. The most appropriate way of calculating the IPR infrastructure for a given time duration is proposed in ABC Model of Organizational Performance [40-41].

6.5 How to develop Emotional Infrastructure :

Creation of emotional surplus with respect to employees and customers is a big challenge for every organization. Universities also should strive for emotional surplus as their essential infrastructure in order to accelerate their growth. Providing a good working environment for all stakeholders with ethical policies and transparent academic and administrative system and giving extra care in all service area of both higher education and research activities are the necessary and sufficient conditions for developing emotional infrastructure in the HEI organizations. Creating a substantial amount of emotional infrastructure for a university takes long time since it has to prove its long time credibility & identity through its dedicated and committed service to the society. Some of the strategies which support to develop emotional surplus as emotional infrastructure in universities are listed below :

- (1) All regulations related to various services should be framed from learner centric.
- (2) Honest effort of providing transparency in administration with democratic touch.
- (3) Leaders should be visionary and have inherent intention to treat every stakeholder as the family member.
- (4) Atmosphere to be created to build mutual trust and respect between stakeholders.
- (5) Develop an institutional tradition and culture from local tradition and culture.
- (6) Develop core values of commitment, dedication, and service among all stakeholders.
- (7) Create a system where everybody should know their responsibility and struggle to achieve it.
- (8) Create a system where every stakeholder gets security and justice.
- (9) Openness & transparency in all administrative decisions.
- (10) Accountability based on job description at all levels of the university.
- (11) University social responsibility for economically weaker sections.

To create emotional infrastructure in substantial amount and use it as a resource for brand creation, the university has to make sustainable efforts for long time period. Most of the existing universities all along the world with more than 100 years existence have advantage in accumulating emotional infrastructure compared to recently started universities. However, using innovative strategies, it should be possible for the present generation universities to create substantial emotional infrastructure for a time period of 10 to 30 years.

6.6 How to develop Networked Infrastructure :

Through effective networking with industries, other HEIs and various research organizations, universities can prosper and develop as one among world leader. The network collaborative model should have a systematic plan of involving industry experts in teaching-learning process. Starting from planning the courses and the subjects, developing the curriculum, collaborative training, collective evaluation, and offering employment, industry-institute interaction has the opportunity to add value to their services. Connecting with the industry,

with the alumni, with other higher education & research institutions creates synergy for collective development.

The following steps may be helpful for developing networking infrastructure for universities and HEIs:

- (1) Universities should realize that they are by the society and for the society so that by working with more organizations in a team, they can fulfil their objectives and contribute substantially for the society.
- (2) Involving alumni in close confidence in many processes, universities can get huge benefit for their brand building exercise.
- (3) Identifying and involving various industries which provide internship and employment opportunities in curriculum design.
- (4) Networking with student feeding institutions by means of involving/admitting faculty members of such institutions in university research programmes.
- (5) Collaborating with national and international universities for joint research & publications, Credit transfer Courses, Dual degree programmes, etc.

By means of properly planned collaborations and implementing the objective of collaboration leads to a positive-sum game. Organizations which focus on effective networking can encash more opportunities for self and mutual developments along with their brand image. Collaboration and partnership with local, national, and global agencies can be used to support other infrastructures like innovative academic infrastructure, intellectual property infrastructure, and emotional infrastructure.

The estimated time period required for development of the essential infrastructures for a university in a private sector where the board of directors have autonomy to make investment decision is shown in Table 10.

Table 10 : Time period required to develop various infrastructure optimally

S. No	Essentials infrastructures for attaining Excellence	Time period required for reaching optimum level
1	Physical Infrastructure	02 - 03 years
2	Digital Infrastructure	01 - 02 years
3	Innovative academic Infrastructure	03 - 05 years
4	Intellectual Property Infrastructure	10 - 15 years
5	Emotional Infrastructure	10 - 30 years
6	Networked Infrastructure	05 - 10 years

7. CONCLUSION :

The important essential infrastructures required for a growing university to emerge itself as a world-class university are discussed. It is postulated that the six essential assets to be developed by a university based on predictive analysis for the accelerated growth and prosper as world-class university are (1) Physical infrastructure, (2) Digital infrastructure, (3) Innovative academic & training Infrastructure for confidence building, (4) Intellectual property infrastructure, (5) Emotional infrastructure, and (6) Networked infrastructure. The study focuses on various components of these infrastructures and how to develop these infrastructures for growing universities along with the essential objectives in detail. The various generic strategies to be followed to develop such infrastructures along the lifecycle of the university including Survival, Sustainability, Differentiation, and Growth & prosperity

are analysed. The necessary and sufficient conditions of developing such infrastructures using all the above strategies towards building World-class universities are identified.

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A STUDY ON THE WORKING CONDITIONS AND OCCUPATIONAL PROBLEMS OF TAXI DRIVERS IN MANGALORE CITY

Pinto Vincent*, D'Mello Laveena**

*Freston Knowledge Foundation®, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail:

Vincentpinto79@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

Taxi drivers are susceptible to many types of problems and issues. The major problems faced by them include unpredictability of pay, long hours of work and health related problems. The customers perceive that the only thing they have to do is drive around and give rides, but even though this job is simple in theory, the day-to-day working conditions of these taxi drivers are actually quite stressful. In order to find out the intricacies of the work life of the taxi drivers of Mangalore city, this study is conducted. The research design adopted by the investigator is exploratory and descriptive in nature. Accidental sampling technique was used for the selection of the respondents. A structured interview schedule was used to elicit the required information. The results of the study reveal that the respondents develop pain on the body, sleeplessness and eyesight related problems due to the nature of their work. They also have developed bad habits like drinking, smoking or tobacco chewing. Road accidents and lack of safety were considered the major occupational risk by the respondents. The study also points out that few respondents also have faced problems from police and other law enforcement authorities. Competition from their own co-workers was also felt by some of the respondents. The study suggests that there is a need for sensitizing general public about the working condition and work life of the taxi drivers. It also suggests that awareness programs need to be conducted among this group also about health, safety and security of life.

Keywords: Taxi drivers, work life, health, habits, sensitization and Working conditions.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Prevalence of a good urban transportation system can ease a lot of other urban problems like housing, shopping centers and industrial locations. On the contrary lack of it could accentuate the problems to a greater degree. Urban transport of Udupi is exceptional in several ways to that of other cities of the state, and without exaggeration of the country. For a city of Udupi size and economy the city bus services both private and public are really extra ordinary. But it does not mean that Udupi city bus services are beyond reproach and problems. Taxis are very less in number. This is due to small geographical area of Udupi, as also due to cheap and efficient transport provided first by the city buses and secondly by auto rickshaws. As a large number of passengers do not use taxis in the urban transportation of the Udupi, their

study is eliminated by most researchers. But we should hasten to add that in Udupi taxis especially private taxis are playing highly appreciable role in the short distance inter-city transport of Udupi. They travel between Mangalore-Udupi, Udupi-Manipal; Udupi-Kundapur-Batkal is highly facilitated by these bank financed private taxis. Due to petrol price hike these taxi drivers are facing their own problems. This intercity taxi service deserves a separate study of its own.

2. WORKING CONDITIONS OF THE TAXI DRIVER:

Industrialization and urbanization brought about the migration of a large number of the people from village to towns. As job opportunities increased, the number of workers too increased in these areas. This naturally brought about an increased demand for traffic. Hence a good number of people find it advantage to take driving as their profession and become taxi drivers. Good drivers are familiar with streets in the areas they serve so they can choose the most efficient route to destinations and avoid traffic. They know the locations of frequently requested destinations, such as airports, bus and railroad terminals, convention centers, hotels, and other points of interest. In case of emergency, drivers should know the location of fire and police stations, as well as hospitals. Taxi drivers are under a lot of stress during their shift being a taxi cab driver sounds like an easy gig. After all, the only things they have to do is drive around and give people rides, But even though this job is simple in theory, the day-to-day working conditions of cab drivers are actually quite stressful.

3. CHALLENGES:

Pay is Unpredictable: Taxi drivers do not earn a regular paycheck or an hourly wage. Instead, they are paid based on the number of fares they get. Drivers usually use a meter to charge their customers based on time and distance, and one trip counts as a single fare. Since the number of fares a driver might get in one day can vary greatly, a taxi driver is never sure of how much money he'll make.

Long Hours and Limited Mobility: Not only do taxi drivers work eight-hour to 12-hour shifts, they also move very little during the day. Cab drivers sit in their seats for almost their entire shift; because they need to pick up as many fares as possible, some only get up to use the bathroom a few times during the day or to get gas. Taxi drivers don't even have to get up to eat, since they can use fast food drive-thru windows without having to stop the taxi.

Negative Effects on Health: Speaking of fast food, taxi cab drivers are prone to health problems due to their diets and limited movement. They are prone to heart problems, musculoskeletal and digestive system disorders, hemorrhoids, and fatigue. Many cab drivers have obesity too.

Crime: Taxi drivers are susceptible to many types of crime. Robbery is common, and drivers can also be victims of things such as murder, rape, car thefts, and hit-and-run accidents. Because cab drivers are constantly on the go, they are easy targets for criminals. Vehicle break downs, adverse weather, and other traffic risks are also faced by them.

Employment Change: Because the demand for taxi services is very sensitive to economic cycles, drivers may see declining demand for their services during economic downturns. Taxi drivers who work for private companies or individuals may face layoffs or reduced hours during times of economic distress. Opportunities fluctuate significantly with the overall

movements of the economy, because the demand for transportation depends on business travel and tourism.

4. METHODOLOGY:

The investigator has met with a few of the taxi drivers of Mangalore city and found that most of them spend a great deal of time away from their homes, usually eating their meals in hotels. Under such conditions it is likely that this particular section of the community would have certain needs and problems. Thus to conduct a study on the working conditions and its related problems was considered necessary, so as to attempt to evolve plans for the amelioration of their conditions. This present study is the result of an ardent desire on the part of the investigator to find out the real work-life conditions of taxi drivers, so as to provide suggestions for their improvement.

Aim: The main aim of the study was to understand the working conditions and problems of taxi drivers in Udupi. And the objectives are: To study the personal profile of the respondents; To find out the problems faced by taxi drivers in relation to their job-pertaining to relationship with commuters, co-workers and law enforcing authorities; To examine the socio-economic conditions of taxi drivers; To study their health problems; and to find ways and means to improve their work and service life situation.

Materials and Method: The research design adopted by the investigator is exploratory and descriptive. This research design suits the present study as the investigator tried to explore their problems with regard to their working conditions and problems. For this study, the investigator has made use of accidental or convenience sampling technique. According to this study system, a sample is selected according to the convenience of the researcher, considering the nature of the respondents' work, that their services are asked by the public at any time and having no fixed hours of work or leisure time, made it necessary for the investigator to choose accidental or convenience sampling technique. An interview schedule was the principal tool in collecting the necessary data. The schedule was administered by personal interviews with the respondents. The interviews were conducted at bus stands, on the road sides, near hotels, where the respondents could be available, while waiting for their passengers.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The data analysis of the study reveals certain significant aspects, which are termed to be the major finding of the study. It has been found that 34percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years of age. Another finding reveals that a certain group of taxi drivers are above the age of 70 years. Majority (64percent) of the respondents are Hindus. Majority (82percent) of the respondents are part of nuclear families. There is considerable number of the employees who belongs to joint families too. Majority (46percent) of the respondents have acquired general or formal education. None of the respondents were illiterate. The study reveals that 76 percent of the respondents were married and 2 percent of the respondents were widowers. Findings reveal that the average number of members in each of the respondents' families is 4-6. Majority 44 percent of the respondents' spouses were housewives. The study clearly shows that 36 percent of them do not have any children and 34 percent of them have 2 children. The investigator has found that the total monthly income of all respondents is above Rupees 3000. While 32 percent of the respondents' families earn Rupees 20001-30000, 26

percent of the respondents' families earn Rupees 10001-20000. The study shows that a majority (32percent) of the taxi drivers have worked in similar jobs before taking up this profession, like auto rickshaw drivers, bus drivers, etc. Some of the respondents have been taxi drivers and not held any other type of profession. Majority (76percent) of respondents had below 10yrs of experiences in their previous jobs and 14percent of the respondents have between 11-20yrs of experience, as made known in this study.

Duration of Present Job and Earning from the Present Job: Every individual is expected to be committed to the jobs that they perform. Certain jobs are sought after for the payment received while certain others are undertaken out of personal interest. When a person takes up a job only on the basis of pay, it is highly possible that if encountered with an opportunity to earn more he/she will move on to such jobs. (*Table 1: Duration of present Job*)

The above data indicates the duration of present job and salary of present job, the majority of

Duration of present job	Earning from the present job			
	5000-10000	10001-15000	15001-20000	TOTAL
Below 10YRS	12 (38.71%)	19 (61.29%)	0	31 (100%)
11-20YRS	4 (36.36%)	5 (45.46%)	2 (18.18%)	11 (100%)
21-30YRS	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	0	4 (100%)
31-40YRS	0	2 (100%)	0	2(100%)
41-50YRS	2 (100%)	0	0	2(100%)
TOTAL	20 (40%)	28 56%)	2 (4%)	50(100%)

the respondents (62%) were having 1month to10 years of experience, 22 percent of them were experienced 11 to 20yrs and 8percent of the respondents were experienced 21-30 years and Four percent respectively were experienced 31-40yrs and 41-50years. Majority of the respondents (56%) were earning Rupees 10001-15000 per month whereas 20 respondents (40%) of them were earning only up to Rupees 5000-10000 per month and remaining two percent of them were earning 15001-20000 Rupees per month. Further a vast majority of the respondents (62%) have an experience of 1month to10years and these taxi drivers are earning Rupees 10001-15000per month. A contradiction is observed in the study is that the drivers having an experience of one month to 10 years were earning more income than the experienced drivers with more than 10years of experience. It draws a conclusion that the income earned may or may not depend on the years of experience of the taxi drivers.

Distribution of Health Related Problems and Handling Health Problems: Taxi driving is not just as easy as it seems. It involves a lot of concentrations and stiff body control the frequency of stress, working condition etc leading to body ailments like pains and aches, sleeplessness and so on. The job also involves a lot of commitment and working hard at times, especially during the seasons, one cannot afford to take rest at home for several reasons like loan, debt, expenses at home, dependents etc. (*Table 2:Health related problem and handling health related problem*)

Health problems	Handling Health Related Problem			
	Nothing till now	Taking Rest	Treatment	Total
Nothing till now	27 (100%)	0	0	27(100%)
Pains and Aches	0	3 (23.07%)	10 (76.92%)	13 (100%)
Sleeplessness	0	5 (100%)	0	5(100%)
Eye Sight	0	0	5(100%)	5(100%)
Total	27 (54%)	8 (16%)	15 (30%)	50 (100%)

The above table shows the health problem faced by the respondents and measures taken for handling them. It is learnt that 27 respondents who forms the majority have not faced health problem till now due to their job and this corresponds with the majority of 27 taxi drivers who say that they have not taken any measures of handling health problems. While 13 respondents experience pains and aches, further 5 taxi drivers have suffered from sleeplessness because of the nature of their job and 5 respondents have developed eye sight related problems. Of the 23 respondents, 15 respondents have availed treatment of some sort and 8 taxi drivers have preferred to take rest to solve their health problems.

Opinion about Habits Developed: Sometimes due to stress, bad company kept among colleagues one tends to develop socially unacceptable habits or bad habits that can lead to several problems related to social, personal, health and finance.

DIAGRAM NO: 1a

The above graphs reveals that 50percent of the respondents (25) have not developed any bad habits in their period of working, whereas 20percent of the respondents (10) started tobacco chewing as taxi drivers since they were sometimes required to work during night shifts and tobacco keeps them from falling asleep and 16percent of the respondents developed smoking habits and 14percent of them developed drinking habit in their work life. Along with all these

some respondents have also developed habits of intermingling with the other taxi drivers, making friends' which tends to bring unity among all the taxi drivers.

Job Related Risks: The risks faced by the taxi drivers are immense. Bad roads are the cause for several fatal accidents and deaths, bad street lighting, environmental conditions like landscape, heavy rainfall or even uprooted trees fallen on roads cause major risks. At times technical problem like vehicle breakdowns, tire punctures is also possible.

DIAGRAM NO: 2a

The above line graph reveals that the job related risks faced by the respondents in respect to their job. Here 44 percent of the respondents believe road accidents were the biggest risk, while 38percent of the respondents have not come across any risks from the beginning up till now whereas 16 percent of the respondents consider lack of safety to be risky especially during vehicle breakdowns, use of the car for robbery by customers. No job is risk free, be it the nature of the job or any other feature that is concerned with the job like travelling and so on. In a job concerned with transportation, safety on road becomes the biggest cause of anxiety, for both passengers and drivers.

6. OTHER PROBLEMS:

The investigator has found out that 22percent of the respondents face problems of competition from co-workers whereas 62percent of the respondents said they have no such problem. A majority (84percent) of the respondents does not face problems from law enforcement authorities but 8percent respondents reported that they are at times subjected to unnecessary inspection by the police and have been asked to pay fines for reasons like not wearing uniforms and so on. A majority (84percent) of the respondents does not face problems from law enforcement authorities but 8percent respondents reported that they are at times subjected to unnecessary inspection by the police and have been asked to pay fines for reasons like not wearing uniforms and so on. A relatively small percentage that is 20percent of respondents has a problem with the Road Transport Officer for high payment of taxes.

7. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Man has been working since time immemorial. The urge to work seems to be deep rooted in most men and work is viewed as much more than a means of seeking economic gratification.

- 1) There is a need for sensitizing the general public towards taxi drivers and the work they perform.
- 2) Awareness among the general public has to be created to treat the taxi drivers as human beings and not as the slaves while hiring the taxi and to respect and co-operate with the taxi drivers for ensuring better hospitality and services from them.
- 3) Awareness among the taxi drivers should be created so that they can develop a friendly and humane approach towards the customers in order to deal with them effectively.
- 4) Taxi drivers need to be sensitized about the legal provisions and the legal compliances.
- 5) They need to form associations through which they can take better actions on tackling problems they face, especially during night shifts like lack of proper road lights, bad roads, etc by appealing as a whole to the competent authorities.
- 6) There should be proper co-ordination between the government authorities (like Police, Road Transportation Officer) to ensure smooth functioning of the taxi drivers profession.
- 7) In order to prevent exploitation by the government officials there should be measures imposed in order to bring about transparency in the system.

9. CONCLUSION

The study successfully brings to fore beyond doubt, the working conditions and problems of the taxi drivers in Mangalore city. Taxi driving as a profession is not much important today as it is believed to be a job that a person would take up as a last resort and not as career. However taxi drivers do form an important part of the professional world, for everyone requires their transportation facility at one point of time or the other. They too face lot of constraints in the course of their work. It includes problems of night shift, transport authorities and whole lot of physical ailments. This study has made an attempt to bring to light the general work conditions of taxi drivers in Mangalore city and the problems they face while on duty. The Major risk they face from their profession is fear of accidents. It is important that there should be some sort of training and awareness programs conducted for these drivers so that, they can manage the hardships of life.

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INNOVATION IN ENGINEERING CURRICULUM AS B.TECH. (HONS) BY INTEGRATING STEAM, ESEP & IPR

P. S. Aithal¹, & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal²

¹College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail: psaithal@gmail.com

Abstract

Innovation in course curriculum is a continuous process in the higher education system (HES). As the amount of published information growing with time at geometric progression, it is necessary to increase the depth and breadth of the HES curriculum of every course with time. Engineering education is one of the prominent areas in science & technology education, finding many opportunities and facing many challenges in the 21st century due to the accelerated advancement of technologies in many areas. Keeping students in pace with such developments and adopting such newly emerging areas of technology in the current curriculum is an essential requirement of the education industry's progress. In this paper, we have proposed improvement in engineering education in India at the undergraduate level by means of six innovations to improve the depth, breadth, and vigorousness of the B.Tech. programme by suggesting a Student integrated development Framework in engineering based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning. The six innovations proposed in this model upgrades the B.Tech. (Pass) programme into B.Tech. (Honours).

Keywords : B.Tech. degree, B.Tech. (Hons), Engineering curriculum, STEM, STEAM, Employability skill enhancement program (ESEP), Experimental learning, STEAM-Employability Model.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Higher education system (HES) has an objective of improving the knowledge, skills, experience, & ethics of students towards increasing their confidence to identifying and solving problems of the society through effective and contemporary education using a suitable teaching-learning model [1]. Innovation in course curriculum is a continuous feature in the higher education system. As the amount of published information growing with time at geometric progression, it is necessary to increase the depth and breadth of the HES curriculum of every course with time. This also involves in removing obsolete part of the curriculum without hesitation to give room for new and emerging issues in the course subjects. Upgrading HE curriculum by adding area based specific focus models like STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), and STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts & design, and Mathematics) are the current trend in both secondary and

college education system. It is believed that such an education model can prepare students all-rounder to face any challenges in their life and make them innovative in their working place. Apart from area-based specific focus during higher education which enhances knowledge and subject-specific skills, additional supporting skills like communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, enhancing competitiveness, preserving a vision in life, desire for learning and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, self-control and such other qualities inculcate confidence and enhances leadership behaviour among the students to become winner in competitive society. These factors also enhance the employability of the students in industry specific areas where general skills and competency are essential for survival [2].

Engineering education is one of the prominent areas in science & technology education, finding many opportunities and facing many challenges in the 21st century due to the accelerated advancement of technologies in many areas of society [3-5]. Technology is considered as lifeblood of all developments and solutions to all problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human being in the society. Keeping engineering students in pace with such developments and adopting such newly emerging areas of technology in the current curriculum is an essential requirement of the education industry's progress. In this paper, we have proposed a new improved model on engineering education system of India which includes basically STEAM model with employment skills enhancement program (ESEP) subjects in every semester and earning IPR by every student as top-ups. This model proposes six innovations at the undergraduate engineering level to improve the depth, breadth, and vigorousness of the B.Tech. programme by suggesting a Student focussed integrated development (SFID) Framework. This integrated development framework in engineering education is based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning. The six innovations proposed in this model with increased credits in every semester upgrades the conventional B.Tech. (Pass) programme into B.Tech. (Honours). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages from students, institutions, and job offering industries point of view are analysed. Many recommendations are submitted based on the analysis to make this model of B.Tech. (Honours) more effective in its objective of enhancing competency, confidence, and employability of graduates to secure better job.

2. RELATED SCHOLARLY WORKS :

2.1 STEM Model as First School of Innovative Thought :

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) as integrated single subject in school education is becoming popular in many countries and now spreading its roots to higher education system. Apart from school education, if college level curriculum is planned with STEM subjects, the scientific thinking and innovative ability of students can be improved to make them smart graduates who can adopt technology in decision making and problem solving. In STEM curriculum model at college level, a student has to study science, technology, engineering, and mathematics subjects in each year (preferable in semester) to be competitive in order to get further opportunities. Identifying such subjects in a systematic combination to make effective STEM interconnected model is the challenge for educators. Table 1 contains some of research papers published during the 21st century related to college education.

Table 1 : Published papers related to STEM education

S. No.	STEM Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	21st century STEM education concepts & priorities	A tactical model for long-range success	Ostler, E. (2012). [6]
2	STEM subjects for College education	College student pathways to the STEM disciplines	Engberg, M., (2013) [7]
3	Facilitating change in undergraduate STEM education	STEM for Change in knowledge & skills	Beach, A. L., (2012) [8]
4	Innovation processes in university STEM education	System model	Porter, A. L., (2016) [9]
5	Integrated STEM education	Benefits and procedure of integration	Roehrig, G. H., (2015) [10]
6	How an integrative STEM curriculum	For students of engineering design practices	Fan, S. C., (2017) [11]
7	From STEM to STEAM Strategies for enhancing engineering & technology education	Importance of Arts & Design education for enhancing creative abilities	Connor, A., et al. (2015) [12]
8	The potential of technology education	STEM education	Wells, J. G. (2008) [13]
9	STEM and technology education	International state-of-the-art education	Ritz, J. M., (2015) [14]
10	Developing effective STEM professional development programs	Design of STEM programs	Avery, Z. K., (2013) [15]
11	Reformation of engineering education.	Transitioning from STEM to STEAM	Watson, A. D., (2013) [16]
12	Rethinking STEM education	An interdisciplinary STEAM curriculum	Madden, M. E., [17]

2.2 STEAM Model as Second School of Innovative Thought :

An improvement in STEM is argued by many researchers in education to make students as all-rounders. As per this argument, apart from learning for knowledge, skills, and experience which are specific for a given industry, student should also enhance their creative thinking and design abilities by involving in art and design related trainings. Hence a new model which integrates STEM with Arts & Design subjects is proposed. Based on studies it is realized that such a transdisciplinary STEAM model is the current requirement to enhance the creative thinking abilities among engineering graduates. Table 2 reviews some of the papers published related to STEAM education model.

Table 2 : Published papers related to STEAM education

S. No.	STEAM Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	STEAM education	Development of a theoretical model	Kim, Sung-Won, et al. (2012) [18]
2	Development and application of STEAM teaching model	Based on the Rube Goldberg's invention	Kim, Y., (2012) [19]

3	A study of teaching-learning methods for the IT-based STEAM education model	With regards to developing people of interdisciplinary abilities	Kim, J. A., (2011) [20]
4	Rethinking STEM education	An interdisciplinary STEAM curriculum	Madden, M. E., (2013) [21]
5	Transitioning STEM to STEAM	Reformation of engineering education	Watson, A. D., (2013) [22]
6	From STEM to STEAM	Toward a human-centred education	Boy, G. A. (2013) [23]
7	An analysis on STEAM education teaching and learning program	On technology and engineering areas	Ahn, J., (2013) [24]
8	STEAM teaching practices	Developing a conceptual model	Quigley, C. F. (2017) [25]
9	From interdisciplinary to transdisciplinary	An arts-integrated approach to STEAM education	Liao, C. (2016). [26]
10	STEAM Education	Study on the current status	Park, H., (2016) [27]
11	STEAM as social practice	Cultivating creativity in transdisciplinary spaces	Guyotte, K. W., (2014) [28]
12	STEAM Education through Case Studies	Examination of the Practical Model	KIM, J. W. (2015) [29]
13	From STEM to STEAM	Students' beliefs about the use of their creativity	Oner, A. T., (2016) [30]

2.3 Improving Competency through Employability Skills Enhancement Model :

Competency means ability or capability to do things effectively and performance is the proof of competency. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. But based on many studies, it is evident that a major portion of engineering graduates have lack of competency to be employed. This problem can be resolved by means of offering special training on employability skills enhancement during the engineering course by adopting such training in the college curriculum. Many research papers published on such industry oriented employability skills to be inculcated with the students to transfer them as employable graduates. A review on some of the papers on employability skills enhancement based education is given in Table 3.

Table 3 : Published papers related to Employability skills enhancement based education

S. No.	ESEP Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	Career management skills	Enhancing graduate employability	Bridgstock, R. (2009). [31]
2	Employability skills in higher education	Various methods in order to promote employability skills in HE	Asonitou, S. (2015). [32]
3	A European study	Graduate employability, 'soft skills' versus 'hard' business	Andrews, J., (2008) [33]

		knowledge	
4	Engineering employability skills required by employers	In Asian countries	Zaharim, A., (2009) [34]
5	Recognizing the enhancement of graduate attributes and employability	Through part-time work while at university	Muldoon, R. (2009). [35]
6	Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation	In Higher Educational Institutions	Aithal, P. S., (2015). [36]
7	Bridging the gap between degree programme curricula and employability	Through implementation of work-related learning	Hills, J. M., (2003) [37]
8	Defining and measuring employability	Measurement ideas	Harvey, L. (2001). [38]

3. OBJECTIVES :

This paper is a conceptual suggestion based proposal to convert B.Tech. (Pass) course into B.Tech. (Honours) with the following objectives :

- (1) To study emerging models in undergraduate engineering programmes and emerging technologies in the 21st century to be incorporated in the curriculum of undergraduate engineering programmes.
- (2) To propose employability and research oriented curriculum in engineering education based on emerging technologies.
- (3) To suggest an innovative curriculum scheme based on STEAM and employability skill enhancement Program (ESEP) papers along with a focus on research in the improved model.

4. EMERGING MODELS IN UNDERGRADUATE ENGINEERING EDUCATION :

4.1 New Models in Engineering Education :

Autonomy for higher education institutions supported many innovations in course identification, course design, course pedagogy, student services, examination, and evaluation systems. Engineering education, being a prominent field in higher education, became witness in such innovations. Many student centric models are offered in engineering education during last few years mostly by autonomous and private universities. Some of such successful models which attracted many students are as follows :

(1) Industry Integrated B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses are designed to train students for specific industries. The curriculum of such courses is designed by involving experts from such industries along with academicians. Such courses will have more practical components in the form of industry specific projects and industry based internships.

(2) Super speciality B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses are designed to train the students in emerging engineering and technology areas to full fill the requirements in future industries. These emerging areas usually falls

under General purpose technologies which offers huge job opportunities in future days in many industries.

(3) Skill focussed B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses focus on developing some specific skills along with the general requirements of engineering knowledge, skills, and experience. Usually, these courses have components which are taught by a specific set of professionals or consultants who have proprietary knowledge in that area.

(4) B.E./B.Tech. Programs with Multi-continent exposure :

In this model, students are exposed to different educational environment by taking them to three to four continent. The students get multi-cultural, multi-teaching- learning atmosphere, along with mult-country industry exposure. Student will study foreign language, and the attitude of other country people due to their immersion in different country environment. The social and technological scenarios will modify the critical and creative thinking abilities to contribute differently to their future organizations.

(5) Integrated Dual degree during B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

In this model, a student registers for two university degrees simultaneously either at the same institution or at different institutions of same university or some times of different universities. This model allows a student to study two degrees in different subject areas simultaneously so that the precious time resource can be utilized effectively. Such studies may be of two different undergraduate programmes as parallel programmes in different disciplines or two sequential programmes as undergraduate and postgraduate programmes in a single discipline.

(6) Research focussed B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

Undergraduate degree programmes in engineering can be made innovative and more intensive by integrating research components in one or more semesters so that along with conceptual and practical studies, students are compulsorily involved in research and publications along with the faculty members so that students are exposed to systematic innovative thinking and analysis.

4.2 Emerging Technologies to be Incorporated in Engineering Education :

The future education is mostly driven by technology and hence customizable. In this century, education sector, being a part of the service industry is also going to witness the fourth industrial revolution (IR 4.0) with the features of mass customization, personalization, and student centric approach. The technology based disruptive model of education is going to be a driving force of future education at both school and college levels. The engineering education also be accessed via following nine trends [x] which include (1) ubiquitous education model, (2) personalized learning model, (3) choice based pedagogy model, (4) project & experimental based learning model, (5) field based learning through internship, (6) data interpretation skills, (7) competency based evaluation model, (8) teachers as facilitators & guides during learning process, and (9) student-self designed curriculum model. These trends of education 4.0 can be realized using various emerging technologies under the umbrella of ICCT (Information communication and computation Technology) and nanotechnology.

The various emerging technologies which have an impact on teaching – learning and various industrial applications [39-42] are :

(1) Artificial Intelligence : Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science which focuses on the creation of intelligent machines which can mimic the decisions of human beings. The primary objective of AI technology is to develop machines which can think and do things better than human beings. The main functions of artificial intelligence machines are to recognize the environment such as speech recognition, Learning, Planning, Problem solving, and hence decision making. Artificial intelligence machine mimics cognitive functions of human beings associated with other human minds, such as learning & memorising and decision making for problem solving. ICCT has created a platform for AI to be introduced and developed for adding intelligent thinking components in electronic systems used in any industrial sectors. Artificial intelligence has its applications in almost all industries in the primary sectors, secondary sectors, tertiary sectors, and quaternary sector.

(2) Machine learning : Machine Learning is the learning in which machine can learn by its own without being explicitly programmed. It is an application of artificial intelligence that provides the system with the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience. Machine learning is based on the idea that we can build machines to process data and learn on their own, without our constant supervision.

(3) Robotics : *Robotics* technology deals with the study of design, construction, operation, and application of computerized *robots and* their control, sensory feedback, and information processing abilities. Robotics technologies are useful in developing machines that can replicate and substitute human actions.

(4) Internet of things : It is a network of various electronic, computing, and optical devices/objects including human beings connected virtually by means of internet or intranet for enabling them to send and receive data and information. These objects are provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and are capable to transfer data and information over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction by using IoT technology. Such a connection of physical things/objects through the Internet allows to access remote sensor data and to control the physical devices connected to it from a distance. The data captured from such sources, can create new synergistic services which will be superior to such services provided by an isolated embedded system. Internet-of-Things (IoT) is not in any new disruptive technology but is the pervasive deployment and innovation of ICCT.

(5) Autonomous vehicles : An autonomous vehicle can guide itself without human control. This kind of vehicle has become a concrete reality and may pave the way for future systems where computers take over the art of driving. An autonomous car is also known as a driverless car, robot car, self-driving car or autonomous vehicle. An autonomous vehicle is an application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in automobile engineering.

(6) Bio and nanotechnology : Bionanotechnology is a branch of **nanotechnology** which uses biological starting materials, utilises biological design or fabrication principles or is applied in medicine or biotechnology. For example, nanoparticles can serve as probes, sensors or vehicles for biomolecule delivery in cellular systems.

(7) 3-D printing : 3D printing is an ICCT application where various materials are joined or solidified using various processes under the control of the computer to create a three-dimensional object. In 3D printing, an object is created by laying down successive layers of material until the object is created. 3D printing can be divided into metal, fabrics, bio and a whole host of other industries with many applications in many industries worldwide. 3D printing is a variant of ICCT general purpose technology and has wide scope in various

industrial automation and home automation processes. 3D printing technology is expected to revolutionise the material fabrication processes. 3D printing comprises of many other technologies along with ICCT. Some of the 3D printers make use of nanomaterials and nanocomposites for anything, anywhere manufacturing.

(8) Material science for energy Storage : Sustainable *materials* are the key requirement of many advanced *energy* technologies including solar cells, batteries, fuel cells, and catalysis. There is a large demand for cost-efficient methods for *energy storage* and conversion in the society and hence it has become imperative to accelerate the rate at which *energy*-related *materials* are developed. Material scientists are developing various materials which show improved properties like smart materials, superconductors, nanomaterials, polymers, etc.

(9) Quantum computing : High speed computers based on optical signal switching and optical signal processing are expected to breakthrough with their full potentials and capabilities using optical logic gates and flip-flops fabricated by nanocomposites are expected to breakthrough in this century. High speed computation and data storage using nanotechnology based optical/quantum computers are going to revolutionize the entire computer industry. Optical computation is joining both general purpose technologies of Nanotechnology and ICCT through the processes of design & production as well as operation & applications respectively. Various optical principles like photo-refraction, optical spatial solitons, and optical logic gates are under considerations for building all-optical computers.

(10) Business Analytics : The emerging subfield of ICCT named big data and business analytics focus on handling huge amount of data continuously generated in any business or data capturing process and analyses it using various quantitative analytical techniques and mathematical models to study the pattern and descriptive information, predictive information, and prescriptive information for supporting the decision makers to take optimum decisions to the problems related to future aspects of the business. Predictive analytics in various functional areas like Marketing analytics, Retail Analytics (Customer Analytics/ Supply Chain Analytics), Pricing Analytics, Financial analytics, Social media analytics, sports analytics, and Healthcare analytics are finding importance in the business environment for effective decision making. Further Prescriptive Analytics for optimizing the decisions with multiple objectives/ portfolio analytics, optimizing complex decisions/ sales force analytics, and Retail Analytics etc are also have futuristic impact on effective business decisions.

(11) Cloud Computing : Cloud computing is one of the advances in computer technology and is uses information communication technology as well. Due to the ubiquity of cloud computing facility with flexibility in scaling it has become an important topic of research and provides the value for computing processes in the business. The cloud computing model also provides a most important application called Business Intelligence (BI) for effective decision making in business processes via the Internet. Cloud computing model provides its clients with both hardware as well as software to process the data and information online as a rental service. Cloud computing model has three variations as Software as a Service (SaaS), Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) and Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) to provide ubiquitous computing service solutions to the business. The cloud computing solution used by any business will allow companies to reduce their investment cost, maintenance cost, and hence business cost without compromising to have access to BI solution which will give the business an edge on their competition.

(12) Blockchain Technology : Blockchain is basically a growing list of records containing data or information, called blocks, which are linked using a secured technique called cryptography. Every such block contains a cryptographic hash code of the previous block, a

timestamp, and transaction data. By design, a blockchain is resistant to modification of the data. Blockchain gives the history of currency transaction and hence its spending pattern. Blockchain technology is widely used by cryptocurrency transactions. The discovery of the blockchain technology for bitcoin made it the first digital currency to solve the double-spending problems without the need of a trusted authority. Blockchain technology has potential applications in digital currency technology and secured transactions.

(13) Online education technology : Online educational technology supports learning from distance so that a person can earn educational credentials and improve his performance by creating, using and managing appropriate technological processes and resources using internet and multimedia technologies. Online educational technology is the use of both physical hardware and educational theoretic along with wireless systems and internet. This technology has huge amount of applications in many kinds of services in almost all industry sectors for training and development.

(14) Virtual & Augmented Reality : Virtual reality is an artificial environment that is created with the help of computer-based software and presented to the user in such a way that the user suspends belief and accepts it as a real environment. On a computer, virtual reality is primarily experienced through two of the five senses: sight and sound. Currently, the virtual reality is mainly developed and used in simulated training and education as well as the simulated game environment. But it may further find its applications in many other areas including business as augmented reality and may enter the group of general purpose technology.

These emerging technologies have many applications in engineering industries. Having knowledge and learning such technologies is essential for undergraduates during their studies so that such exposure

5. EMPLOYABILITY & RESEARCH ORIENTED CURRICULUM BASED ON EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES :

Engineering graduates are expected to have certain minimum knowledge, skills, and experience as their graduate attributes to identify problems, design solutions, and develop processes and products with new innovative features in industries. Creativity, design thinking, problem solving, self-motivation, positive attitude towards professional challenges, working culture, team work and leadership qualities are essential traits to be successful in getting good job and further promotions. Engineering colleges should focus on planning and implementing such education model which can offer essential employability skills to their students. Some of major employability skills for engineering graduates are in table 4 along with their description and method of acquiring.

Table 4: Major Employability skills required for Engineering graduates

S. No.	Employability skills	Description	Method of gathering
1	Effective Communication skills	Communication of information in understandable manner and in right time	Training
2	Team work skills	To increase the performance of the team	Target based group projects
3	Problem solving skills	Use a combination of intuition and logic to come up with right	Experimental learning

		solutions at right time	based laboratory courses
4	Data interpretation & Numerical competency	To measure an individual's ability to interpret and manipulate data, which is required in most industry roles	Skill labs
5	Leadership skills	How to analyze, how to synthesize, and evaluate situations to make sound decisions	Training
6	Technology skills	Technology awareness	Technology adoption
7	Self-awareness & Competency in specific engineering discipline	Re-defining the goal & SWOC analysis	Competitions
8	Attitude & responsibility towards work	Accountability in overall performance	Workshops & Field works
9	Innovative & creative thinking	Research based new knowledge creation	IPR
10	Design thinking	Product and Design & simulation	Self designed courses

6. B.TECH. (HONOURS) MODEL WITH STEAM & EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS FOCUS :

Based on focus group analysis, we have gather ideas and concepts to improve engineering curriculum with above requirements of new knowledge, new skills, new experience through hard and dedicated learning model which is based on STEAM, Employability enhancement features, creating intellectual properties and industry oriented internship for the 21st century education Industry 4.0 version. The findings are postulated as follows :

- (1) Semesters with increased subjects & Credits (from 6 to 9 subjects & from 20 Credits to 25 Credits).
- (2) Redesigning the Subjects in each Semester as per STEM/STEAM model wherever possible with emerging technologies.
- (3) Increasing Experimental/lab based learning (EL) part in each semester so that equal importance is given to theory and practicals.
- (4) Introducing employability skills enhancement papers (ESEP) in each semester from Industry Experts.
- (5) Focussing on IPR awareness and Patent analysis in every student’s specialized area.
- (6) Compulsory IP generation through Copyright/Patenting/International Journal Publication of the internship based project.

The above postulates are identified as integrated student development framework in engineering based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning and IPR generation. The model is also represented in the form of a block diagram as shown in figure 1.

The ideas and concepts to improving engineering curriculum with above requirements of new knowledge, new skills, new experience through hard and dedicated learning model which is based on STEAM (Science, technology, Engineering, Arts & Design, and Mathematics), Employability skills enhancement program (ESEP) features, creating intellectual properties, and industry oriented internship.

Fig. 1 : Integrated Student development Framework for effective engineering education

7. COMPARISON OF B.TECH (HONOURS) MODEL WITH B.TECH. (PASS) MODEL :

The newly proposed integrated student development model (ISDM) is compared with the traditional undergraduate engineering model of many universities in India and the comparative features are listed in table 5.

Table 5 : Comparison of the features of B.Tech (Hons) and B.Tech (Pass) model

S. No.	B.Tech. (Pass)	B.Tech. (Hons)
1	Less number of papers per semester (6 to 7)	More number of papers per semester (8 to 10)
2	About 18 to 20 credits per semester	25 credits per semester
3	SEM Model	STEAM Model

4	Less lab based experiments papers	Equal number of theory and laboratory papers
5	No focus on Employability Skill Enhancement in each semester	Two Employability Skill Enhancement Papers (ESEP) in each semester
6	University centric Examination system	Student centric Examination system
7	No projects in every semesters	Teamwork based projects in every semesters
8	No IPR training to motivate students for new knowledge creation	Compulsory IPR training in fourth semester to create awareness about patent & copyright
9	No papers and training on patent analysis	Training and involvement of students on existing patents analysis in their special subjects.
10	No compulsory project work based on full semester internship	Compulsory project work based on full semester internship and compulsory patent application filing/journal publication

8. CONCLUSION :

An innovative, effective, efficient new model in engineering education is proposed. This Integrated student development model based on STEAM, ESEP & IPR features enhances the weightage of conventional B.Tech. (pass) course and elevate it to highly employable based on enhanced competency in concerned engineering subjects called as B.Tech. (Hons). It is predicted that B.Tech. (Hons) graduates have better capability to work and solve problems in the industry due to their enhanced knowledge, skills, experience, and confidence. Such innovations in existing higher education courses are essential to ensure that the graduates studied in such courses are useful for society to contribute to their specialized fields.

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WELFARE OF UNORGANIZED WORKERS: PROBLEMS & PROSPECTS

Pinto Vincent*, D'Mello Laveena**

*Freston Knowledge Foundation®, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail:
Vincentpinto79@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

A large portion of India's workforce falls into the unorganized segment and there is a steady growth in it over years. They are outside the purview of labor legislations and without benefits of social protection and often do not even have a legal status as worker. In spite of such common features, the unorganized/informal sector comprises several heterogeneous groups. The researcher has undertaken this study to find out the effectiveness of certain welfare activities in the unorganized sectors in Udupi District. The study further tries to suggest concrete measures to improve the situation of unorganized workers towards their growth and development through labour welfare measures. The units of population were selected by using simple random sampling method. It comprised of 50 respondents out of which 20 workers selected from fishery, 15 workers from unskilled category and 15 from construction industry according to the number. A descriptive design was used. The study attempts to give a true picture regarding the miserable situation of unorganized workers in terms of their working conditions, remuneration, terms of employment, lack of facilities and amenities. There are some practical difficulties in the administration of welfare measures for this sector due to the complex nature of the sector. However the study recommends that the workers in the unorganized sector can be recognized as a special target group by the government for the implementation of programmes of general welfare in the spheres of housing, education, health and other services. Apart from this all governments must support social security measures by providing necessary budgetary support since this sector suffers from paucity of funds.

Keywords: Unorganized, Unskilled, Fishery, Construction, Welfare, and Workforce

1. INTRODUCTION

The question of labor is of vital significance for any country both from the National and International point of view. Indian labour economy is quite wide and there are three major sectors in our economy namely service sector, agricultural sector and the industrial sector. It is quite evident that there are organized and unorganized workers in all these three sectors. Workers employed in industrial sectors are to some extent organized but their number is quite negligible since majority of employees in the industrial sectors are working in household, construction and beedi industries. Hence we find a huge number of workers in the unorganized sector especially in the service sector namely; shops, commercial

establishments, hotels, transport, education, health, banks, post offices, non government organizations, social welfare centers, market, fishing, domestic employment, security guards etc. According to the National Sample Survey conducted in the year 1999-2000, the total employment in both organized and unorganized sectors in the country was of the order of 397 million. Out of this, around 28 million was in the organized sector and the balance 369 million in the unorganized sector. The number of workforce figure 450 million in 2011 where around 430 million workers are employed in a unorganized sector which is increased consecutively. In this context the researcher attempts to highlight the significance of unorganized sector while trying to confer the major problems faced by the workers of this sector.

2.UNORGANIZED WORKER

Unorganized workers are those who engaged in a variety of occupations or employments, ranging from those forest workers like tribes trying to follow traditional vocations within their traditional habitats, and fishermen who venture out to sea in vulnerable canoes, to those who are working in their homes with software, or assembling parts for a highly sophisticated product. Almost the entire non-agricultural activity in rural India is unorganised. Thus, workers in the unorganised sector include all the workers of the unorganised sector as well as the casual and contract workers in the organised sector who, for one reason or another, have failed to get the benefits of protective legislation or laws on social security. Unorganised sector workers are those who do not have any job security, income security or social security and are therefore extremely vulnerable to exogenous shocks. The National Commission on Labour in India 1966 stated, unorganized labour cannot be identified by a definition but would be described as those workers who have not been able to organize in pursuit of a common objective because of the following constraints – the casual nature of employment, ignorance, illiteracy, small size of establishment per person employed, scattered nature of establishment and superior strength of the employer operating singly or in combination. Hence the basic characteristic of this sector is of the variety, complexity, dimensions and variety of the workforce. Thus the term unorganised labourer refers to workers who are employed without job security, standard wages, fixed hours of work, leaves and holidays, and social security like provident fund and medical benefits. They may be working in traditional sectors like domestic work and agriculture or even in the organized sector as casual workers or contract labourers. They may also be self-employed. They are outside the purview of labour legislations and without benefits of social protection, and often do not even have a legal status as worker. In spite of such common features, the unorganised/informal sector comprises several heterogeneous groups. Ministry of Labour has categorised the unorganised labour force under four groups in terms of occupation, nature of employment, especially distressed categories and service categories.

4.KEY CONCEPTS

Unskilled Workers: Manual workers and a number of other workers in the unorganised sector performing diverse activities are considered unskilled workers. Unskilled workers, who are not employed in the organised sector, come in the category of workers in the unorganised sector. The majority of agricultural workers and construction workers belong to this category. Helper category of jobs in all sectors, the manual workers, roadside workers available for all kind of petty jobs, head load workers/ porters, etc. come under this category.

Fishery: India is one of the major fishing countries, with about 5.4 million tonnes of fish production (both from marine and inland water sources). India ranges first among Commonwealth countries and 7th in the world.

Construction Labour: Construction workers may be broadly classified as skilled and unskilled. Usually, couples are found to be working on the same worksite. Though child labour is prohibited, children are engaged for unskilled jobs. Most of the workers in this sector are employed on a casual basis. Unstable employment/earnings and shifting of workplaces are the basic characteristics of work for construction workers. Women engaged in construction work, are the most exploited. Frequent changes in their work and instability deprive them and their children of primary facilities like health, water, sanitary facilities, education and ration cards. In most cases, safety norms are violated.

3. THE STATUS OF THE UNORGANISED SECTOR

The vast majority of India's labour belongs to the unorganized sector. The facts say that about 93 percent of the Indian labour force belongs to the unorganized sector, which is growing, and that hardly any tangible efforts exist to improve their living conditions are truly alarming. Labour welfare laws have not come to the rescue of the unorganized workers and so far there is no way to organize them to make available the benefits, facilities and protection provided by the labour welfare to the unorganized workers. The scope and coverage of labour legislations is limited to hardly 9.4 percent of the total workforce, who are in the so-called organized sector, as per 1991 census. But remaining 90.6 percent of the persons working in unorganized sectors such as the small and marginal farmers, the landless agricultural labourers, the rural artisans, the handicraft men and women, the fishermen and women, the salt workers, the hamals and the building and construction workers, etc., are deprived of protection under social security legislations of the state. Most of the workers of the unorganized sector come from dalit, tribal, minority and most backward caste communities. Caste, class, ethnicity and gender are fundamentally contributive factors to being a worker in the unorganized sector. The plight of rural working class is more deplorable because they are not educated, ready to migrate, and unorganized totally. However, as far as the agricultural sector is concerned, irrespective of economic class, the share of the unorganized workforce remains flat. Further analysis reveals that the coverage of social security schemes has been extremely sparse among the economically and socially vulnerable sections.

4. THE PROBLEM

Over the years, the status of unorganized labour in the country has been studied by various Commissions and the Study Groups. All these studies have projected the plight of the workers in the unorganized sector and called for substantial measures to improve their protection. Several schemes have been evolved in India through legislation and policies to provide social security to the workers in the unorganized sector. Constitution of India makes special provisions in its various articles. There are several legislations which apply partly to the unorganized sector. The proposal of enactment of a comprehensive legislation for the unorganized sector was discussed during 38th Session of Indian Labour Conference held in the year 2002 at New Delhi. Accordingly, the 'Unorganized Sector Workers Bill, 2003' was drafted. It successively drafted another, i.e., the unorganized Workers (Conditions of work) Bill, 2005. The proposed legislation envisaged to regulate the employment and conditions of

service of the unorganized sector workers and to provide for their safety, social security, health and welfare. Lately, the Unorganized Workers Social Security Act, 2008 has been enacted by the Government to provide social security to workers in the unorganized sector. Taking into consideration the all round growth and progress of workers on account of the various existing, both statutory as well as voluntary, labour welfare measures there arise the following pertinent questions. Since most of the welfare legislations cater to workers in organized sectors, how far the unorganized workers have benefited from such labour welfare measures? Has labour welfare so far led to the development of labourers or just met their daily necessities of life? Whether social welfare measures are effective in administering them to the workers of unorganized sector? In this connection the researcher aims to undertake a study on the effectiveness of certain welfare activities in the unorganized sectors in Udupi District. The study further tries to suggest concrete measures to improve the situation of unorganized workers towards their growth and development through labour welfare measures.

5. OBJECTIVES

The study is undertaken with the following objectives.

- To prepare a socio-demographic profile of workers of unorganized sector in Udupi District of Karnataka State.
- To assess the socio-economic status of the respondents.
- To diagnose the work related problems of unorganized workers.
- To identify welfare measures available to unorganized employees and to gather their opinions about the effectiveness of the same.
- To arrive at some concrete and practical measures to improve the socio economic conditions of unorganized employees and elicit their suggestions regarding the same.

6. METERIALS AND METHODS

The universe of the present study constitutes unorganized workers of different categories, i.e., Fishery, Unskilled Workers and Construction Workers in the regions of Coastal Karnataka. The selected population was measured under simple random sampling method. It comprised of 50 respondents out of which 20 workers selected from fishery, 15 workers from unskilled category and 15 from construction industry according to the number. The respondents were explained the purpose of the study and ensured confidentiality of the data. The researcher used three methods of data collection in order to gather information both from respondents and other informants which consisted of personal interviews, discussions and observation. The study used a descriptive research design. For systematic processing of data the researcher made use of both manual and mechanical system of data processing. Hence the data collected was coded, tabulated and analyzed by the application of logical and statistical reasoning.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-demographic data showed that 40 percent of the respondents were in the age group of 35-45 years, 80 percent were female employees where as 20 percent of them were male employees. The marital status of the respondents revealed that 64 percent of the respondents

were married. Distribution of the religious affiliation shows that majority of them are Hindus (58%) and the rest forming the minority. Majority (86 percent) of the respondents were from rural background. The educational status of the respondents reveals that 86 percent of the respondents were below high school. With regard to the mode of employment of the workers a majority of 54 percent is casual workers and 42 percent are contract workers respectively.

Table No: 1 Family Income of the Respondents

Family Income per month (in Rupees)	Number of Respondents	Total
Upto 5,000	7	14%
5,001-10,000	30	60%
10,001- 15,000	8	16%
15,001 and above	5	10%
Total	50	100%

It is evident from the above table that majority (60 percent) of the respondents' monthly family income distribution is between Rs. 5,001 –Rs. 10,000 per month. Among the other respondents, a considerable percent of respondents fall below Rs. 5000(14 percent) and 16 percent of them are having a monthly family income of Rs. 10,001/- to Rs. 15,000/- per month. There are 10 percent of the respondents earn an income of more than Rs. 15,001/- per month. From the above analysis, we can depict the economic situation of workers in unorganized sector. Since a large number of respondents earn within the category of Rs. 5001-Rs. 10,000 it draws our attention towards the present standard of life in comparison with the income. The living is become very expensive and it is very difficult to maintain a family with scanty financial resources. Also, 10 percent of respondents are very poor since they earn below 5,000. Hence a large (70%) group of respondents live below the poverty line in the unorganized sector.

Table No: 2 Categories of Unorganised Workers V/S Effectiveness of Welfare Measures

Occupation of Workers	Assessment of Problems & Areas of Welfare Suggested									
	Good working environment & Safety practices		Attractive Compensation packages		Availability of job on regular basis		Minimum working hours, Rest and Leisure		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Fisheries	3	6%	5	10%	2	4%	10	20%	20	40%
Construction Workers	2	4%	4	8%	3	6%	6	12%	15	30%

Unskilled workers	4	8%	3	6%	3	6%	5	10%	15 30%
Total	9	18%	12	24%	8	16%	21	42%	50 100%

The table depicts that out of total respondents 40 percent of them belong to the work category of Fishery, 30 percent each from construction & unskilled category respectively.

According to the section on assessment of problems & areas of suggested welfare, the respondents demonstrated higher scores of 42 percent in the domain of minimum working hours, rest and leisure. Here, the vast majority of respondents do not find their work hard on account of the above said problems. Among the other respondents, 24 percent are happy with the compensation package being offered and this is a sizeable percentage where respondents are able to manage with the package that is offered to them. However, there are two other areas of problems are grave because quite a small percent of respondents are satisfied with the facilities while it is a problem for others. The distribution of the same spreads as 9 percent in the case of healthy working environment and safety practices and 8 percent with the job offered on a regular basis.

From the above, we can draw the major problems being faced by the workers in the unorganized sector are: 1. Seasonal employment 2. Unhealthy Work Environment and less safety 3. Low compensation package 4. Lack of regulation in working hours, rest and leisure provided. While two of the former problems are experienced by a large number of respondents, the latter areas are taken care in many of the establishments. Hence the major trouble faced by the unorganized sector is non-availability of work throughout the year. Further, out of 40 percent respondents in the category of fishery only 4 percent are getting employment on a regular basis. Similarly merely 6 percent each receive employment on habitual basis in construction and unskilled category respectively. The second major hitch that we have in this sector is unhealthy working environment, insanitary conditions, lack of security systems, and pollution control, devices which cause great health hazards to workers. Supplementary to this barely 6 percent respondents are pleased with the provisions among 40 percent in Fishery while 4 percent in construction (out of 30 percent) and 8 percent in unskilled (out of 30 percent) category respectively. The next concern for the unorganized workers being the compensation package, opinions slightly differ. There is a considerable percent of respondents(10 percent) are contented with the package offered in Fishery while others still feel it is a smaller amount of the package. Likewise 8 percent in construction and 6 percent in unskilled category among 30 percent of respondents each. This varied distribution may be based on the socio-economic status of the respondents. In the same way, there are equal respondents (20 percent out of 40 percent) express a positive feeling about the minimum working hours, rest and leisure. Also 12 percent respondents in construction and 10 percent in unskilled category get leisure and rest sufficiently. This shows that the problem of working hours does not affect the unorganized workers as much as other problems.

8. IMPLICATIONS AND SUGGESTION

The study is significant in the following ways. It attempts to give a true picture regarding the miserable situation of unorganized workers in terms of their working conditions, remuneration, terms of employment, lack of facilities and amenities. In this way it will bring to light the vast gap in the distribution of income and fair treatment of workers between a

small group of organized employees and a large majority of unorganized workers. The study is an eye opener to the government officials in the ministry of labour and the Non Governmental as well as voluntary agencies working for the betterment of workers to pay immediate attention and initiate swift action in order to work out some efficient and effective measures to improve the conditions of the unorganized employees. Despite of the fact that provision of social security to unorganised sector workers assumed unprecedented significance in the development discourse of India in recent times, it not only fails to cover all the categories of unorganized workers but also in the effective administration of the same. Hence an attempt should be made to rethink the existing social security measures in order to discuss the scope for designing more effective measures as well as machineries to implement these measures.

General suggestions

- There are some practical difficulties in the administration of welfare measures for this sector due to the complex nature of the sector. However, workers in unorganized sector can be recognized as a special target group by the government for the implementation of programmes of general welfare in the spheres of housing, education, health and other services. Apart from this all governments must support social security measures by providing necessary budgetary support since this sector suffers from paucity of funds.
- Though the government is very much concerned to make labour welfare measures available to unorganized workers and introduced several schemes but these has not been implemented in letter and spirit for lack of adequate supervision. Hence, collaboration with various agencies of the government like Panchayats, Nagarapalikas, Department of Social Justice Welfare, NGOs and social workers, etc. will be effective.
- There is no trade union or institutional machinery to represent workers. Unless they are organized and made aware of their strength in unity the dreams of development might remain plat.
- The establishment of more and more institutions of mutual benefit for self employed workers will support the cause very much.

Specific Suggestions

- The major trouble faced by the unorganized sector is non-availability of work throughout the year. The employers should take the responsibility of dispensing them with other occupations so that the employer not only builds a long term relationship with the worker but also continuity with the worker ensures optimum productivity, efficiency and effectiveness. Secondly stock of raw materials can further provide few more months of employment to the workers. Thirdly, the government should support these workers by providing social assistance to undertake self employment in the stop gap period.
- The unorganized sectors continue to suffer from unhygienic and insanitary conditions, lack of security systems, and pollution control, devices which cause great health hazards to workers. So welfare funds need to be augmented to provide maximum welfare services to workers in proportion to their number. The number of welfare

centers in each state also needs to be increased and located near the working place to enable the workers and their families to make their maximum use.

- As mentioned earlier, social assistance by the government and budgetary support will improve the financial situation to provide a good compensation package to the workers. It is also suggested that employers as well as government should promote direct marketing facility to the products of the unorganized sector. This would maximize the profit and in turn benefit the employers as well as employees.

9.CONCLUSION

India's workforce comprises nearly 93 per cent of unorganized workers, with virtually the entire farm sector falling under the informal category, only one-fifth of the non-farm workers are found in the organised segment which is growing, and that hardly any tangible efforts exist to improve the living conditions of these unorganized workers are truly alarming. Though the government has shown interest to make labour welfare measures available to unorganized workers and introduced several schemes these have not been implemented in letter and spirit for lack of adequate supervision and administration. This legislation needs to be an enabling one that will improve livelihood opportunities, provide a decent life to the workers and integrate them with the growing opportunities in the country. Together with the government it is the employers and Trade Unions also have the obligation to contribute to the welfare of the workers for their health and safety through the implementation of different legislations by taking up the activities falling within their purview and sphere.

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Paper 4

SIBLING RELATIONSHIP AND MENTAL WELL-BEING AMONG YOUNG ADULTS OF INSTITUTIONS FROM BHADRAVATHI IN SHIVAMOGGA DISTRICT

Cleona Crasta*, **Monteiro Meena ****, **D'Mello Laveena *****

* II MSW, School of Social Work, Roshni Nilaya, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

** Associate Professor, Social Work Department, School of Social Work, Roshni Nilaya, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail : monteiromeena@yahoo.com

***Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to learn about the importance of the relationship between siblings and their mental well-being, including psychotherapeutic intervention. This study adopted purposive sampling method. A sample of 50 young adults belonging to the age ranges 18 to 40 years having biological siblings were selected from 2 institutions in Bhadravathi, Shivamogga district. WEMWBS (Warwick Edinburgh's Mental Well-Being Scale), and ASRQ-S (Adult Sibling Relationship Questionnaire Scale) with the factors Warmth, Conflict, Paternal, and Maternal Rivalry, referred from Wallace's Thesis on "Sibling Relationship", were the scales used to measure The Relationship of Siblings and their Mental Well-Being. This study used SPSS and Descriptive analysis to interpret and describe the data. Therapeutic intervention such as Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy, Post Modern Approaches' Solution Focused Therapy, Narrative Therapy, Virginia Satir's Human Validation process, and Jay Haley and Cloe Madanes' Strategic Family therapy can be used to change Dysfunctional patterns in the family, and enhance Family bonding and thus improve the mental health of the people.

Keywords: Sibling Relationship- Warmth, Conflict, Paternal and Maternal Rivalry, Mental Well-Being, Therapeutic Intervention, Young Adults.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sibling relationship has an impact on Mental Well-Being. Healthy sibling relationships can significantly benefit us later in life. Those with positive sibling relationships report higher life satisfaction and lower rates of depression later in life. Also in times of illness and traumatic events, siblings provide emotional, social support to each other. Research shows that this support is common regardless of whether they live together or far away from each other (Lohmann, 2014). Sibling relationship incorporates actions, verbal and nonverbal communications between individuals who share the same biological parents (Cicirelli, 1991). (Wallace, 2012). According to (Cicirelli, 1994), sibling relationships play an important role not only in the family life but by influencing the way that the family functions within society.

To learn more about sibling relationship, mental wellbeing and therapeutic intervention, an attempt has been made to review the literatures on this topic: Article "Theoretical

Perspectives on Sibling Relationships.” Review To stimulate interest in sibling research and to serve as a guide for future investigations by family scholars, they analyze four theoretical psychologically oriented perspectives—(a) psychoanalytic-evolutionary, (b) social psychological, (c) social learning, and (d) family-ecological systems. Most research on siblings has focused on childhood and adolescence, their review highlights these developmental periods, but they also incorporate the limited research on adult sibling relationships, including in formulating suggestions for future research on this fundamental family relationship. According to Happiness and Human Potentials, Wellbeing is a complex construct that concerns optimal experience and functioning. (Rayan & Deci, 2001) State that current research on well-being has been derived from two general perspectives: The Hedonic Approach: focuses on happiness and defines well-being in terms of pleasure attainment and pain avoidance. The Eudaimonic approach: focuses on meaning and self-realization and defines well-being in terms of the degree to which the person is fully functioning. In the Human Validation Process Model, Satir (1988) outlined four communication stances that people tended to adopt under stress: blaming, placating, super reasonable, and irrelevant. The antidote to these stress communications is congruence, by which Satir ment emotional honesty, in which one speaks for oneself, stays grounded (or centered), and is able to both share what she or he is feeling and ask for what is needed.

2. AIM

The aim of this study was to know the significance of Sibling relationship, and Mental Well-Being among young adults and comprise Psycho-therapeutic intervention. The main objectives of this study was to learn about Sibling Relationship, Mental Well-Being, analyze Sibling Relationship and Mental Well-Being among young adults, and to facilitate the role of a Psychotherapist to enhance the sibling relationship and mental well-being, This study adopted the Descriptive Analysis as research design.

3. FINDINGS

Mental well-being of the respondents was assessed by using Warwick Edinburgh mental well-being scale with 14 positive statements in it. Sibling Relationship was assessed by adding the dimensions of warmth (Intimacy, Emotional Support, and knowledge) and Conflict (quarreling, Antagonism, Dominance), paternal and maternal Rivalry.

Mental well-being of the respondents has been highlighted in three different tables Viz. table 1, table 2 and, table 3.

The first table indicates that, 24 percent of the respondents rarely felt optimistic, 8 percent of them felt optimistic some of the time, 12 percent of them often felt optimistic and 46 percent of the respondents felt optimistic all of the time. 2 percent of the respondents rarely felt useful 72 percent of the respondents felt useful some of the time and 26 percent of the respondents often felt valued. 4 percent of the respondents said that they are never interested in other people 16 percent of the respondents thought that they are interested in other people some of the time 76 percent of the respondents often felt interested in other people and 4 percent of the respondents felt interested in other people all of the time.

MENTAL WELL-BEING OF THE RESPONDENTS

Statements	None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time
Feeling optimistic	0	12 24%	4 8%	11 22%	23 46%
Feeling useful	0	1 2%	36 72%	13 26%	0
Feeling interested in other people	2 4%	0	8 16%	38 76%	2 4%

THE RESULT OF EMOTIONAL SUPPORT AMONG SIBLINGS

Statements(Emotional support)	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Regularly
How much do you try to cheer this sibling up when he/she is feeling down?	4 8%	7 14%	7 14%	32 64%
How much can you count on this sibling to be supportive when you are feeling stressed?	A little	A lot		
	32 64%	18 36%		
When this sibling is stressed are you more likely to provide emotional or practical support?	Emotional support	Practical support	Both	Neither
	11 22%	32 64%	7 14%	0
How often do you discuss important decisions with this sibling	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Regularly
	6 12%	0	33 66%	11 22%

The table above shows emotional support between siblings 8 percent of the respondents never tried to cheer up their sibling when he/she was feeling down, 14 percent of them rarely tried to cheer their sibling up. Of which, 64 percent of the respondents counted a little on this sibling to be supportive when they were feeling stressed and 36 percent of them were able to count a lot on their sibling to be supportive when they were feeling stressed. 22 percent of the respondents were able to provide emotional support when their siblings have stress, 64 percent were more likely to provide practical support when their sibling was stressed and 14 percent were more likely to offer both emotional and practical support. 12 percent of them never discussed important decisions with their sibling 66 percent of the respondents occasionally discussed important decisions with their sibling and 22 percent of them discussed important decisions with their sibling on a regular basis.

The factors that influence mental well-being and sibling relationship could be societal norms, social pressure, parenting style, and parent-child relationship, family dysfunction, social support system, high/low self-esteem, work, school and college environment, physical and mental abuse.

Solution-focused therapy is well suited for people with adjustment disorders, and for problems of anxiety and depression. According to Family Therapy, the family is viewed from an interactive and systematic perspective. The family provides the context for understanding how individuals function in relation to others and how they behave. Treatment deals with a family unit.

The family therapist functions as a teacher, coach, model, and consultant. The family learns ways to detect and solve problems that are keeping members stuck and it learns about patterns that have been transmitted from generation to generation some approaches focus on the role of therapist as an expert; others concentrate on intensifying what is going on in the here and now of the family session. All family therapists are connected with the process of family interaction and teaching patterns of communication.

4. RECOMMENDATION/ SUGGESTIONS

As this study was done only on young adults, cross-sectional study considering also the middle-aged and the elderly in sibling Relationship study is recommended because the previous studies have found that there is a close bond between siblings as they grow older. It is recommended to focus on gender difference with regards to sibling relationship and mental well-being. Depending on parenting style, how the older sibling form a relationship with the younger one can be taken into consideration for this study. Causes for Maternal Rivalry and Paternal rivalry could be lack of mutual understanding, un-forgiveness among couples that may indirectly affect their children in a negative way, miscommunication, jealousy, manipulating children to get their work done, causing children to quarrel with each other thus destroying family bond. This can be prevented using Virginia Satir's Human Validation Process Model and Jay-Haley and Cloe Madanes' Strategic Family Therapy and through role-modeling as well as making family to learn communication skills and assertiveness training. Studies have found that parental support may create an atmosphere in the family highlighting the importance of helping each other which lasts to adulthood.(Voorpostel and Blieszner; 2008), (Wallace, 2012). Through family therapy (intervention of a Family Therapist), dysfunctions in the family can be evaded and built positive and healthy families. Rational Emotive Behavior therapy by Albert Ellis, Family Systems Therapy, Postmodern Approaches (Solution Focused Brief Therapy; Narrative Therapy), and assertiveness training is found to be helpful in dealing with miscommunication, misunderstanding, and rivalry in the family.

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A MODERN LEADERSHIP THEORY BASED ON ATTITUDE-BEHAVIOUR (AB) FRAMEWORK

P. S. Aithal¹ & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal²

¹Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Abstract

The organizational fate depends on a committed effective decision maker who can predict the future business situations based on various affecting parameters on the organizational business. Such right decisions at right time to be taken by a decision maker can transform himself as an acceptable leader. Such decisions can also decide the fate of the organization along with the livelihood of its employees. A winning leader is an asset of an organization and the employees are directly and indirectly get the benefits of such leader. If the leader fails in predicting the future of a profit oriented organization or not for profit organizations, the employees are directly going to be the victims of such wrong decisions. In this paper, with case studies and prediction model support we have developed a theory on Acceptable Leadership called AB Theory of Leadership which depends on the attributes of Attitude, Behaviour, Choice, Decision of leader while analysing and making decisions on a problem solving by considering organizational perspective.

Keywords : AB Theory of Leadership, Attitude, Behaviour, Choice, Decision, Winning Leader, Winning organizations.

1. INTRODUCTION :

An effective leader is the strength of an organization and his ability of making decisions related to the problems on short term and long term objectives of the organization decides the fate of the organization and hence the fate of the stakeholders. A committed leader in business organizations is an effective decision maker who can predict the future business situations based on various affecting parameters on the organizational business. Making right decisions at right time on organizational challenges can elevate an organization as winning organization and transform the decision maker into an acceptable leader. Making right decision in organizational and business environment depends on three factors (1) leaders personality and behaviour, (2) quality of the information related to the problem/challenge, and (3) the ability of the leader on predicting the future. Since the decisions taken by the leader decides the fate of the organization along with the livelihood of its employees and their dependent family members, the role of the leader is very challenging and risk taking. It is argued in many scholarly analysis that a winning leader is an asset of an organization and the employees are directly and indirectly get the benefits of such leader. If the leader fails in predicting the future of a profit oriented organization or not for profit organizations, the employees are directly going to be the victims of such wrong decisions. Thus an understanding leader who can be role model for every employee is important in every organization for sustainability for long time.

Leaders should be able to make correct judgement while taking decisions based on his personal traits (personality), his attitude, and ability to make effective predictions by using predictive analysis framework. The attitude of the leader plays an important role while making decisions on solving organizational/individual problems. It is argued that the personality of a leader cannot be changed easily [1]. In Simon’s model of decision making, the attitude of the leader decides his ability of identifying a problem, finding alternative solutions, analysing these alternatives to find optimum alternative, and finally to implement the best alternative to practically solve the problem. Thus identifying a problem is the behaviour of a leader and is important initial instinct and it depends on the attitude of a leader.

According to ABC model of attitude suggested by Eagly & Chaiken 1993 & Van den Berg et al. 2006 [2-3], human attitude as an object has three components identified as Affect (A), Behaviour (B) and Cognition (C). Affect component represents the individual’s feelings about the object Attitude, Behaviour component represents the individual’s intention towards the object Attitude, and Cognitive component represents the beliefs of an individual towards the object attitude.

But based on the observation and review of related works, we have developed an improved model on successful leadership for winning organizations which is based on Attitude and Behaviour of a leader called Attitude-Behaviour framework of Leadership. This model holds good for individual leadership and organizational leadership and describes how the past and present environment of a leader effects the present decisions on future performances of the organization for sustainability.

2. RELATED WORKS :

2.1 Leadership Theories

Many leadership theories are evolved during last 100 years. These theories are tried to explain the successful leadership qualities individually, working in teams, working in organizations and even working as leader in society. The important theories developed during last century with generality in their model include Great-man theory, Trait theory, Contingency or situational theory, Style and Behavior theory, Process Leadership theory, Transactional leadership theory, etc. Table 1 contains some of general leadership theories developed during last century. These theories are framed based on certain characteristics of a leader while making decisions and certain nature of the leader towards the problems he faces in his life/organization/society. These theories focus on attitude of a leader and his behaviour towards making decisions.

Table 1 : Review of General leadership Theories and their focus

S. No.	Leadership Theory	Focus	Reference
1	Great-man Theory	Leader is born not made	Thomas Carlyle (1847) [4]
2	Trait Theory	Based on (i) emergent traits (those which are heavily dependent upon heredity) as height, intelligence, attractiveness, and self-confidence and (ii) effectiveness traits (based on experience or learning), including charisma	Ekvall & Arvonen, 1991 [5]
3	Contingency Theories (Situational)	There is no single right leadership because the internal and external dimensions of the environment require	Greenleaf, 1977 [6]

		the leader to adapt to that particular situation	
4	Style and Behavior Theory	Leaders of three categories as democratic leaders, autocratic leaders, and laissez-faire leaders	Yukl (1989) [7]
5	Process Leadership Theory	Process theory focus on servant leadership, principal centered leadership and charismatic leadership	Greenleaf, (1996) [8]
6	Transactional leadership Theory	Type of contingent-reward leadership that had active and positive exchange between leaders and followers	Bass and Avolio (1994) [9]
7	Transformational leadership Theory	A transformational leader attempts to induce followers to reorder their needs by transcending self-interests and strive for higher order needs. Such leaders empowers the followers	House & Shamir, (1993) [10]

Further specific leadership theories developed and tested during last 50 years are also listed in table 2 which also include some of the general leadership theories. The focus or the constructs of the theories are listed along with scholarly published references. These theories are build or developed based on the leaders attitude of seeing and understanding the problems or situations to make decisions and his behaviour towards individual or organizational or social problems. All leadership theories deal with the decision making abilities of a leader in internal or external environmental uncertainties. Thus the published work deals with mainly on the behaviour of a leader in a given environment.

Table (2.a) : Specific Leadership theories developed during last 50 years

S. No.	Type of leadership Theories	Focus/ Constructs	Reference
1	Implicit leadership Theories	Individuals create cognitive representations of the world, and use these preconceived notions to interpret their surroundings and control their behaviours.	Offermann, L. R., (1994) [11]
2	Managerial leadership Theories	Leader who engages in an influence process for the purpose of helping others understand what needs to be done, or that helps other individuals or groups accomplish shared objectives	Yukl, G. (1989). [12]
3	Transactional and transformational leadership theories	Transactional leaders focus on organization, supervision, and group performance, where as transformational leaders focus on change within the organization.	Wofford, J. C., (1994) [13]
4	Contingency leadership Theory	It claims that there is no best way to organize a corporation, to lead a company, or to make decisions. Instead, the optimal course of action is	Yukl, G. (2011). [14]

		contingent (dependent) upon the internal and external situation.	
5	Strategic Leadership Theories	It is the ability to influence others to voluntarily make decisions that enhance the prospects for the organisation's long-term success while maintaining short-term financial stability.	Tone Hosmer, L. (1982). [15]
6	Situational leadership Theories	It refers to when the leader or manager of an organization must adjust his style to fit the development level of the followers he is trying to influence.	Hersey, P., (1997) [16]
7	Personality and charismatic leadership	Articulating a vision and mission, and creating and maintaining a positive image in the mind of followers	House, R. J., (1992) [17]
8	Distributed leadership Theories	It equates with shared, collective and extended leadership practice that builds the capacity for change and improvement.	Barry, D. (1991) [18]
9	Shared leadership Theories	It broadly distributes leadership responsibility, such that people within a team and organization lead each other.	Pearce, C. L., (2000) [19]
10	Servant leadership	It is a philosophy and set of practices that enriches the lives of individuals, builds better organizations and ultimately creates a more just and caring world.	Van Dierendonck, D. (2011). [20]
11	Clinical leadership	The concept of clinical healthcare staff undertaking the roles of leadership: setting, inspiring and promoting values and vision, and using their clinical experience and skills to ensure the needs of the patient	Stanley, D. J. (2012). [21]
12	Spiritual leadership	It is a holistic approach to leadership in which the leader strives to encourage a sense of significance and interconnectedness among employees.	Fry, L. W. (2003). [22]

2.2 Attitude–Behaviour Models :

Attitude-behaviour relations model is initially systematically studied in social psychology by Ajzen I et al during 1977 [23]. According to this model, the attitudinal and behavioral entities consisting of four different elements namely (1) the action, (2) the target at which the action is directed, (3) the context in which the action is performed, and (4) the time at which the action is performed. The model predicts that behaviour is a monotonic function of attitudes and external conditions and that the strength of the attitude-behaviour relationship is a function of the strength of the external environment [24]. Ellis et. al [2] developed another ABC Model on human behaviour where – A stands for Antecedent (situation), B stands for Beliefs (thoughts of the situation/ interpretation of an event), and C stands for Consequences (outcome).

3. OBJECTIVES :

The paper is conceptual in nature and follows a research model of review based prediction and postulates based analysis to identify the suitable model in the form of a Theory to answer a question on what factors decides an acceptable leader in Winning Organizations. This also include :

- (1) To identify a suitable reason for success of a leader in winning organizations
- (2) To develop a suitable theory on Leaders' action called behaviour.
- (3) To determine the underlying constructs of behaviour which decides the decision making characteristics of a leader in business organizations which have a long term objectives.

4. FACTORS AFFECTING THE ATTITUDE :

The attitude of a person is determined by psychological factors like ideas, values, beliefs, perception, etc. All these have a complex role in determining a person's attitude. Aman Sharma, (2016) [25] identified eight factors responsible for the development of attitudes. These eight factors are (1) family, (2) peers, (3) conditioning, (4) social adjustment functions, (5) direct instruction, (6) modelling, (7) satisfaction of wants, and (8) prejudices. Another study [26] on factors influencing the attitude lists nine factors which are considered as (1) Social Factors, (2) Direct Instruction, (3) Family, (4) Prejudices, (5) Personal Experience, (6) Media, (7) Educational and Religious Institutions, (8) Physical Factors, and (9) Economic Status and Occupations.

5. FACTORS AFFECTING THE BEHAVIOUR :

Behaviour is the outcome of the attitude of a person. The behaviour of a leader in a given situation depends on the attitude of him. This is well known and the outcome of many psychological studies [27]. According to one school of thought, the four main factors that influence behaviour and performance are: Biographical and demographical characteristics, Intellectual and physical abilities, Self-concept and self-esteem, and Personality. As per another school of thought, the behaviour of a person depends on six factors : (1) Willpower, (2) Knowledge and skills, (3) Social motivation, (4) Social ability, (5) Structural motivation, and (6) Structural ability. The third school of thought includes three factors as (1) Personal factors, (2) Environmental factors, and (3) Organizational factors affect individual behaviour. Finally, it is also argued that the following five factors affect the behaviour of a leader which include : (1) Personality, (2) Situation, (3) Needs, (4) Leadership style, and (5) Operating environment.

6. ATTITUDE-BEHAVIOUR MODEL OF LEADERSHIP :

Attitude is the mental status of a human being which represents the emotions at a given time and controls his/her instantaneous behaviour. Such behaviour reflects in instantaneous decision making of a leader.

6.1 Postulates of Attitude-Behaviour Model :

It can be argued that the behaviour of a human being depends on his/her attitude and the attitude depends on his or her feelings at that time which in turn depends on the emotions of the person. It can be argued that the emotions of a person depend on his/her beliefs on the situation. It is also known that the belief of a person is strongly depending on the environment around him during his present and past life. Accordingly, we propose the following postulates :

- (1) Personality cannot be changed so easily, but behaviour of a person can be changed.
- (2) The behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude.

- (3) The attitude of the leader depends on his feelings.
- (4) The feelings of a leader depend on his emotions.
- (5) The emotions of a leader mostly depend on his beliefs.
- (6) The belief of a leader depends on his present and past environment.

(Behaviour) => (Attitude) => (Feelings) => (Emotions) => (Beliefs) => (Environment)

Fig, 1 : Block diagram representing depending factors of Attitude and behaviour of a leader [x]

6.2 Leadership and decision making :

A winning leader will make winning decisions by rightly analysing the situations to predict the future state of affairs. According to our theory of leadership, the behaviour (action) of a leader to solve an identified problem depends on his attitude. Hence the theory is called attitude-behaviour theory, which states that the behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude towards solving a problem or making a decision which further depends on his feelings, emotions, beliefs, and hence his present and past environment. The constructs of Attitude-Behaviour (AB) model are :

(1) Attitude :

Attitude is a tendency to act in a certain way, either favourably or unfavourably concerning objects, people, or events. Attitude of a person depends on how a person feels about a situation or an issue. It expresses an individual’s positive or negative feeling about an object or a situation. Attitude of a person towards a given situation can be measured by measuring and understanding his feelings, and thoughts by asking questions to a person one can measure his feelings and thoughts. In general, if a person has a positive attitude about his work responsibilities, it will be reflected by good work performance, less absenteeism, less turnover, obedience towards rule or authority, etc. If a person has got a negative attitude towards his work responsibilities, he will act in exactly the opposite way. The negative attitude can be changed by simple persuasion or by training and coaching. Attitude is an abstract learned reaction and as per our postulate, it heavily depends on the feeling of a leader towards an object or an issue.

(2) Behaviour :

As mentioned earlier, behaviour is the outcome of the attitude of a person. The behaviour of a leader on a given situation depends on the attitude of him. This is well known and the outcome of many psychological studies. Behaviour can be measured by understanding the attitude of a person either by observing the actions or simply by asking questions to him about how he would behave in a particular situation. Behaviour is the action performed by a person based on his attitude towards an object or an issue. As per our postulate behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude. Hence by improving the attitude, the behaviour can be improved.

(3) Feelings :

In psychology, the word is usually reserved for the conscious subjective experience of emotion. Feelings are also known as a state of consciousness, such as that resulting from emotions, sentiments or desires. Feeling is an internal state of affair of a human being. As per our postulate, feelings of a leader depend on his emotions.

(4) Emotions :

Emotion is considered as the feedback of feeling. Emotion is the external state of affair of a human being. Emotions are mental states of readiness that arise from appraisals of events or one's own thoughts. It is argued that emotions are event-driven, while feelings are learned behaviours that are usually in hibernation until triggered by an external event. Unlike feeling, an emotion involves little cognitive awareness. As per our postulate emotion of a leader depends on his beliefs about that event or issue or object.

(5) Beliefs :

Belief of a person depends on what he follows with or without any reason. Beliefs of a leader are distinguished into three types as : (1) behavioural beliefs, which are assumed to influence attitudes toward the behaviour, (2) normative beliefs, which constitute the underlying determinants of subjective norms, and (3) control beliefs, which influence perceived behavioural control. As per the postulate of our attitude-behaviour theory, belief of a leader depends on his present and past environment.

Fig. 2 : Components of environment which effects the leaders’ attitude

(6) Environment (Past & Present) :

The operating environment around a leader supports for risk taking and is motivating and encouraging creativity and allowing appropriate flexibility, rather than with rigidity and inflexibility. The environment which affects the attitude of a leader through his beliefs has various components (figure 3). The important components which decide the attitude of a leader are (1) Individual maturity of generous thinking which may have positive or negative effects as a positive thinker or negative thinker respectively. (2) Living place and the country situation which may have positive impact or negative impact. (3) Family culture and tradition has mainly positive impact. (4) Organizational atmosphere which may have positive or negative impact. (5) Competing situations internally or externally in the organization which is against organizational objectives or individual objectives of a leader.

The important environmental components which affects the belief and hence the attitude of a leader and hence affects his behaviour are discussed below and some of the important characteristic elements of these components are listed in table 3 :

(1) Impact of Individual Maturity for effective Leader :

Leadership maturity is a leader's ability to engage consistently with others who are the stakeholders of the organization. Individual maturity demands the ability to make wise and appropriate judgments about different problems. Usually, the leadership maturity is decided based on certain parameters like (1) relevance to time, place and person, (2) productive in terms of contributions made, and (3) uplifting in such way that interactions are positive, fulfilling, and enriching. Acquiring leadership maturity is a lifelong process and involves various stages. In each stage of developing maturity, leaders will develop a corresponding identity. Based on how a leader process life events and experiences, he may spiral upwards to higher maturity or downwards to lower maturity. Sometimes, they may also get stuck at one level for the rest of their life.

(2) Impact of Living place & Country on effective Leader:

The environment in living place and the people in the surroundings also play an important role in developing the characteristics of a leader. Positive and encouraging atmosphere in home and surroundings will cultivate positive, generous feeling within a leader. Family stress may affect the decision making ability of a leader and such cases may create a catastrophic outcome in organizational performance. Similarly, the political and economical environment of the country and its impact on organizational performance or on society also affects the decision making ability of the leader.

(3) Impact of Family culture & tradition on effective Leader:

Culture plays a primary role on the person's perception of the world. Many studies have shown that people from different cultures perceive things differently. Perception is the process by which we become aware of our environment. Culture and perception are closely related because it is through their own culture that people view and perceive themselves and others in the environment. The application of a leadership style cannot be an imposition but needs to consider the diversity of cultures in order to be effective. Although we live in a globalized economy in which everything is standardized, it is unlikely to find a generalization of the way culture influences leadership perception and execution.

(4) Impact of Organizational atmosphere on effective Leader:

Organizational business, opportunities, and culture also effect and makes an impact on a leader's ability and quality. It also improves the confidence of a leader for further innovation. A positive organizational atmosphere supports the leader for taking winning decisions.

Stakeholders view on the organization or society in that country enhances or suppresses the confidence and risk taking ability of a leader.

(5) Impact of competing situations on effective Leader:

Both internal and external competition affects the strategic thinking ability of a leader. Competition may have either positive or negative effect on leaders decision making ability based on his personality, which depends on his attitude and hence his feelings, emotions, and belief. Positive leaders turn difficult situations into engaging learning moments whereas negative leaders convert challenges into unsolved problems.

Table 3 : Components of Environmental factor and their important characteristic elements

S. No.	Components of Environmental factor	Characteristic elements
1	Individual maturity of generous thinking	(1) Age (2) Education (3) Responsibility has taken (4) Challenges faced
2	Living place and the country situation	(1) Peace in home (2) Peace in neighbourhood (3) Facilities during childhood (4) Country situation (social & political)
3	Family culture and tradition	(1) Home culture (2) Parents & Family members attitude (3) Religion culture & tradition (4) School studies with teachers & friends attitude
4	Organizational atmosphere	(1) Nature of employees (2) Type of business & its connectedness with the leader (3) Opportunities expansion & growth (4) Current status of organizational business
5	Competing situations internally or externally in the organization	(1) Competing organizations (2) Status of the organization in its environment (3) Environmental situations for the business (4) Internal and external strategies followed

7. CONCLUSION :

A winning leader will have a positive attitude so that he will take winning decisions through his appropriate and acceptable behaviour. The positive attitude is always derived from his feelings about the problem or situation which may be positive or negative. These situational feelings depend on his emotions which in turn depend on his beliefs in life and about the situation/problem. But the belief of every person depends on his past and present environment where he has cultivated such belief. By changing the environment of a leader, his beliefs, and hence his emotions, and hence his feelings can be changed which in turn change his attitude and hence his behaviour. This may modify his ability to understand the problem, analysing the situation, and to make a sound decision. Thus the leader’s problem solving and decision making ability can be improved by providing a positive atmosphere, trouble free supportive environment which supports positive feelings and hence winning

attitude. Leaders may fail due to wrong decisions which are mainly due to their wrong attitude towards the problem.

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Paper 7

THE FUNCTIONS AND JOB DESCRIPTIONS AT HOTEL INDUSTRY: A CASE OF GRAND HYATT, MUMBAI

Noronha Andrea Deardre *1, Dmello Laveena **2

*BHM Student Trainee, Sarosh Institute of Administration, Mangalore 575 005, Karnataka, India. Email Id:deardre199623@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities,, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. lavyoronha@gmail.com

Abstract:

The training and working in the Hotel industry will give the true light. It will help to realize that Hotel Industry is much more than just fun & pleasure; it's a lot of hard work. There are multiple departments with junior and senior professional. Each person is unique in nature and has different talents to contribute in the industry as a team. Every job has its nuances and its value and that no job is superior to the other. When a person wants to sustain in the industry, he has to improve constantly. A student in a hotel industry has to keep documentation and try hard to gain experience along with their studies in college. This paper will throw light on the different departments and the job descriptions at Grand Hyatt and it is purely a case study. The hierarchy which exists in the hotel industry for the smooth functioning of the Hotel is explained in this study.

Keywords: Hotel Industry, departments, practical skills, profession, customers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The story of Hyatt hotels and resorts, which opened its first hotel in 1957, is a tale of continual innovation, remarkable expansion and a single-minded dedication to the highest of standards. The US-based company has, for nearly 50 years, transformed the hospitality industry by combining friendliness and efficiency with the finest traditions of international hotel keeping. In the process, Hyatt has redefined luxury for the modern traveler. Hyatt Hotels Corporation is an American multinational owner, operator, and franchiser of hotels, resorts, and vacation properties. The Hyatt Corporation came into being upon purchase of the Hyatt House, at Los Angeles International Airport, on September 27, 1957. In 1969, Hyatt opened its first hotel outside the United States, the Hyatt Regency Hong Kong. In 1980 the Grand Hyatt and Park Hyatt brands were introduced. Hyatt runs resort hotels, starting with the Hyatt Regency Maui in 1980. As of 30 November 2015 Hyatt had over 627 hotels worldwide. As of March 25, 2018, Hyatt has 777 properties in 54 countries. In 2018, Fortune magazine listed Hyatt as the 9th best U.S. Company to work for.

2. PROFILE OF GRAND HYATT MUMBAI

Hyatt Mission, Goal and Values: The mission is to provide authentic hospitality by making a difference in the lives of the people we touch every day, including our associates, guests

and owners. The goal is to be the most preferred brand in each customer segment that we serve for our associates, guests and owners. We aim to foster a common purpose and culture within the Hyatt family through shared core values of mutual respect, intellectual honesty and integrity, humility, fun, creativity and innovation. The mission, goal and values are interdependent, and refer to this interdependence as the “Hyatt value chain.” The Hyatt value chain begins with their associates. They believe that their efforts to engage their associates in planning for how they can better serve their fellow associates, guests and owners contributes to their commitment to genuine service, which is the first step to achieving high levels of guest satisfaction

Overview: Grand Hyatt Mumbai is a luxury 5-star hotel located off the Western Express Highway, Santacruz (East) in Mumbai, India. Designed by Chicago's Lohan Associates, Grand Hyatt Mumbai was opened in 2004.

Infrastructure and Amenities: The hotel has a total of 547 rooms and 111 serviced apartments built on an area of about 12 acres. The banquet level of the hotel offers nearly 30,000 square feet/2,790 square meters of conference and meeting space including one fully wired ball rooms in the city; seven additional meeting rooms and board rooms and a pre-function area. It also has four specialty restaurants — China House, Celini, Soma and Fifty Five East; which serve Indian and international cuisines. It also has a Bar, lounges, Gourmet Store, fitness center and a beauty salon which are situated inside a multi-level shopping plaza. It also has a Grand Club, Club Oasis spa, pool area and barbecue area for Residences; Kids play area, Business Center, outdoor recreation facilities and facilities for physically challenged guests and single women travelers. The hotel also has one of the largest collections of art in a public space in India that showcases over 100 commissioned pieces of art by established and upcoming artists curate in collaboration with Rajeev Sethi

Grand Hyatt Mumbai, India: This luxury hotel and residential development sits on 12 acres located just 20 minutes south of Mumbai’s international airport. The five-star property includes 547 guestrooms, 110 serviced apartments, a business center, health spa, fitness center, pools, and 10,000 square meters of retail. In addition to the pools, outdoor recreational facilities include basketball, tennis and volleyball courts, as well as a paved jogging path. The property is distinguished by stunning water features, distinctive hard cape elements and lush landscaping, as well as many sculptures and other works of art throughout. Due to its proximity to the airport, the structure could not be more than six stories tall, and local mandates required that 15 percent of the site remain open. To attract major conferences and India’s customary weeklong wedding celebrations, the hotel includes a 1,000-seat grand ballroom, meeting rooms, four restaurants, an entertainment center, and below-grade parking for 700 cars.

Places to visit in Mumbai: *Bandra:* Located 20 minutes away from Grand Hyatt Mumbai, Bandra is a prominent entertainment and culture hub in Mumbai. Termed as the ‘Queen of Suburbs’, Bandra is a melting pot of activity and culture; showcasing a cross section of lifestyle products and services, restaurants, pubs, bars and high-street stores. *Bandra-Worli Sea link:* Opened in 2009, The Bandra Worli Sea link also known as the Rajiv Gandhi Sea link is a cable-stayed bridge that connects the suburbs of Mumbai to the arterial roads of downtown Worli and South Mumbai; the richest urban precinct in India that places the city’s main business areas, prime office spaces and high-end residential facilities within itself. *Worli:* A key commercial district in Mumbai, Worli is home to a congregation of

multinational companies like Novartis, GSK Pharma, Barclays Bank, Credit Suisse, Hindujas, YES Bank and Maersk Shipping. *Bandra Kurla Complex and Kalina*: Bandra Kurla complex (BKC); an emerging business district centrally located in the heart of Mumbai. It is home to international schools such as the Dhirubai Ambani International School and the American School of Bombay (ASB).

3.THE DEPARTMENTS

a. FOOD & BEVERAGE SERVICE: *Food and Beverage Outlets: Celini:* Exuding an understating elegance, Celini's interiors are contemporary and simple, using interesting textures of natural wood, stone and matte-finishes steel. The truly Italian home-style cooking embraces traditional Italian recipes and presents them with a modern approach. Inspired by the restaurants wood fired ovens, rotisserie and charcoal grill, Celini's authentic cuisine is prepared in an open show kitchen. **Soma:** A palate of Indian food and art, Soma's modern interior, bold artwork and cotemporary furnishing conspires to create a unique concept for the restaurant. Soma offers regional and tandoor grilled cuisine, simple but delicious it offers a fantastic array of flavours. The theatrically lit tandoor show kitchen is the restaurants central feature where you can see the skilled chefs preparing food right before your eyes. **Fifty Five East:** A casual dining restaurant featuring interactive kitchens which offer Thai, Lebanese, sushi, Western and Indian specialities prepared a la minute. The design of the restaurant draws inspiration from the natural phenomena of sunlight passing through leaves and branches in a forest, the result is a textured look with uneven shadows in harmony with each other. Melding the eclectic energies of Asian cuisine with unlimited glasses of one of France's premium champagnes, The Essence Brunch is the ultimate showcase of taste and temptation, flavor and flamboyance. **Lobby Lounge:** A stylish contemporary lounge offering an all-day dining menu. The lobby lounge offers an eclectic mix of Indian and international specialties, afternoon high tea as well as canapé menu. One of the highlights of the beverage menu is the premium selection of Indian single estate teas. **China House Lounge:** Multi-faceted in spirit, China House Lounge serves as a versatile retreat and the ideal place to linger after dinner over a drink or party to the high- energy music spun by the in-house DJ. **The Bar:** A great place to unwind after a long day. Select from a range of vintage wines by the glass, finest whiskies and exclusive single malts. **Gourmet Store:** Located at ground level of the hotel's Shopping plaza, the Gourmet Store is a one-top hopping destination for a range of food products such as homemade breads, chocolates, cookies, cheese, meat selection, sandwiches, salads, cakes, pastries and some retail food beverage products. There are also varieties of coffee, tea, soft drinks, shakes and other beverages. **Aqua:** The poolside bar is the idea place to reflex after a swim at the pool. The refreshing Aqua menu features a variety of beverages in addition to delectable snack menu. **Banquets:** As we all know Grand Hyatt Mumbai is known for his banquets. Grand Hyatt Mumbai's banquet is spread out over a large area in the hotel. It involves 10 meeting rooms and one huge ballroom and a Grand lawn. The hotel holds various functions like award functions, weddings, meetings, concerts etc. With over 30,000 sq. feet/2,790 sq. meters of sophisticated, indoor banquet space on offer, including one of the largest ballrooms; seven additional smaller venues, a spacious pre-function area and a dedicated Events team, we help you translate your dream wedding to an opulent reality; the way you have always imagined it to be! 100

The hotel has different venues all the events and functions: **The Grand Ballroom:** The size of the pillar less ballroom 11,600 sq.ft/1075 sq.meter. The height of the ceiling is 24 feet. The ballroom can be partitioned into three sound proof sections ranging from 325 to 400 sq.meter

each. It can accommodate 450-1500 in a cocktail reception style. **The Grand Salon:** The modern and elegant grand salon is 2.184 sq.ft/196 sq.meter. It can accommodate 120-150 guests in a cocktail reception style. It can be divided into 3 separate partitions ranging from 72-84 sq meters. **Mahogany:** The Mahogany is of 1104 sq.ft/98.sq meters. It can accommodate 50 guests for a cocktail function and it can accommodate 40 guests for an elegant and formal seating. **Boardroom:** The boardroom is of 1680 sq.ft/ 156 sq meters and is used for smaller functions and events. It can accommodate 40 guests and it has warm and welcoming atmosphere for the guests. **Drawing Room:** The drawing room is mostly used for smaller but private functions. It can have private receptions and cocktail evenings. It can accommodate 60 guests with the seating of couches and sofas. It has a lower and upper deck. The size of the room is 1890 sq.ft/185 sq meter.

b. JOB DESCRIPTION

Job Description of Food and Beverage Director: Reports To: General Manager; **Position Summary:** The Director of Food & Beverage is responsible for coordinating all phases of group meeting/banquet functions held in the Hotel; coordinate these activities on a daily basis; assist clients in program planning and menu selection. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Achievement of budgeted food sales, beverage sales, labour costs and profitability; Completion of Customer Follow-up calls on a timely basis; Timely analysis of Food & Beverage Prices in relation to competition; Participation and input towards F&B Marketing activities; Supervision of daily paper flow including Proposals, and Function Contracts; Preparation of Sales Promotions & Mailings; Directly responsible for large function billings and overseeing medium/small function billings with particular regard to accuracy and timeliness (48 hours); Evaluation forms must accompany all invoices; Gather for large events; oversee for medium/small events, guaranteed attendance numbers. They are required 3 business days in advance of functions.

Job Description of Assistant Food and Beverage Manager: Reports to: Food and Beverage Manager. **Position summary:** An assistant director of food and beverage is one who looks after the administration of the hotel staff, which caters to the needs of the customers. He is a senior team management member who will direct the staff in deciding the various cuisines, and other factors to the likes of the customer to facilitate the smooth functioning of the hospitality trade. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Taking orders from the director and bring them to the staff; Discuss the budget and accordingly plan the inventory, chart menu cards along with their prices in the approval of the director; Supervise over the activities of the staff to get the desired tastes to the likes of the customers; Take the approval of the directors in case of large orders like organizing of parties and marriage banquets; Oversee the duties carried out on day to day basis; provide the inventory and funds required on need; Watch over the paper work done while noting down day to day expenses, direct the staff to record the daily expenses incurred.

Job Description of Outlet Manager: Reports to: Assistant Food And Beverage Director. **Position summary:** Manages daily outlet operations and assists with menu planning maintains sanitation standards and assists servers and hosts on the floor during peak meal periods. Strives to continually improve guest and employee satisfaction and maximize the financial performance in areas of responsibility. **Duties and responsibilities:** Supervises food and beverage service staff in accordance with operating policies that he or she may help establish; Creates a positive team atmosphere among Team Members; Maintains records of

staff periodic manner and operating costs; Provides feedback and coaching to the Team regularly; Understands building capability through Cross training; Sets high standards for appropriate team behaviour on shift.

c. FOOD PRODUCTION

Main Kitchens of the hotel are: Celini kitchen, Soma kitchen, China House kitchen, Fifty Five East kitchen, Gourmet Store kitchen, Banquet kitchen, Bakery, Pastry, Butchery, Chocolate room, Staff kitchen and Gard manger. **Celini live kitchen:** Celini kitchen embraces traditional Italian recipes and presents them with a modern approach. Exuding an understated elegance, the interiors of Celini are contemporary and simple. The Mumbai restaurant showcases a wood-fired pizza oven, rotisserie and charcoal grill – all built into its show kitchen designed by Molteni of France, where the sights and smells of Chef Alessandro Persico’s Italian cooking invades all the senses. The restaurant has an exhaustive list of delectable wine and multiple seating options like table booths and lounge. **Soma live kitchen:** Indian restaurant Soma offers authentic specialties from North India and the North-West frontier cuisine. The food at the best Indian restaurant in Mumbai is simple, with a selection of tandoor-grilled meats, seafood and vegetables, each prepared live to perfection. The tandoor show kitchen at Soma is the restaurant’s central feature, allowing diners to see skilled chefs preparing the meal right before their eyes. The colorful and eclectic art at Soma restaurant in Mumbai reflects the moon in its serene traditional moods, providing the ideal ambience for savoring authentic and traditional Indian cuisine. The restaurant has an exhaustive wine list and unique desserts. **China House live Kitchen:** China House, the best Chinese restaurant in Mumbai offers casual dining with a modern approach. China House offers delectable signature dishes such as Beggar’s Chicken, hand-pulled Dan Dan noodles, Peking Duck, Black pepper king crab, Steamed crystal prawn dumplings; that are complemented by an exhaustive list of delectable wines and a host of mouth-watering desserts to cleanse the palate. The China House restaurant design integrates interactive glass show kitchens into a multiple-seating layout with table booths and lounge. **Fifty Five East live Kitchen:** Fifty Five East is a casual dining restaurant in Mumbai featuring interactive kitchens, offering Thai, Japanese, Lebanese mezze, Western and Indian specialties prepared à la minute. Fifty Five East restaurant is also known for its exhaustive wine list and is popular for its business luncheons and Sunday brunches. **Gourmet Store Kitchen:** The Gourmet Store kitchen features a large selection of gourmet delicatessen items such as cheeses, cold cuts, home-made salads, meats and made-to-order sandwiches, as well as coffee, an array of teas, smoothies and milkshakes, which are available to take away or be consumed in the Gourmet Store. A selection of cakes, breads, decorative pastries and cookies in specially designed packaging are also offered. **Banquet kitchen:** It is the main area of kitchen which provides food for banquet functions in areas like Pre-function area, Ballrooms, Boardrooms and Mahogany room. **Bakery:** The Bakery of Grand Hyatt provides varieties of baked goods and different types of breads like Ciabatta, Focaccia, French baguettes Brioche etc; to all other outlets.

Job Description of Executive Chef: Reports To: General Manager. **Position Summary:** Responsible for the consistent preparation of innovative and creative cuisine of the highest quality, presentation and flavor for the dining rooms, banquets and other food facilities, resulting in outstanding guest satisfaction. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Trains, develops and motivates supervisors and culinary staff to meet and exceed established food preparation standards on a consistent basis; Teaches preparation according to well defined recipes and

follows up and discusses ways of constantly improving the cuisine at the property; Display exceptional leadership by providing a positive work environment, counselling employees as appropriate and demonstrating a dedicated and professional approach to management; Should be able to provide direction for all day-to-day operations in the kitchen; Determines how food should be presented, and create decorative food displays; Recognizes superior quality products, presentations and flavor; Ensures compliance with food handling and sanitation standards.

Job Description of Executive Sous Chef: Reports To: Executive Chef. **Position Summary:** The Executive Sous Chef is responsible to assist the Executive Chef for overall kitchen operation as a successful independent profit center, ensuring maximum guest satisfaction, through planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the Kitchen operation and administration. Exhibits culinary talents by personally performing tasks while assisting in leading the staff and managing all food related functions. Also assists in supervising all kitchen areas to ensure a consistent, high quality product is produced. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Interacts with guests to obtain feedback on product quality and service levels; Responds to and handles guest problems and complaints; Able to make recommendations to the Executive Chef regarding succession planning; To be aware of all financial budgets and goals; To ensure that guests are always receiving an exceptional dining experience representing true value for money; Ensure that all recipes and product yields are accurately costed and reviewed regularly; Ensure that all food items are prepared as per standard recipe cards whilst maintaining portion control and minimizing waste.

Job Description of Pastry Chef: Reports to: Executive Chef / Sous Chef. **Position Summary:** A Pastry chef is responsible to create high quality pastry dishes with the standard recipes and presentations in order to maintain quality standards and consistency of product. Also assist in production and maintenance of par stocks of pastry and dessert with proper rotation of products and maintain highest cleanliness and hygiene standard in the pastry and bakery section. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Manages all day-to-day operations of the pastry and bakery section of the kitchen; prepare a wide variety of goods such as cakes, cookies, pies, bread etc. following traditional and modern recipes; Able to produce all baked goods including but not limited to artisan breads and rolls, muffins, laminated Danish, laminated croissants and doughnuts etc; Decorate pastries and desserts using different types of icings, toppings etc. and ensure the food presentation will be beautiful and exciting; Monitor stocks for baking ingredients such as flour, sugar etc. and make appropriate orders within budget; Check quality of material and condition of equipment and devices used for cooking. 38

Job Description of Grade Manager: Reports to: Executive Chef. **Position Summary:** Responsible for managing the food production and quality control for all meat, fish, fowl and other food items prepared in the cold kitchen. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Oversee the consistency of various preparations within the cold kitchen to ensure quality product and adherence to standard recipes; Prepares all cold food according to recipes, guidelines and standards set by the Executive Chef or hotel standards; Ensures that assigned work area has proper level of par stocks and supplies according to daily production sheets (based on house count), daily menus and banquets events; Always keep all refrigeration, equipment, storage and working areas in clean, working condition in order to comply with health department regulations; Delegates and assists in preparing of cold food items like salads, sushi, cold cuts, salad dressings etc.

d. FRONT OFFICE

The front office is the part of an organization that comes in contact with guests, marketing, sales, and service departments. In the hotel industry, the front office (also known as front desk) welcomes guests to the accommodation section: meeting and greeting them, taking and organizing reservations, allocating check in and out of rooms, organizing porter service, issuing keys and other security arrangements, passing on messages to customers and settling the accounts. A hotel front desk agent represents the first point of contact with guests and handles all stages of a guest's stay. A typical day as a hotel front desk agent, involves registering/booking guests in and out of their rooms, while accommodating any special requests.

Front Desk: The **hotel front desk** is the reception area of the hotel. Those at the desk basically keep the hotel operating, with its many responsibilities. It is the front desk staff that checks guests in and assigns them a room. Front desk staff is also in charge of sending hotel staff to clean the rooms that have been used. Guests also come to the front desk to ask questions and to check out when they are done. A guest's experience at a hotel is largely dependent on the treatment experienced by the hotel staff, especially those at the front desk. The front desk staff represents the hotel in the eyes of guests. **Reservations:** Reservation office, takes care of booking or reserving of a room (accommodation) by a guest. Reservations leads to reserving of a particular type of room for a particular guest for a given period of time. It also gives the guest the first impression of the hotel. Reservations involve activities which do not take place in front of the guests. The entire front office activities start the moment an enquiry or request regarding accommodation is made at the reservations. 91

Guest Relations Executive (GRE): A Guest Relation Officer, also known as a Guest Relation Coordinator or Guest Relation Specialist, is a customer service-oriented employee who essentially greets hotel guests. From escorting guests to rooms to assisting in arranging reservations, Guest Relation Officers ensure a pleasant and satisfying stay at a hotel. They also handle guest complaints, assist with the check-in process and explain all facility amenities, such as pool areas and restaurants. **Skills of a Guest Relations Executive:** Since Guest Relation Officers spend a great deal of time interacting with guests, it is important that they have strong communication, interpersonal and listening skills. They should also be aggressive problem-solvers and have the ability to manage crises successfully. Above average organizational and time management skills are also critical for Guest Relation Officers. Being detail-oriented and possessing the ability to work closely in teams also contributes to the success of this position.

The Concierge: Concierges specialize in guest services at hotels, but some work in clubs and restaurants. Separate from other guest services workers, concierges usually provide guests with information and advice about locations and services outside of the hotel. Concierges often call taxis to transport guests and arrange storage for packages and luggage. Hotel concierges provide guests with highly specialized services meant to improve guest experiences. Some concierges acquire event tickets for guests, which could involve making reservations or payment under a guest's name. Concierges may also arrange guided tours and other special activities for guests. In case of emergencies, concierges help guests locate medical facilities, dentist offices or veterinary care hospitals.

Guest Service Centre (GSC): Guest service centre is a part of back office operations where the Guest Service agents answer telephone calls from guests seeking to make or cancel hotel reservations. Agents answer guest requests for assistance and coordinate with housekeeping, bell service, staff and management to fulfill guest requirements. They provide guests with access to hotel services, forward in-room meal requests, and ensure that mail, faxes and packages are delivered in a timely manner. Agents also deal with irate guests and find ways to resolve issues to the guest's satisfaction. They may also serve as concierges, assisting guests with ground transportation, restaurant or entertainment reservations, and providing other information about the locale. Agents may also be responsible for bookkeeping duties, including maintaining a cash drawer, preparing bank deposits and posting charges for items that guests may order or use during their stay. Upon checkout, agents calculate the guest's final bill and collect payments.

Bell Desk: A bellman is a hotel employee primarily in charge of transporting the luggage from the car to the hotel room and back. A bellman may also load or unload luggage from the car, store luggage for the guests, help guests with packages and find lost luggage. After the guests check in at the front desk, the bellman will escort the guests to their hotel room. The bellman should tell guests about the rooms' features as well as the services that are available in the hotel.

Job Description of Rooms Division Manager: Reports to: General Manager. **Position summary:** The Rooms Division Manager is responsible for Executive Housekeeping and Front Office. He/she manages the general operation of the Front Office e.g. Reception, Reservations, Concierge, Switchboard and Night Manager. **Duties and responsibilities:** The position's main duties are divided in spot checking of hotel rooms to ensure standards, authorizing all leave schedules or ensuring control of expenditures as well as budgets set. A RDM attends weekly executive and sales meetings as well as the General Manager's briefings with Front Office and Housekeeping. For that a Rooms Division Manager needs clear, concise written and verbal communication skills at his/her disposal, as well as strong organizational, excellent time management skills and technical skills; Reporting directly into the Executive Assistant Manager (Rooms), your responsibilities will include but not be limited to ensure timely, efficient & professional welcome and check-in is provided by all Front Desk Colleagues ensuring customer satisfaction; Maintain a high morale and productivity as well as good communication within the Front Office as well as between other departments; Develop colleagues, Team Leaders and Managers by delegating tasks and then empower and coach them making sure they achieve the desired results; Monitor the level of service provided by the department (i.e. by analyzing the Guest Satisfaction Reports) and constantly working on improving it through investigation, analysis and corrective action; Prepare the departmental budget and put measures in place to achieve or exceed the budgeted profit. 100

Job Description of Front Office Manager: Reports to: Rooms Division Manager. **Position summary:** Directly supervises all front office personnel and ensures proper completion of all front office duties. Directs and coordinates the activities of the front desk, reservations, guest services, and telephone areas. Prepare monthly reports and budget for front office department. **Duties and responsibilities:** Trains, cross –trains, and re-trains all front office personnel; Participates in the selection of front office personnel; Schedules the front office staff; Supervises workload during shifts; Evaluates the job performance of each front office

employee; Maintains working relationships and communicates with all departments; Maintains master key control; Verifies that accurate room status information is maintained and properly communicated; Resolves guest problems quickly, efficiently, and courteously; Updates group information. Maintains, monitors, and prepares group requirements. Relays information to appropriate personnel.

Job Description of Guest Relations Executive: Reports to: Front Office Manager. **Position summary:** Attend to guests courteously and deal promptly with their requests and queries. Have Detailed information about the hotel and city. Check on VIP guest movements, complete their pre-registration formalities. Allocate rooms to all arriving guests after checking the guest preferences. Collect guest feedback forms and do any possible first hand service recovery steps. **Duties and responsibilities:** Welcome guests during check-in and giving a fond farewell to guest while checkout; Handling guest complaints and concerns in an efficient and timely manner; Overseeing VIP guests, arrivals and departures; Coordinating and multi-tasking job duties in a busy environment; Should possess detailed information about the Hotel, city as well as the competition; Detailed information regarding arrivals and room requirements; Providing information regarding the Hotel, town attractions, activities etc; Check on VIP reservations, complete their pre-registration formalities; Allocate rooms to all arriving guests.

Job Description of Bell Desk Captain: Reports to: Duty Manager. **Position summary:** Primarily responsible for the supervision of all bell desk staffs, activities and also up keeping of desk area. The bell captain is also responsible for welcoming all guests to the hotel as well as bidding them with a fond farewell. He should make sure all luggage, letter, courier and message movements are tracked and accounted. **Duties and responsibilities:** Ensure that bell desk is manned at all times; Keep working area, clean and tidy always; Ensure that smooth and fast baggage handling for all arrival / departure guests; Maintain close relationship with reception / information / cashier as well as other departments; Attend all guest calls for Bell stand / Door Services related services; Delegate bell boys to pick up the baggages from guest rooms.; Errand cards are filled in for all baggage movements (Check-in, Check-out, Left luggage etc.)

e. HOUSEKEEPING

Housekeeping is a department that deals essentially with cleanliness. The guest satisfaction is its primary objective and the hygiene factor must always be present in the hotel. **Task:** To be responsible for the guest rooms, back of the house and front of the house; To ensure cleanliness, maintenance, hygiene and safety of the hotel; To ensure guest receives high quality services; To ensure that the brand standard are applied; **Areas within housekeeping department:** Rooms, Public area, Laundry, Uniform room, Pest control, Mini-bar and flower rooms.

Job Description of Executive House Keeping: Report to: General Manager. **Position Summary:** Supervises all housekeeping employees, has the authority to hire or discharge, plans and assigns work assignments, give training for newly recruited employees, audit and inspects housekeeping personal work assignment and requisition supplies. Take care of the budget and budget controlling for the department. **Duties and responsibilities:** Supervises all housekeeping employees, hires new employees as needed, discharges employees when necessary and take disciplinary actions when policies are not followed. Evaluates employees

in order to upgrade them when openings arise; Plans the work for the housekeeping department and distributes assignments accordingly. Assigns regular duties and special duties for housekeeping staff. Schedules employees and assigns extra days off according to occupancy forecast; Maintains a time log book of all employees within the department; Recruit and train new employees. Assigns new employees to work with experienced help. Checks on the work of these employees occasionally and observes the report made by the supervisors.

Job Description of Assistant Executive Housekeeper: Reports: Executive Housekeeper. **Position Summary:** The Assistant Executive Housekeeper supervises and coordinates activities of room attendant, house attendant, public area cleaners and floor supervisors. He / She assists in the managing and directing of the day-to-day operations of all Housekeeping and laundry functions. **Duties and responsibilities:** Should have an eye for detail and the ability to effectively deal with guests, other departments and housekeeping staff; Obtains list of vacant rooms to be cleaned immediately & list of prospective checkouts or discharges in order to prepare work assignments; Experience with turn down service, special needs of VIP Guests, foreign dignitaries, etc. is helpful; Assigns team members their duties, and inspects work for conformance to prescribed standards of cleanliness; Prepares and distributes the Room assignment sheet and floor keys to room boys; Maintain clear and efficient communication and coordination with the Front Office and other departments of the hotel; Schedules the cleaning of the room carpets, upholstery, and draperies as needed, along with deep cleaning projects and window cleaning as necessary. 86

Job Description of Laundry Manager: Report to: Executive Housekeeper / Asst. Executive housekeeper. **Position Summary:** A Laundry Manager is responsible for running laundry departments day to day operations and also to deliver an excellent Guest experience while managing stock ordering and supplier relationships. **Duties and responsibilities:** Developing and putting into operation the current system and technical advancement in the field of Laundry operations; Formulating washing formula for stained loads; Ensuring the washing of linen and uniform as per standard; Maintenance and upkeep of all laundry equipment; Co-ordinating with the Engineering Department about their routine maintenance of the equipment; Preparing Annual Laundry Budget; Record and monitor laundry cost.

Job Description of Guest Room Attendant: Reports To : House Keeping Supervisor **Position Summary:** Performs routine duties in cleaning and servicing of guest rooms and baths under supervision of housekeeping supervisor. Room attendant promotes a positive image of the property to guests and must be pleasant, honest, and friendly and should also able to address guest requests and problems. **Duties and responsibilities:** Enters and prepares the room for cleaning; Makes bed; Dusts the room and furniture; Replenishes guestroom and bath supplies; Cleans the bathroom; Cleans the closet; Vacuums and racks the carpet; Checks and secures the rooms; Replenish amenities according to the operational standards; Deliver and retrieve items on loan to guests e.g. iron and ironing boards; Ensure security of guest rooms and privacy of guests; Cleans guest bathroom/bed room/floor corridor.

Job Description of Florist: Reports To: Executive Housekeeper / Asst Executive Housekeeper. **Position Summary:** As a Florist / Floral Designer the primary responsibility is to create innovative floral décor and lead floral installation for the hotel lobby, Guest Rooms,

Restaurants, Spa and other public areas. Have a good coordination with the housekeeping and as well as other department like Front office, F&B Service in order to cater to their floral requirements. **Duties and responsibilities:** Able to create visually appealing flower arrangements for hotels daily requirements; Able to provide specialized design and floral expertise to plan, design and create floral arrangements for all events in the hotel eg: Weeding, Engagement, product launch etc; Able to preparing bouquets for guests, lobby centre pieces and other flower arrangement as per request or memo from both housekeeping and other departments; Assist with loading or unloading of flowers and props from vehicles as and when required; Ensure that all designs meet hotels standards and meet or exceed guests expectations.

Room Supplies: Bath rooms; Moisturizer, Cotton tips, Cotton, wipes, Comb, Disposable bags, Shower cap, Shampoo, Soap, Dental kit, Shaving kit, Emery board, Body lotion, Ear buds, Water bottles, Toilet rolls, Hair dryer and Napkin. Writing table: Telephone, Business kit, Lamp, Newspaper, Magazine, TV remote, Scribbling pad, TV guide, Wardrobe and Iron. Wardrobe: Hangers, Pillow, Bathrobe, Safe, Laundry slip, Shoe shine, Shoe mitt, Slipper, Shoe bag. Mini bar: Coke, Sprite, Diet coke, Perrier, Red bull, Beer, Whisky, Water bottle, Soda.100

f. HUMAN RESOURCES

Human Resource Management in a hotel is the management of the employees of an organization. Simply speaking, it is putting right people to the right task thereby making maximum use of the employees' talent and abilities. Human resource management is responsible for how people are treated in an organization, they deal with bringing people together in an organization, helping them perform their work, compensating them for their work and solving problems that arise. Management functions include: Staffing, Performance appraisals, Compensation and benefits, Training and development of employees and labor relations, Safety and health and Human resource research. It is strategic in nature that concerned mostly with directly assisting an organization to gain sustained competitive advantage. Its characteristic features are: Organizational Management, Personnel Administration, Manpower Management and Industrial Management.

Job Description of Director of Human Resources: Reports To: General Manager.
Position Summary: The Human Resources head oversee the daily operation of the Human Resources office. Responsible for areas of Recruiting, Employee Relations, Benefits, Events, Workers Compensation and other employee-related tasks. Additionally responsible for short and long term planning of all the HR related functions like workforce planning, recruitment, staffing strategies, wage and salary administration, associate and labour relations, benefits, workforce training and development etc.
Duties and responsibilities: To ensure that the company HR operational policies and processes are adhered to and continually improved; To assist in all activities concerning the sourcing & recruitment of staff, performance management, staff discipline and HR administration; To coordinate all matters of employee work permits and visas; To coordinate and / or conduct departmental training and conduct new hire hotel orientation program; Implement corporate policies and procedures on compensation, incentive, bonus and benefits; Continually assesses employee morale by analyzing absenteeism and turnover records, lateness and resignations; Coordinates, controls and inspects employees accommodation, staff canteen, rest rooms etc. ensuring it is of the highest possible standard of cleanliness and comfort; Coordinate employee wellness and

safety programs; Conduct needs analysis, develop, implement, and monitor training programs and materials.

Job Description of Training And Development Coordinator: Reports to: Assistant Human Resources Manager. **Summary:** The Hospitality Training and Development Coordinator is responsible for providing learning and development expertise to all locations in the Hospitality Division. This person will design programs and activities to support team effectiveness while also developing the methods to successfully measure the effectiveness of the training. **Duties and responsibilities:** Take care of entire training and development program, Handle all industrial trainees, Takes care of the budget of the department, Take feedback on various training schedules, and Keep a track on what are the latest innovations and up graduation in the market and train our employees according to them.

Job Description of Personnel Manager: Reports to: Assistant Human Resources Manager

Summary: The personnel manager is the one who manages all the people in an office. They have to look after all the professional doubts and queries that they might have. They attend to the new employees and the existing ones. **Duties and responsibilities:** Personnel managers handle all the employees in a company; They are like a bridge between the management and the staff and should help them both communicate with each other; They in consultation with the senior management, have to formulate all the company policies and implement them; They have to inform all the employees about the policy changes; They have to handle all the complaints made by the employees and have to look into all the complaints in an impartial manner; They have to design programs and events that will boost employee morale and in turn increase productivity; They have to hire employees for the company and they have to arrange for their orientation and training. Human Resource planning enables a department to project its short to long term needs on the basis of its departmental plans so that it can adjust its manpower requirements to meet changing priorities. The more changing the environment the department is in, the more the department needs manpower planning to show: o the number of recruits required in a specified timeframe and the availability of talent o early indications of potential recruitment or retention difficulties o surpluses or deficiencies in certain ranks or grades o availability of suitable qualified and experienced successors

CONCLUSION

fo@iwact.org
toiyo@yyu.edu.tr

<http://iwact.org/>

The original owners of the Hyatt House hotel, a luxury hotel situated near the Los Angeles Airport, were entrepreneurs Hyatt Robert von Dehn and Jack Dyer Crouch. Considering the growing use of air travel for business, the Pritzker brothers realized that locating a high quality hotel near a major airport was a valuable business strategy. Within two years, they opened another Hyatt House hotel near the San Francisco Airport and then another near the Seattle–Tacoma Airport. Over the following decade, acquisitions were made, and Hyatt became the fastest-growing hotel chain in the United States. The Grand Hyatt hotel industry will have different department and work systematically for the smooth functioning of the industry. Students are also given opportunity to do their internship and study in various department, which is very useful for the students to gain knowledge along with the college education. This type of training will push trainees to both excel academically and develop practical skills. The benefits are Hotel industry continue to grow and the students who aspire to continue their studies and take profession will increase. They get experience to see the

staffs determination, commitments, so that they get an idea that the expectations of the stakeholders.

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Paper 8

INFORMATION ASSURANCE: EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM AT BACHELORS LEVEL—AN INTERNATIONAL LOOK

P. K. Paul¹, & P. S. Aithal²

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Security is become an important name these days for different reasons. Today organizations and institutions are engaged in information affairs and in which IT Components become important and valuable. Worldwide manpower requirement in this field is highly solicited, different educational institutions viz. colleges, universities, technical institutions are doing well in this context. There are different areas closely related with the Information Assurance such as Cyber Security, Information Security, IT Security, Computer Security etc. Information Assurance is a broader version of IT Security which talks and deals with both manual and computational security related affairs. Information Assurance moreover comes with the topics in policy designing for healthy information systems designing and development. The framework, guidelines for sustainable information systems designing is also part of Information Assurance. Initially different universities have been started Information Assurance program at Doctoral level and in recent past apart from Masters degrees few have started Bachelors as well. This paper is highlighted the basics of Information Assurance and mainly the available programs of Information Assurance at Bachelors degree level. Paper mentioned the emerging areas and topic of interest as well. It is noted that few universities offers the areas as a full-fledged manner and few as a specialization within a broader domain.

Keywords: Information Assurance, IT Security, Security Education, Information Privacy, Educational Development, Information Science, BS Information Assurance, Cyber Security

1.Introduction

Information Security is a valuable name in the field of Information Science and Technology; there are different Securities fall within this domain viz. IT security, Network security, Database security, Web security including latest and emerging Mobile and Cloud Security. Information Assurance is responsible for implementing and managing and various contents viz. information, data, and knowledge in different including manual and computational. Technological solutions and managerial solution to information are the core of Information Assurance [1], [5]. Information Assurance internationally started by many universities as

short term and long term program. There are various basics areas covered directly under the Information Assurance program viz. *Information and Computing, Managing Information in Organizations, Information and Society, Technology in Organizations and institutions, Information Organization and management including Information Policy etc.*

There are different nomenclatures available of this field and these are depicted in next section. Information Assurance as a broad and interdisciplinary field needs knowledge of various techno-managerial areas [12], [17] viz.—

- Communication Strategies for the IT & Security Professionals
- Enterprise Security Architecture
- Ethics for IT & Security Professionals
- Business Goals for the IT and Security Professionals
- Risk Assessment and Prevention
- Enterprise Tools, Concepts and Processes
- Governance, Quality, Compliance and Ethics
- Security Management [4], [6], [11].

Apart from these kind of techno-managerial areas; Information Assurance professionals should have knowledge in core technologies if they are interested to work in technology segment and among these few important are depicted in the section of ‘**Analysis of the Programs and Challenges**’

2.Objective and Agenda

This is a conceptual paper and theoretical in nature, the following are the core objective of the paper—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its stakeholders and origin in brief manner.
- To learn about the importance of the Information Assurance in basic and common sense.
- To know about the allied and related branches of Information Assurance with reference to educational programs available internationally on this domain.
- To learn about the Bachelors degree available on this areas with both fullfledged degrees and specialization based degrees.
- To learn about the focus and curriculums nature of such program for solving industrial problems.
- To find out the challenges, issues related to the Information Assurance in brief manner.

3.Information Assurance and Similar Educational Programs

Information Assurance is a latest and most emerging domain of security lies on technological policy sciences [2], [3], [7]. Among the other areas, few important are include Information Security, IT Security, Cyber Security, Computer Security, Cyber Forensic & Cryptography etc.

Information Assurance combines with both technological and manual information security related areas and fall under the interdisciplinary approaches and thus following merged nomenclature are also popular and available for the field viz.—

- Information and Cyber Security
- Information Assurance and Security
- IT Security and Information Assurance
- Information Assurance and IT Management
- Information Technology Management and Privacy etc.

Most of these type of programs are also available in different levels in many countries. The most common degree is Masters, among the leading universities; few are depicted in following table: 1.

Table: 1-Depicted few universities offers Masters in Information Assurance internationally

Sl. No.	Institute/ University	Name of the Program	Country
1	Davenport University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (2 Years)	USA
2	Nova South Eastern University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (1 Year)	USA
3	Sam Houston University	MS Information Assurance & Security (1 Year)	USA
4	Florida Institute of Technology	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (1 Year)	USA
5	Oklahoma State University	MS Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
6	CAPELLA University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
7	Western Governors University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
8	Johnson & Wales University	MS Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
9	FAIRLEIGH DICKINSON University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
10	King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals	MS Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	UAE
11	Southern Utah University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
12	Southern Utah University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA

Though few universities have started Information Assurance Doctoral program leading to traditional PhDs and other professional Doctorates. Table: 2 listed few universities in this regard.

Table: 2- Few universities offers Doctoral programs in IA or tagged nomenclature

Universities
Northeastern University
The University of Dallas, Texas
Capella University
The State University of New York
The University of Maryland
Colorado Technical University
University of Fairfax

It is worthy to note that most of these universities includes lot of Coursework including theories and practice in the Doctoral level program. And most of these are both Policy and Technology focused Security courses [8], [9], [12].

4.Information Assurance Program at Bachelors Level: A Case

Information Assurance is broader field and thus many universities have started Bachelors Degree in the field. However, universities are keeps both technological and managerial courses in the curricula. For this study general Search Strategy plays a leading role and total 22 results were considered to find out the BS/ BSc Program in Information Assurance or in similar nomenclature. Here it is important to note that, program without the term “Information Assurance” was not considered. As per the study following three universities noted with the Information Assurance nomenclature. Table: 3 is depicted the list of universities including the courses in detail (Source: URL of the Program).

Table: 2- Few universities offers Doctoral programs in IA or tagged nomenclature

Programs and Universities	Curriculum Focus on the Security
BS-IT (Information Assurance and Cyber Security), offered by the Capella University, United State. 180 Credit	<p>General Education (45 Credit) Communication Humanities Natural Sciences & Mathematics Social Sciences</p> <p>Core Courses (51 Credit) IT Concepts &Practice Communication Strategies for the IT Professionals Introduction to the Database Systems Introduction to Programming with Java Introduction to the Network Technology Ethics for IT Professionals</p>

	<p>Introduction to the Web Development Introduction to the Java Script Business Goals for the IT Professionals User Experience and Interaction Design Hardware & Operating Systems System Administration Software Architecture Intermediate Java Programming Network Architecture Principles of Project Management</p> <p>Specialization (51 Quarter Credit) Introduction to the Programming Cyber Defense & Countermeasures Cyber Attacks & Ethical Hacking Organizational Security Computer Forensic Security Management & Policies Python Scripting Operating Systems and Application Security System Assurance Security Electives (27 Quarter Credit) Capstone Project (06 Credit)</p>
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the City University of Seattle, United State.</p> <p>180 Credit</p>	<p>Basics for the Degree Fundamentals of Accounting Introduction to Web Design Any Two Research Methods & Practice Justice and Ethics Criminal Procedural Law Principle of Micro Economics</p> <p>Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core (45 Credits) Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change (5) Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance (5) Investigation of Cyber Crime (5) Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention (5) Enterprise Risk Management (5)</p>

	<p>Homeland Security and Espionage (5) Policy and Audits (5) IT Compliance (5) Investigation of Business Crimes (5) Or Risk Assessment and Prevention (5)</p> <p>Cybersecurity Technology Core (40 Credits)</p> <p>Network Communications Basics (5) Network Security (5) Data Management Communications and Networking (5) Internet Technologies (5) Information Systems (5) Information Security (5) Tools and Techniques (5) Computer Science I: C++ (5) Or Programming with Python (5)</p> <p>Required Electives (10 Credits) Any Two</p> <p>Legal Issues in the Workplace Operations Management (5) Fundamentals of Criminology (5) Investigation of Business Crimes* (5) Organizational and White-Collar Crime (5) Communicating Crisis, Emergency, and Social Change (5) Systems Analysis and Design (5)</p> <p>Capstone (5 Credits) Bureaupathology (5)</p>
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the University of Michigan-Dearborn, United State.</p> <p>106 Credit</p>	<p>Cyber Security and Information Assurance (CIA) Core</p> <p>Computer Science 1 Computer Science 2 Computer Organization and Assembly Language Data Structure and Algorithm Analysis Software Engineering 1 Database Management Systems</p>

	<p>Computer Networks Web Technology Operating Systems Design Seminar 1 Design Seminar 2</p> <p>Concentration <i>(Cyber Forensic/Cyber Security & Privacy)</i> Cyber Forensic Specialization Digital Forensic-1 Digital Forensic-2 Introduction to Computer and Network Security Or Multimedia Forensic Or Digital Content Protection Criminology Digital Evidence Forensic Evidence Intel and Homeland Security Or Cyber Crime Cyber Security & Privacy Specialization Computer Security Wireless and Mobile Computer Security Data Security & Privacy Intel & Homeland Security Digital Content Protection And one 6 Credit Elective</p>
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It is worthy to note that among the areas related with the Information Assurance most common and merged nomenclature was Cyber Security, and all these result showing universities are belongs to US based.

5. Analysis of the Programs and Challenges

The listed universities have followed the basic nature of Information Assurance and thus listed both technological and managerial courses of security. Among the Technological Security areas few important—

- Network Security & Privacy or Secure Networks and Communications
- Database Security & Privacy or Secure Database and Information Systems

- Web Security or Secure Website
- Internet Security or Secure Internet
- Secure Software Coding or Secure Software Engineering
- Secure Multimedia Systems
- Secure Contents and Privacy
- Hacking and Countermeasures
- Digital Forensic
- Secure Server and System Administration
- Secure Operating Systems

The most universities offers program with basics of IT and then concentration or Major on the Information Assurance area. Homeland security is an emerging area of Information Security as well.

6. Conclusion with Suggestions

Technological Security related to the Information products, services are the core of Information Assurance. Various components and their security concerns are the core of this. Similarly, other hand managerial security also important and as a result most of these universities focused on this and various courses listed within this viz. Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change, Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance, Investigation of Cyber Crime, Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention, Enterprise Risk Management, Homeland Security and Espionage, Policy and Audits of Security, IT Compliance, Investigation of Business Crimes, Risk Assessment and Prevention etc [13], [15], [16]. But it is worthy to note that the areas of manual Content security may also included which are absent and among these few promising may be fundamentals of Information Management, Documentations and Information Sources, Information Management etc. Few emerging technologies may also included viz. Mobile Security, Cloud Security, IoT Security etc for more better results among the products.

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CHANGING PERSPECTIVES IN INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

Kamath Anusuya*, B. K. Veena**

*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.

Email. kamathanusuya@gmail.com

**Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.

Email. veenabk19@gmail.com

Abstract:

Education is a unique asset for human beings to reach their goals in life. Through education any sort of knowledge that is gained can be put into practical basis and by practicing this in our day today life activities will help us to develop our knowledge and get experience. Earlier Gurukula system was one of the unique residential learning systems and here the Guru, the teacher will help his pupil's to acquire knowledge and get an eternal success in their life. In Gurukula the pupil's help their Guru in house core activities and also learn to lead their life in a positive manner as a down to earth learning is been taught to the pupils and as a gesture of respect shown to the Guru they give Gurudakshina at the end of their learning. After Gurukula we can observe the existence of British education policies and they introduced the circular learning system. After independence the government introduced the education is right to all and implemented a free and compulsory primary education to all. Later in education system many innovation and experiment has happened and they introduced an online base learning and teaching by the collaboration with other countries we can get our degree by online courses. The educationists thought that vocational learning is a best method of learning which helps the individual face the competition in this present world than curricular learning system. In present scenario we can observe the global partnership with various countries to get an education in various fields. The changing trends in education has made the people to gain knowledge through practical thinking and bring change in the society and is a part of nations development as Education is the only property that cannot be stolen by anyone.

Keywords: Education, System, Development, Vocational learning, trends in education and Knowledge.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a powerful asset which leads the individual to achieve their goals. In education system we can see tremendous changes as well as development from earlier to till modern century. In primitive time we can observe that giving education as well as getting education is treated as a very sacred aspect in each pupil's life. The objectives of the study are To understand the quality of education system in India. To sensitize the people to change their attitudes through the education system.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Dr. C Chakrabarty; the knowledge, skills and productivity of our growing young and dynamic work force forms the backbone of our economy. To reap the benefits of such a young work force, need to implement the reforms in the education system and also bring forth new factors of production, namely knowledge, skills and technology which have the ability to unleash the productive frontiers of the economy in the most efficient and dynamic way. He further, underlines three major areas to be focused to ensure that our education system is sustainable and meets global standards: i. Quality of Education – in terms of infrastructure, teachers, accreditation, etc. ii. Affordability of Education – ensuring poor and deserving students are not denied education. iii. Ethics in Education – avoiding over-commercialization of education system. According to Dr. RadhikaKapur; In Indian education system, there has been growth taking place. Individuals from all areas and backgrounds are realizing the significance of education, there has been an increase in the enrolment of students in educational institutions and there have been advancements in the teaching-learning methods. On the other hand, the occurrences of problems prove to be impediments, which are required to get eliminated or modified. There should be formulation of appropriate measures and policies and their effective implementation would lead to development of the Indian education system.

According to Mrs. Mukesh Chahal; Higher education in India plays many roles. It is of extraordinary importance to many and reforms are often seen as significant threats to specific, social arrangements that provide benefits to powerful groups. Higher education in India is an extraordinarily important part of modern Indian society and it is intertwined in the political and social systems of the society. It is in need of change, development and important. In order to effectively plan for reforms and improvement, it is necessary to have in realistic perceptions of what is possible and what is not. According to Dr. R. N. Nadar, Indian education system is widely criticized in multi-dimensions for its failure to create required employability in its students according to the industry requirements and its inability to contribute to inclusive growth in the nation as a whole. The issues in the present education system that are daunting the growth of this country can be tackled effectively if constructive and committed actions are taken by the Government to resolve them.

In ancient India the Gurukula System is a residential learning system which had its own value and Gurukula system of learning is a holistic approach as in this system The Guru (Teacher) teaches his Shishyas (Pupil) the disciplined and cultured education which will help them to lead their life in a positive manner. In Gurukula, the Shishyas would help their Guru in the house chore activities which teaches them the simplicity and sharing of responsibilities and so on. After finishing their education pupil's offer Gurudakshina, the one-time fees to their Guru as a token of gratitude. In Ancient India the many famous Kings and rulers built many Universities for higher education like Nalanda University, was one of the famous ancient university built by one of the Gupta emperor named Kumara Gupta. Then there were various other universities like Takshashila, Vikramashila, Valabhi, Somapura and so on. These universities motivated the students to learn more about Indian culture, tradition and involve these in their life. But in India the caste system became one of the cruel aspects specially in getting education in Indian society. Here the people divided them based on their classes and the caste was been upheld and demotivated the lower caste people and these did not get an opportunity to learn from the Gurukula's and Universities this made major change in the system of education as it was been given only to the elites and poor low caste people were

been ignored. Later, when British entered into India they introduced the new type of learning system that is class room teaching and curricular system of learning. In this system, the student and teacher relationship had become commercial in nature as the payment was made in monetary basis this type of learning system made the individuals to learn the different cultures of different countries and here the British's gave more importance to learn the English language. British East India company they had no concern about empowerment in education system in India, their prime goal was to improve their trade and marketing in the country and making a good profit by using education as a weapon; British education system encouraged the pupil to do new innovation in technology as well as they also did the publicity related to their work. British introduced the new educational policies which helped them to gain more from our country.

After independence our government introduced right to education for all. Government made the compulsory and free education for children up to 14 years. But it did not become a success; later, another mile stone of education system in India was the recommendations of national education policy by Kottari Committee. The main objectives of National educational policy were to provide equal educational opportunities for all. To Promote research and technology, to empower advanced agricultural technology the new pattern of education, three language formula, introduction of regional language in higher education, development of agricultural and industrial education and adult education. To combat the changing socio-economic needs of the country, Government of India announced a new National Policy on Education in 1986. Universalisation of primary education, vocationalisation of secondary education and specialisation of higher education were the main features of this policy. The basic recommendations of the policy were related to national form of education, more emphasis on learning, delinking degree for any service, vocationalisation of education, importance on moral values, emphasis on reforms in the examination system, education of the weaker section of the society, starting of an All India Educational Service, starting of Open Universities, establishing many Navodaya Vidyalayas, women education, Operation Blackboard and preservation of culture. Primary education – been free and compulsory. Mid-day meal has been started in schools since 1995 to control the drop-out rate.

The School learning process also changed its teaching methods like Nali Kali, Saturdays No bag Day was to encourage children to learn creative and innovatively engage in the learning process. In higher education system to improve the quality of education the University Grant Commission was introduced in the Central level and drafted new education policy as it sees to the education qualification of the teaching professionals through the competitive exams, granted funds for workshops, seminar, conferences and so on to enhance the knowledge and skills among the pupils and educators. There is a tremendous change in the education system as the degree could be received through online courses. In present trend, the online education has been a blessing for the people who can avail this type of learning and add on to their academics and improve in their career status. It is where they can learn in their leisure time and get a validated certificate. A numerous field is been explored to the general public as there is a global partnership with various countries to get an education in these various fields. Here, the pupils can enrol themselves in these courses which is of their interest based study at their fingertips and enhance knowledge as well as they can get their refresher course, faculty development programmes which is feasible through this online learning. The Indian Government has introduced numerous skill based education for the pupils and also have allocated funds in the annual budget for the same. Here, the pupils get the skill through the experts and also the job placements. If they want to start their own business they can pitch

their ideas and get the fund through government to become an entrepreneur. The education system has been changed through imbibing knowledge and wisdom to vocational training and making a place of their own in the society being independent.

3. CONCLUSION

The changing trend in education through many innovation and experiment has made the people to gain knowledge through practical thinking and bring change in the society and is a part of nation's development. Education is the only property that cannot be stolen by anyone.

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M.TECH. IN IT AND COMPUTING AREAS WITH POSSIBILITIES IN INFORMATION ASSURANCE SPECIALIZATIONS: *THE INNOVATIVE FRONTIERS IN EDUCATION*

P. K. Paul¹, A. Bhuimali², P. S. Aithal³, R. Rajesh⁴

¹*Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India*

²*Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India*

³*Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India*

⁴*Principal, Rohini College of Engineering and Technology, TN, India*

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Information Technology is an important domain within Applied Science and Technology responsible for information affairs leading to collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination. Information Technology has consist with different components and among these important are web technology, network technology, database technology, multimedia technology etc. As far as Information Assurance is concerned, this is fall under the area of network technology mainly within IT and partially database and web technology. The IT and Computing education in India offered in two platform, in one it is the area of Science (Applied) and in another it is fall under the area of Technology/ Engineering. This the IT programs comes with BSc/MSc and BTech and MTech nomenclature. However the BTech and MTech is also offered as BE/ME Degree in some respect. In recent past many universities in India have started the IT and Computing programs with specialization or Honors or Major. The importance of Information Assurance and Cyber Security is increasing; this paper is proposed about the Information Assurance major with MTech-IT and allied degrees keeping in mind Indian need in industry and policies of higher educational institutions. Paper highlighted the model curricula in this context as well. As a whole complete SWOT has been mapped of Information Assurance programs in MTech-IT and allied fields.

Keywords: Information Assurance, IT Security, Information Management, Systems Management, MTech Information Technology (Information Assurance), Indian Higher Education, HEIs, India

1.Introduction

Information Assurance is an advanced field of study and practice which is responsible for the designing, development, management, evaluation of information security. Information Assurance in short called as IA. Information Assurance term got popularity in last few years.

Previously the related known field was Information Security, Information Privacy, Information Technology (IT) Security, Cyber Security, Cryptography etc. The field and nomenclature Information Assurance is widely popular in united states and few western countries. Information Assurance is deals with both Computational Security and Manual Content security. Hence Information Assurance is focused with two major issues and concerns. The manpower and workers of Information Assurance related areas need to know both the areas [1], [5]. Cyber Security's technologies are the prime mover in Information Assurance whereas Information Privacy are also important and valuable in Information Assurance in managerial context. The field of Information Assurance is gaining popularity in different universities worldwide, but most of these universities offers the program as Science degree with BS and MS Degree. But in India few Science and Technology field is available both as Engineering and Applied Sciences Degrees (*and with the common degrees of BE/BTech as Engineering and BS/BSc as Science programs*) and among these important are Computer Science, Electronics, Information Technology etc. Hence as a Technical field Information Assurance may also offered as Engineering program in Indian context.

2.Objective and Agenda

This paper is about Information Assurance and completely theoretical in nature but strongly proposed as a policy paper. The following are few affairs in this regard—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its stakeholders and requirement.
- To learn about the basic features and function of Information Assurance so that we can why Information Assurance is needed as Masters level with reference to Engineering Degree.
- To find out few universities internationally those who are offered Information Assurance program at Masters level with MS/ MSc degree.
- To find out the way and suitable nomenclature of Information Assurance in Information Technology and Computing field.
- To learn about the Indian education sector with reference to Engineering Education to find out the feasibility in Information Assurance as an MTech Specialization.
- To learn about the existing Computing and IT Programs in India to help and design Information Assurance better way.

3.Information Assurance: Overview

Information Assurance is an emerging term in Information Science and Technology related to the privacy and security. Information Assurance is a broad field than that of Information security, Information Technology security and other areas of IT Security viz. Web Security, Database Security, Network security etc. The field Information Assurance is talks about the theory and practice of assuring, managing and assuring information and knowledge [2], [3]. The two sides of Information Assurance, viz. technological and manual solution becomes possible with the expert of Information Assurance. The uses, processing, storage, and transformation of information become easy with Information Assurance practice and principles. Information Assurance is widely available in developed countries as an alternative of cyber security. Hence, Information Assurance can be of following two methods based –

- **Computational/ Technological Information Security**
- **Manual Information Security/ Privacy.**

The following areas and tools are widely used in IT or Cyber Security and these are include but not limited to the following—

- **Database Security**
- **Network Security**
- **Web Security**

4.Information Assurance: Characteristics

Information Assurance become an advanced and super specialty areas of Information Science and Technology and thus many universities offers the programs leading to Bachelors, Masters, Doctoral Degrees and even Certificate, Diploma, Advanced and PG Diploma programs. Due to its need and requirement Information Assurance is gaining popularity worldwide and with the following features and characteristics of Information Assurance we can learn more; why the field becomes popular and available—

- Information assurance is dedicated to the information affairs towards information available to the respective individual in a right place [4], [7].
- Information Assurance is needed for protect data as well as privacy of unauthorized and illegal access.
- Technological security is also under the jurisdiction of this field of Information Assurance.
- Emerging cyber terrorism, cyber war etc concepts are also manageable with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.
- Information Assurance is essential for the mobile security as well as other allied security solutions specially the guidelines and principles etc.
- Design, development, and modernization of a secure and robust database and information systems are also become part of Information Assurance solutions.
- Cloud security including *infrastructure—trust* management become possible in solid and healthy Information Assurance practice in technological way.
- Strategic solutions in information and technological sectors become positively possible in Information Assurance solutions [8], [11].
- Information assurance deals with all the features and function of IT Security so it is dedicated to the malicious attack prevention including ethical hacking [6], [9].
- Fraud management system designing and Cyber forensic solutions are immediately possible with Information Assurance practice.
- Transparencies in information including public right on information are the solutions in Information Assurance.
- The holistic manual information system and computational information system security development are the core job in Information Assurance solutions.
- Management become core in Information Assurance and responsible for the designing, development as well as implementation of Information, cyber and IT related policies, framework and guidelines [10], [12].

Thus Information Assurance become urgency in almost all types of organizations and institutions regardless of private or government these day. As a result in India, Information Assurance should be offered in all the level of education to solve the market requirement in India.

5. Information Assurance and Allied Education

Internationally many universities have started academic and professional programs on Information Assurance and other allied field with the degree MSc/ MS/ BSc/ BS. Among the few universities few are listed in Table: 1.

Table: 1-Showing few international Universities offers Masters program in Information Assurance & Allied Field

Name of the Program
Davenport University
Nova South Eastern University
Sam Houston University
Florida Institute of Technology
George Mason University
Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University
FAIRLEIGH DICKINSON University
King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals
Hampton University
University of Central Missouri
Southern Utah University

6. India and IA Education in Computing and Information Field

Indian Higher Educational Institutes are growing rapidly, Pan India basis there are more than 40000 Higher Educational Institutes [11], [13]. Indian HEIs are categorized into Universities and College; and universities (refer Table: 2) are categorized into following—

- State Universities
- Central Universities
- Private Universities
- Deemed Universities etc

The Institute of National Importance is another kind funded, managed by the Indian Government towards excellence in a particular field (Refer Table: 3). The Computing as a program available in different universities and colleges and among few of them IT security and allied programs are offered.

Table: 2- Showing Indian Universities at a glance

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Central Universities	49	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	399	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	334	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	124	Except some states and UT

Table: 3- The Institute of National Importance at a glance

INI/ Higher Educational Institutions	In Numbers	Location
Indian Institute of Technology [IITs]	23	Bhubaneswar, Chennai, Delhi, Gandhinagar, Guwahati, Hyderabad, Indore, Jodhpur, Kanpur, Kharagpur, Mandi, Mumbai, Patna, Ropar, Roorkee and Varanasi
Indian Institute of Information Technology [IITs]	23	Gwalior, Allahabad, Jabalpur, Kancheepuram, Sri City, Guwahati, Vadodara, Kota, Trichy, Una, Sonapat, Kalyani, Lucknow, Dharwad, Kurnool, Kottayam, Manipur, Nagpur, Pune, Ranchi, Surat, Bhopal, Bhagalpur
National Institute of Technology [NITs]	31	Agartala, Allahabad, Arunachal Pradesh, Bhopal, Calicut, Delhi, Durgapur, Goa, Puducherry, Hamirpur, Jaipur, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Jalandhar, Jamshedpur, Kurukshetra, Nagpur, Patna, Raipur, Rourkela, Sikkim, Silchar, Srinagar, Surat, Karnataka, Tiruchirappalli, Uttarakhand, Warangal
Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology [IESTs]	1 (4 are in process)	Shibpur (West Bengal)
Indian Institute of Management [IIMs]	20	Calcutta, Ahmedabad, Bangalore, Lucknow, Kozhikode, Indore, Shillong, Rohtak, Ranchi, Raipur, Tiruchirappalli, Udaipur, Kashipur
Indian Institute of Science Education and Research [IISERs]	05	Calcutta, Mohali, Thiruvanthapuram, Pune, Bhopal

Other Central Funded Higher Educational Cum Research Institutes	Approximately 150+	Pan India with 28 States and UT
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7.Engineering Education in India

Different kind of colleges viz. Engineering Colleges, Management Colleges, Architecture Colleges, Polytechnic Colleges etc are come under as Engineering program and under the jurisdiction of AICTE. It is important to note that there are enormous opportunity to offer the Educational as well as research programs on Information Assurance in India in several level and platform. As we aware that many international universities and institutes have been started Information programs due to ins need and importance therefore in India as well the Information Assurance and allied programs may be started positively.

Educational programs are changing internationally and come in a new shape. Different universities are moving towards introducing interdisciplinary and skill based programs. Universities from USA, UK and few other developed countries have started Information Assurance and allied programs as Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral Degrees. India as a biggest educational systems may introduce Information Assurance or allied programs in AICTE approved institutes (depicted in Table: 4). Importantly in almost all the discipline viz. Engineering, Management, Computer Applications etc Information Assurance and similar programs may easily accommodate.

Table:4 HEIs under the AICTE and possible programs in Health Informatics at a glance

Streams	Number of Institutes	Controlling Body	Total Intakes (as on 2015)	Remarks on Information Assurance potentiality
Architecture	177	COA/ AICTE	(Annual Intake of 11070)	May Not Possible
Engineering	6375	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 1903722)	Programs Information Assurance in CSE/IT may be started
Management	3217 (MBA)+ 600 (PGDM)	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 366439)	In Techno-Managerial programs, Information Assurance may be offered

Computer Applications	1469	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 110585)	Specialization of Information Assurance may be offered in MCA/BCA
Polytechnic	4276	AICTE	(Annual Intake of 1308008)	Special thrust may be given in higher semester for Information Assurance papers etc in CSE/IT related courses. Or full-fledged Information Assurance degree may be started

8.MTech Traditional in IT and Allied Fields with Reference to Information Assurance Specialization Potentialities—

Most of the university and colleges offered the departments and schools in following subjects and bellow mentioned areas as Engineering and Technology degrees including MTech Degrees—

- *Computer Science* (Computer Science is mathematical in nature and related with hardcore theoretical areas such as computing logic, software systems, hardware systems, tools, technologies responsible for Computing systems design and development)
- *Computer Application* (Computer Application is responsible for the design and development of software based applications)
- *Computer Science and Engineering* (It is a kind of merging domain and deals the domain of Computer Science and Computer Engineering. It is also related with hardware, mechanics, computing logics including systems development)
- *Information Technology* (It is kind of applied science responsible for information solutions viz. collection, selection, processing, management and dissemination with various technologies such as Multimedia Technology, Computing, Communication Technology, Networking Technology, and Web Technology)
- *Information Systems* (It is related with IT but focused on industry and managerial context)

And hence in all these subjects MTech/ME is offered and naturally due to the demand of the subject i.e. Information Assurance may be introduced.

Here two different approaches may be selected in first, the Information Assurance specialization may be started partially whereas in another approach it may be from 2nd year onwards. The specialization in Information Assurance may also nomenclature as following—

- Cyber Security & Information Assurance
- IT & Assurance

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- Information Systems and Assurance
 - Computer Forensic and Information Assurance etc

It is worthy to introduce various skill based components into the Information Assurance programs viz. Industrial Tour, tie-ups, Industrial Projects, and Skill based Internship for more value addition to the program.

9. Issues and Challenges

There are certain issues pertaining Information Assurance education at MTech in IT and Computing. The possible specializations may be as under

- MTech/ME-Information Technology (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Computer Science and Engineering (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Computer Application (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Information Systems (Information Assurance)

In these programs, Information Assurance may be suitably added but for that apart from skilled manpower in Information Technology Security few other domains are also required viz. Law and Legal Studies, Management, Social and Information Studies etc, as the Information Assurance branch combines both technology and manual contents.

Information Assurance is broad and thus huge amount of financial support is required for the Division, Units and Departments running the program. From students end, the Information Assurance needs interdisciplinary knowledge as well. Initiatives from different stakeholders and related departments are also solicited. Unwillingness towards a new subject like Information Assurance is an important challenges for any interdisciplinary programs and Information Assurance as an interdisciplinary program and moreover skill based is an important challenge.

10. Conclusion with Suggestions

Information Assurance as an advanced program gaining popularity in different sectors, in India technological education is split into two; i.e. Science and Engineering. Hence Information Assurance may be started as a full-fledged degree viz. MTech/ MS- Information Assurance, if infrastructure and other equipments are available. Otherwise, the field can be started as a specialization in other IT and Computing subjects as prescribed above. Here both full-fledged degree and specialization can a treated as unique and innovative program; as worldwide M.Tech. is not offered and Information Assurance is available with MS/MSc Degree. And in India MTech is offered with other broader subjects as defined previously. In an existing university and departments MTech in Computing and IT related subjects, Information Assurance may be a good alternative. And even similar specializations may also be started with solid research or industrial atmosphere.

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Paper 11

A STUDY ON THE INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN EMPLOYEE RETENTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AVIATION INDUSTRY IN INDIA

Jayaprakasha K^{1*} Pradeep M.D.^{2**}

^{*1}Lecturer, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India, Email: jai4appu@gmail.com

^{**2}Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

Abstract

Employee retention involves the effective management of organization through retaining eminent work force thereby considered to be the mastery of managing resources. Every organization invests its time and money to groom newly recruited and developing them to be an efficient employee. Losing a trained employee is a great loss for any organization. Employee retention is an art of using various unique techniques to influence an employee to stay in an organization for the longer duration of his service. Hertz Berg's and Maslow's in their theory have quoted about factors influencing for individual growth and development. Aviation business is facing a serious problem of high attrition since long due to the shortage of technical, non-technical and other skilled professionals. The retention strategies in business help in reducing employee turnover, recruitment and training cost. It also preserves talent and organizational knowledge. The businesses have inculcated trending tools of competitive salary, fringe benefits, skilled hiring, work life balance, career development, friendly work culture, employee engagement, branding, bonding, open communication, work from home, flexible working, fancy designation to demark employee retention. Innovative strategies for employee retention in aviation sector are the need of the day. This paper highlights upon various modern tools and strategies on employee retention with special reference to aviation industry emphasizing on out of the box benefits to its employees.

Keywords: Employee Retention, Efficient Employee, Techniques, Aviation Industry, benefits

1. INTRODUCTION

In simple words, Employee retention means the act of maintaining and sustaining the existing employment relationship for a longer period. It is considered as the biggest ability of any organization, which is essential for organizational success. It is a dynamic process where the employer encourages their employees to remain with the organization for the maximum period of time through innovative retention strategies. The success of any organization is determined by the productivity and effort of its employees as well as the satisfaction that they obtain from their jobs, fellow workers, management, work environment, the rewards system

and the career growth opportunity. The retention of the skilled employee is the major concern of every manager. Maintaining the skills of employees' in order to maintain a competitive edge is becoming very essential in the world of Globalization and Privatization. The process of retention starts from recruitment, hiring the right candidate for the right job is the prime requisite in employee retention. With the introduction of low-cost carriers, aviation industry witnessed a dramatic change and growth during the past decades, which revolutionized the aviation business. But meantime retention of skilled human resource in the aviation business became a challenging task due to various reasons. As per the latest studies, 50 per cent of the employees would leave their current job for better financial and non-financial benefits. "Employee retention is a voluntary act and process of building and promoting a positive working environment by engaging employees for a long period with the organization for mutual benefit"

2. SCOPE OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION

The Cabin crew job has become one of the most stressful occupations due to the perpetual pressure carried while performing duties both on the ground and on board but, the airlines adopting strategies of cost-cutting considers its employees like machines without providing job security, reduced wage and long hours of work [1]. The lack of talented-workers and the risk of losing their skilled, experienced human-resources are considered as the key issues of modern organizations [2]. Abraham Maslow's need hierarchy theory emphasizes on the need of companies to consider factors like employees' health, job security, and remuneration. When employees know that their employer care about their health and that their job is guaranteed, they will be bound to the company [3]. The Airline companies are continuously losing on the skilled employees and are facing a big challenge in retaining these employees. Airlines recruit the most qualified and skilled candidates, retaining these highly skilled employees are a bigger challenge. The employee joins an organization with lot of expectations and employees tend to leave the organization sooner in case if the job in a particular airline company is not meeting their expectation. It is the responsibilities of the managers to examine and identify the reason for retention and formulation of suitable retention strategy. Herzberg's theory focuses on factors like motivator and hygiene factors which determine the rate of employee retention. The motivator factors such as recognition, achievement, work, growth, and advancement will lead to employee satisfaction whereas the hygiene elements like factors include a relationship with management, supervision, remuneration, relationship with colleagues, working conditions and the rules and policies of the company will cause dissatisfaction [4].

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The core objective of this study is to understand the reasons behind the deficiency of qualified professionals in Aviation Industry. It finds the reason behind attrition, analyze employee retention strategies and examining the changes in the emerging trends to retain aviation work force. The paper also examines the sensitive factors like ergonomics, workplace sexual harassment, racial discrimination, technology, HR Policies and its impact on employees in an organization.

4. ATTRITION IN AVIATION INDUSTRY

Turnover of key employees will have dangerous consequences on organization's objectives. With the changing environment, the needs, requirements and expectations of the

employees also changes. So it is the responsibility of every organization to hold their employees tightly because they are capable of building and breaking of any organization. Factors like lack of professionalism, corruption, over involvement of external bodies such as Government and other Agencies, behavior of co-worker will also lead to employee attrition. These factors have an effect on the attitude of the employees resulting in frustration, causing them to change jobs for a better environment, and increasing turnover rates particularly in the aviation sector. Employee turnover issues could be reduced if these factors are paid due attention and managed properly.

5. BREAKTHROUGHS TOWARDS RETAINING EMPLOYEES

Identity of Airline Company is the prestige for its employees. The elements like organizational culture, reputation, benefits, opportunities for advancement will contribute to the brand image. Airlines recruits the most qualified and skilled candidates, retaining these highly skilled employees are a bigger challenge. The employee joins an organization with lot of expectations and employees tend to leave the organization in case of not meeting their expectation. This HR Policy must be conveyed to the employees to plans for the future to increase the employee commitment, personal productivity [5]. Competitive compensation is the most crucial factor of an employee retention strategy [6]. There is a positive relationship between employee retention and job security. Leadership styles effects retention factor. Increased workload creates poor work-life balance. Proper Performance Management System facilitate career development [7]. As the industry jobs are highly risky involving high rate of hazards, providing proper work environment will prevent attrition. The subcontracting for low-bid contractors are worsening the working conditions of baggage handlers, security, cabin cleaners, janitors, wheelchair attendants. The Airline Companies invest a huge amount to training programs to train with virtual reality technique to motivate employees to stick to their jobs [8]. The emergence of low cost career has adversely affected the overall hiring and compensation culture of the industry. The fancy designation is one of retention tools. The racial harassment is the crucial issue in modern working environment. Some organizations offers retention bonus to their employees. A culturally oriented leadership with embracing norms harms the retention [9]. Air Traffic Controlling job profile involves highly complex procedures resulting stress and fatigue hence these jobs are installed with latest know-how with training, job design etc. [10].

6. CONCLUSION

Employee retention has become a global agenda. Ergonomics consideration in Airline industry to increase employee retention rate are lighting, tools and equipment, health and safety Issues, preventing back injuries, work style, stress, fatigue, shift, risk factors etc. Employee retention is a dynamic process, where technique used by the organization also changes with the time. Influential leadership behavior can win the trust and will bring satisfaction to the employees, which will further result in higher organizational commitment and higher level of retention [11]. This paper shows that the poor organization culture and non-effective HR policies are the major reason behind high attrition in recent years. By exploring the HR policies and strategies with innovative and progressive measures can retain its talents.

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PAPER 12

**MOBILE APPLICATIONS SECURITY: AN
OVERVIEW AND CURRENT TREND****P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²**¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal,
India²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**Corresponding Author:** pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com**Abstract**

Mobile Security is an emerging concept and name in Information Technology Security. It is very close with Mobile Computing and concerns with the securing mobile based services and products. It is the protection and system against the attack and vulnerabilities and applicable to the smart phones, tablets, laptop etc. Mobile Security is also related with the wireless security. The concept of securing mobile devices becomes important and valuable and increasing rapidly in recent past. Today the organizations and institutions of different kinds are using various Information Technology tools and components and all are connected to the internet or online systems and as a result vulnerability became crucial. The mobile applications security may be two types active and passive. The device loss becomes an important concern and apart from these few important are application security, device leakages, malware attack, device theft etc. The individuals are also employing different tools and devices and all such products become challenge now days. There are different methods in attacking the systems and also preventing. All these attacking systems and preventing systems are increasing day by day. The domain Information Assurance, as deals with both technology and managerial affairs of the security; so the Mobile Security field is also an important area of the field. This is a conceptual paper and theoretical in nature and deals with several affairs of Mobile Security.

Keywords: Mobile Security, IT Security, Cloud Security, Information Assurance, IT Protection, Digitalization, Information Systems

1.Introduction

Mobile Security is the need of hour; organizations, institutions and individuals are today actively engaged with the mobile and similar devices and all such devices are great threats due to many reasons. Mobile Security or mobile device securities etc are today an important concern of Information Security [1], [5]. There are different means for the attack and its prevention and among the threat of attack few important attack zones and areas are SMS and MMS, in Telecommunication Systems, attack based on GSM and Wi-Fi, Bluetooth systems, web browser, operating systems, attack based on hardware and infrastructure, password cracking in secured software, malware etc [2], [3].

There are different reasons for the security and among these device loss are important concern, many a times we may forgot to take the devices or simply lost the devices [4], [8], [9]. Application security is another concern, which is also very important to take. Today many applications are available freely and that comes with different features and all these vulnerable in many contexts. Similarly data leakage is another concern and data loss results the malicious attack in some cases Malware attack is another concern that concerns about the Mobile Security. According to a study it has been noted that 81% of mobile malware are Trojans, and then rest it monitoring tools (10.1%) and also few malicious applications (5.1%). Today each and every organizations are giving importance to the wireless and mobile security there are different measures available to solve these, and different organizations are also involved into this [5], [6], [7].

2.Objective and Agenda

As the current paper is theoretical and conceptual in nature and thus deals with various affairs leading to Mobile Security and allied areas and among these few important are—

- To learn about the basics of Mobile Security including its features, characteristics and nature.
- To learn about the field of Mobile Security and allied areas in brief.
- To find out the threats and attacking systems to the mobile based IT products and services in brief.
- To learn about the basics of prevention methods of Mobile Security in simple sense.
- To learn about the limitations of such security measure in brief.
- To learn about the Mobile Security Management concepts and tools to manage the overall system.

3.Mobile Security: The Root

Mobile Security is very much close with the wireless security. Very simply, Mobile Security is nothing but the securing mobile services and mobile devices from the third party attack or vulnerability. Today profit making as well as nonprofit making institutes are engaged with different kind of tools and technologies and most of these are mobile based and thus Mobile Security is very close concern about this [6], [10], [11]. It is worthy to note that previous to the concept of Mobile Security the concept of computer security got popularized which is small area and very close to securing the computer itself. Gradually other areas of security has been conceptualized and among these important are IT Security, Information Security are important.

IT Security is concern with different sub fields viz. Web Security, Network Security, Database Security and so emerging areas viz. Cloud Security, Mobile Security etc. Hence Mobile Security is the part of advanced IT Security in many contexts. Different Companies are using different strategies for the Mobile Security and among these, one important is allowing client and employers to use only respective or selected devices only. It has been noted as per a latest survey that 84 % of the threats are fall under the Trojans and rest from other insecure systems. Thus most of the organizations and institutions are using Mobile Security tools and strategy to keep the system smart and advanced [6], [12], [14].

The field Mobile Security is very close with the Wireless Security as well. But wireless security concept developed earlier than Mobile Security and today apart from wireless

security it is very much close with the cloud security, mobile computing as well [11], [13], [15].

4. Mobile Security and Attacks or Threat

Mobile security is an important part of today's Information Technology world. It is very close with mobile computing. In other word it is also called as security of mobile based devices like smart phones. Mobile security normally associated with smart phone, computer etc by the attackers. Normally this comes with short message service (SMS), multimedia messaging service (MMS), WIFI, Bluetooth etc. However few experts are also warns about the operating system security because attackers may use different objects by the browsers or OS or malicious software's. It is worthy to note that downloadable apps sometime also cause for mobile security. Any smart phone or electronic devices should come with privacy and integrity applications. According to network expert the major target of the attackers are-

Data: As smart phone or electronic devices contains different kind of sensitive or virtual information such as –credit card no., authentication indication, audio, visual content, call log etc. So this is the prime target.

Identity: With an electronic device the owner can be indentified easily and hare attackers may use this identity for different purposes.

As far as modern threads are concern with mobile security; concerned with different objects such as-

1. Boot nets
2. Spyware
3. Malicious link
4. Malicious applications

The first one normally holds malware and user get it normally by email attachment. Boot net is a combination of robot and network and it is normally denoting malicious affairs. Here attackers from the network place can control the device and harm the overall system.

Spyware is useful simply to highjack the phone including hare the calls, see the text and content, to know the location of the device by the GPS.

Malicious link normally spread on social networking site for wider distribution and that can be by the backdoors.

Malicious application is available in different app platform. It is useful to get personal information or to enter into the system.

Most of these attackers belong to different community. Many of them are unethical hackers, some of them are professional and they may work in commercial house or military services. However the concept of black hat attackers and grey hat attackers are gaining popularity.

5. Different methods in Mobile Security

There is different attacking system for mobile security and that may cause in the following-

1. Attack based on SMS and MMS

2. Attack based on different kind of network like GSM network and WIFI based network
3. Web browser
4. Operating system
5. Hardware and vulnerabilities
6. Insecure software etc.

In mobile security **SMS** is also a weak point sometime. It causes in the mobile system having binary SMS system. It leads the denial of service attack. We can see such witness in SIMENS S55 model having Chinese Character. Similarly in earlier days few Nokia phones are also unable to recognize denial of service attack. It is important to note that distributed denial of service is also an important attack to the mobile and the telecommunication system.

In mobile security another focus attacking place is **GSM** network. The GSM encryption belongs to **A5** algorithm and their vulnerabilities is an important concern. We can see this kind of attack in some of the Europeans countries. Gradually **A5/3** and **A5/4** algorithm have been popular against this kind of attack. After the development of 2G GSM we can see the vulnerabilities. The hackers in recent past can also break the GSM algorithm.

As far as the **WIFI** is concerned in recent past the attackers can get information of a smart phone by find out the vulnerabilities. The security of wireless network previously secured by **WEP** (Wired equivalent privacy algorithm) keys but the weakness of WEP altered by **WIFI Protected Access (WPA)** and **WPA3** algorithm. The protocol Temporal Key Integrity (TKIP) has been introduced to allow the migration of **WPA2** and **WPA3**.

In the recent past security is also an important concern for **Bluetooth** system. With Bluetooth one can easily break the vulnerabilities. The attackers are required to connect to port for accessing or controlling the device or mobile. In Bluetooth system attackers send a file and if users download the file then the system may be corrupted such as CABIR (SYMBIAN).

6.Security Management & Mobile Security

There are different tools and defending methods exists for Security Management and among these few important are as follows—

Operating Systems—

Operating System is the core of Mobile devices and there are different mechanism for ensuring and protecting Operating Systems from the threat. Smart phones are able in accommodating different kind of applications into it and thus there should be proper mechanism to detect the vulnerabilities and any kind of virus, malware, spyware etc. Sandbox is an important matter in mobile and each mobile phone needs to plan for specific Sandbox in this regard. Few important concern (mainly in Android) in this regard are include—

- The intrusion of the rootkit is very important and thus proper rootkit detection mechanism is very important.
- Process isolation is also very important in android based systems and for proper and scientific security this should be keep in mind. Moreover here each process once start should complete and then only may enter other program. This approach will reduce the chances of vulnerability.

- File system permission is very important concern of android based systems and use of locking memory permission is also with this kind of system.
- Memory protection is an important feature and function of Operating Systems of android based or any similar kind of devices.
- Development through runtime environment is an important concern and here valuable to note that high level language based designed products are suitable for this purpose [7],[16], [18].

Hardware Systems—

The hardware system is vulnerable in different situations. There are different types of attacks/vulnerabilities viz.—

- Electromagnetic waveform is a vital reason for the attacks and these are increasing every day.
- Juice jacking is the vulnerability of mobile security in different context. This is may be applicable in public places during charging of mobile phones in the bus, flights, train and other places. Such type of incident may noticed in different places. Different malicious attacks may be happen in this case. Here actually, USB charger mainly used for the attacking victims.
- Jail breaking and rooting is another vulnerability and related to the physical vulnerability. It is related to the operating systems security.

Malicious Software based Vulnerability—

There are different types of vulnerability can be noted in malicious software as far as Mobile devices are concerned. These days smart phones are highly using for the internet purpose and we aware that a malware is a program responsible for harming the system. A study noted that, the malware variant has been increased in recent past up to 54%. Worms, viruses are considered important in this category [17], [19]. The malicious attacks can be possible with three types viz.—

- Infection of the systems and that can be classified into Explicit Permission, Implied Permission, Common Interaction, No Interaction—all these malicious software are important to attack the mobile device.
- The accomplishment of its goal; which include the affecting the systems after entering the malicious software into the systems and that is done by the monetary damage, damage data and/or device, as well as concealed damage.
- Spread of the malware to other systems is another way to vulnerable the systems and among these important. Here Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and infrared or even using remote networks viz. telephones calls or SMS or emails spreading can be done.

Day by day the malware is increasing and these include the Viruses and Trojans, Ransomware, Spyware etc. Though, according to the Information Scientist few attacks of the systems are includes (refer Fig: 1)

Fig: 1- The vulnerability in Mobile Devices at a glance

7.Mobile Security Policy and Countermeasure

The Mobile Security can be bring with different countermeasure and policy and among these few important are include as follows—

In Operating Systems—

In a mobile, the first preference of the security is required for Operating Systems; resource management, schedule processing and other components role needs to be useful and secure in different sense. The sandbox is the important component of the mobile; where different applications are stored together and thus it is required the operating systems should be secure.

In Security Software—

Security Software is another important component and way to secure the mobile devices. Apart and above of the operating systems security this is important and essential and this is required to protect the mobile systems. Antivirus and firewall is essential to protect the systems. Importantly, it is required as signature detection software detects malicious executable files. The following are important concern in this regard—

- Visual Notification is another important action required for securing mobile devices; especially mobile phones. This is the image based result, viz. incoming call

information on the display unit. Hence if a call triggered by malicious apps that can be noted and detect, if possible.

- Turing Test is another way to bring the security in the mobile devices. It is the applications of Artificial Intelligence; required to distinguish human and virtual users; viz. Captcha.
- Technique of identifying a person by means of their morphology is another security measure. The field in generally may be called as Biometrics. Biometrics is used by studying face, eyes etc. Here no need to remember the password as well. Hence this can be a good tool for mobile security.

Resource Monitoring in Devices—

There are different ways in resource monitoring and we can get an idea on suspicious attack and among these few important are depicted as follows—

- Monitoring battery consumption of the phone may be useful to detect whether any malicious application running or not.
- Every application has a specified memory requirement and it can be suspicious when a applications requires more than that.
- In smart phones many applications are run via network and *like previous point on memory*, the speed of operation of the application can be monitored. Sometimes higher bandwidth than the requirement can be treated as suspicious.

Network Related Issues—

As far as Network Surveillances is concerned following are important to noted—

- Spam is common in Emails and thus for the Emailing services in mobile spam matter should be consider as important.
- Encryption of stored information and data needs to be keep safe and here encryption may be used. Additionally for transferring data also encryption algorithm can be useful.
- Telecom Network monitoring is also important issues for secure mobile based services.

Product Development and Manufacturing—

As far as product development and manufacturing is concerned few things are important and among these valuable are—

- Deleting debug mode is very important in the mobile phones. This mode needs to removed in the devices before its sell to the consumer. Today one manufacturer developed lot of devices and sometimes they sold it in debug mode; so these should be keep in mind carefully.
- During the selling of a smart phone it is essential to keep that in Default setting; otherwise that can led Denial of Service attack.
- The smart phone market is emerging and with lots of applications. It is worthy to note that the security audits of applications are very important and valuable otherwise the whole system may be corrupted or infected.

- Every applications in the android system is asked for permission during its installation and thus during such activity it is essential to read the content carefully and if found unethical or suspicious information.
- Revocation procedure is another one in android system and can be managed by the app provider or system administrator; here uninstall of the app is possible globally. Hence this way security can be ensured.
- Avoid heavily customized systems, may have dual effect of risking the introduction of new bugs in the system and it is an important security concern.
- The updates of the software or patches must be come with the documentation by the manufacturer. Hence by reading everything one can update the systems easily.

User Awareness—

User awareness is very important for running safe and secure android based system. It is a fact that most of the users are not read carefully the messages and details of the applications. Here application provider reputation, security messages, agreement messages are very important. Even there may be some software or application with intensions of phishing etc. Caring the phone with the owner is also important security measure in some cases. Different organizations and association has provided different framework and guidelines all of these need to follow by different stakeholders (refer fig: 2 for details). Different apps and system need to closedown if not required viz.—

- Digital camera
- GPS
- Bluetooth interface
- USB interface
- Removable storage etc.

Moreover latest android phones are come with inbuilt encryption systems with this it may be difficult to hack the systems or loose the information. Here the system may be encrypt or SD card etc.

Centralized Storage Systems—

Sometimes it is better to keep the data and all the text in the company server and storage systems instead of Third Party Company or even own mobile devices.

Fig: 2- Major IT Security Framework providers

8. Conclusion

As a whole Mobile Security is needs different counter measures and defending mechanism but still there are certain issues for which it is difficult to perform the security. And among these few important are Operating Systems. It is worthy to note that, few operating system are single tasking hence such are not capable to do the task along with firewall or antivirus. Energy autonomy is another important concern that should keep in mind. It is worthy to note that, network utilization should not be too high for the security reason. Apart from the technological countermeasure, it is essential to have users interest and awareness for the security related concern. Moreover, few things are essentials viz. rich operating systems, secure operating systems, secure element, secure applications etc.

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Paper 13

OPINION OF TEENAGERS ON THE IMPACT OF A DIVORCED FAMILY IN MANGALURU

Anuradha Shetty *, D'Mello Laveena**

HOD, Dept of Rural Development, School of Social Work, RoshniNiilaya, Mangaluru.

**Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

Marriage is a union between individuals, establishing rights and obligations between them and the resulting biological or adopted children and affinity. The provision of breaking this marriage is called a divorce, which may be due to several personal reasons of the parents but it may affect the children born out of this wedlock in many ways that are physical and psychological in nature. This study aims at learning about the impact that a broken family has on a teenager. It also aims at understanding the level of awareness among teenagers about maintaining a healthy family. This study is descriptive in design. The information has been collected using the questionnaire method. The findings are that even though majority of the families do have fights between themselves but not end up in divorces. They spend the quality time with their children. But in the case of the broken family, the children are affected badly both mentally and emotionally even few developed mental illnesses.

Keywords: Divorce, Impact, Teenagers, Broken Family, Marriage, Children, Relationships, Mental Health

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of human society, a **family** is a group of people related either by consanguinity, affinity, or co-residence or some combination of these. Members of the immediate family may include spouses, parents, brothers, sisters, sons, and daughters. Members of the extended family may include grandparents, aunts, uncles, cousins, nephews, nieces, and siblings-in-law. Sometimes these are also considered members of the immediate family, depending on an individual's specific relationship with them.

Marriage is a socially or ritually recognized union between spouses that establishes rights and obligations between those spouses, as well as between them and any resulting biological or adopted children and affinity (in-laws and other family through marriage). When children are born out of this wedlock, it would constitute of a family. Socially, it is such that the parents would take care of their family, that is, their children.

Divorce, also known as **dissolution of marriage**, is the process of terminating a marriage or marital union. It usually entails the canceling or reorganizing of the legal duties and responsibilities of marriage, thus dissolving the bonds of matrimony between a married couple under the rule of law of the particular country or state. Grounds for divorce vary widely from country to country. Marriage may be seen as a contract, a status, or a

combination of these. Where it is seen as a contract, the refusal or inability of one spouse to perform the obligations stipulated in the contract may constitute a ground for divorce for the other spouse. In contrast, in some countries (such as Sweden, Finland, Australia, New Zealand), divorce is purely no fault. Many jurisdictions offer both the option of a *fault* divorce as well as an *at fault* divorce. This is the case, for example, in many US states.

A broken family can negatively affect all domains of the child's development. The effects of a broken family on a child's development depend on numerous factors, including the age of the child at the time of parents' separation, and on the personality and family relationships. Although infants and young children may experience few negative developmental effects, older children and teenagers may experience some problems in their social, emotional and educational functioning. Although this may not always be true, studies suggest that children from divorced families are more likely to exhibit such behavioral issues than those from non-divorced families.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to a study by Paul R. Amato, Laura Spencer Loomis, Alan Booth (1995) using a 12-year longitudinal study, they find that the consequences of parental divorce depend on parental marital conflict prior to divorce. In high-conflict families, children have higher levels of well-being as young adults if their parents divorced than if they stayed together. But in low-conflict families, children have higher levels of well-being if their parents stayed together than if they divorced. In marriages that do not end in divorce, parental marital conflict is negatively associated with the well-being of offspring. Franklin, K. M., Janoff-Bulman, R., & Roberts, J. E. (1990) Two studies were conducted to examine the long-term impact of parental divorce on beliefs about the self and others. In Study 1, college-aged children of divorce and students from intact families did not differ on 8 basic assumptions or on measures of depression. Those whose parents had divorced, however, were less optimistic about the success of their own future marriages. Assumptions about the benevolence of people best predicted the marital optimism of the parental divorce group, but not of the intact family group. In Study 2, assumptions about the benevolence of people were explored in terms of trust beliefs. College-aged children of divorce and a matched sample from intact homes differed only on marriage-related beliefs, not on generalized trust. Children of divorce reported less trust of a future spouse and were less optimistic about marriage. Exploratory analyses found that continuous conflict in family of origin adversely affected all levels of trust.

A Government research in the UK had found that Children from broken families are nearly five times more likely to suffer damaging mental troubles than those whose parents stay together. The report was funded by the Department of Health and published by the Office for National Statistics. They investigated emotional disorders - ranked as those which cause considerable distress and interference with the way in which children perform at school and during play. It also looked at conduct disorders which result in aggressive, violent or anti-social behaviour. The researchers studied nearly 8,000 children aged between five and 16 in 2004 and found almost one in ten had disorders. They checked again in the year 2007 and the report says that, a child whose parents had split during this time was more than four and a half times more likely to have developed an emotional disorder than one whose parents stayed together. They were nearly three times more likely to exhibit a conduct disorder. Eleven per cent of those children whose families broke up had emotional disorders, against 3 per cent among those whose families were still together. According to a study conducted by Kobrin and Waite(1986), in the

‘Effects of Childhood Family Structure on the Transition to Marriage.’, the consequences of divorce flow from generation to generation, since the children of divorce are more likely to experience the same problems and pass them on to their own children.

According to Sara S. McLanahan (1988), in her work, ‘Family Structure and Dependency: Early Transitions to Female Household Headship,’ The children of divorced parents are more likely to get pregnant and give birth outside of marriage, especially if the divorce occurred during their mid-teenage years. A study by Arland Thornton (1990), in ‘Influence of the Marital History of Parents on the Marital and Cohabitation Experiences of Children,’ says that divorce appears to result in a reduction of the educational accomplishments of the affected children, weakens their psychological and physical health, and predisposes them to rapid initiation of sexual relationships and higher levels of marital instability and it also raises the probability that they will never marry. According to Amato, a study conducted in 1971 showed 60 divorced families along with 131 children. After five years, two-thirds of the children “were clinically depressed, were doing poorly in school, had difficulty maintaining friendships, [and] experienced chronic problems such as sleep disturbances”. As supported by the study, these children may have started acting aggressive and “engaging in bullying behaviour, both of which can negatively affect peer relationships.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive in nature and deals with the impact of broken families on the teenagers in Mangaluru, Karnataka. It was conducted on 20 respondents, all of whom are teenagers residing within the boundary of Mangaluru. The tool used for the study is questionnaire and it was administered online to the respondents.

Objectives:

1. To study about the impact of a broken family on a teenager.
2. To assess the awareness among teenagers about maintaining good family relations.
3. To find out the solutions for the probable solutions that can help the teenagers overcome the difficulties that they are going through.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The age groups of the 20 respondents varies from 17-22 with majority of them being in the age of 20. Around 80% of the respondents were female. The respondents are all residents of Mangaluru. Majority of them had educated fathers working as doctors, business men and bankers whereas 70% of their mothers were homemakers. None of the respondents were a single child. The parents of 80% of the respondents are living together whereas of 20% respondents are living separately.

4.1 Parental Fights

It can be seen that the parents of 75% of the respondents fight whereas of 25% do not indulge in fights.

4.2 Quality time

It is evident that 90% of the parent(s) of the respondent do spend quality time with their children by talking to them, going on picnics/vacations, taking them to parks, sharing stories, watching movies etc. Whereas 10% of the respondent believe that the parents are busy with their own work.

4.3 Blaming

From the above pie chart, we can see that 95% of the parents of the respondents do not blame the child for the fights that they have had, at the same time 5% of the parents have blamed the child.

4.4 Walking Out

According to the data acquired, it can be seen that a parent of 80% respondents have not walked out of the family whereas a parent of 20% of the respondents have walked out.

4.5 Friends with Divorced Families

It is evident that 75% of the respondents have had friends with divorced families whereas 25% of the respondents do not have friends with divorced or broken families.

4.6 Link to Mental Illness (Depression, Anxiety etc.)

All the respondents equally agree that broken families can also be a cause to mental illnesses among teenagers such as depression, anxiety etc.

4.7 Effect of walking out

75% of the respondents who have had a parent walk out of their family (20% as illustrated above) said that they felt very bad and were also scared but it made them stronger whereas the rest said that they understood the reason why the parent had to leave and hence it didn't affect much.

4.8 Reasons why families break

According to the responses received, 50% of the respondents believe that marriages break due to lack of respect and misunderstandings. Whereas the other 50% believes that it is due to lack of commitment, falling out of love, communication gaps, incompatibility, lack of trust, having to give up dreams etc.

4.9 Effect on a child

This question received varied responses from the respondents such as the child would feel abandoned and that would isolate them which leads them into depression, they would misbehave, lack self-confidence and self-esteem, lowers morale and tends to repeat the same behaviour in future. Whereas 25% of them seem to believe that this would lead to having trust and commitment issues for the child and losing faith in the institution of marriage.

4.10 Effect on friends

Every respondent who have had a friend hailing from a broken family (75% as mentioned above) says that they were affected very badly by this. They say that it makes them depressed, lonely and tend to blame themselves for what has happened. They tend to have random emotional outbursts and lose self-confidence. They lose faith in relationships and do not trust anyone. Some of them also believe that it may have made them mentally stronger.

4.11 Child ensuring secure family

As individuals, this question had received varied responses such as they could go for counselling, encourage live-in relationships, understanding partners better, conversing and communicating effectively, marrying someone out of their own choice, respectfully handling situations etc.

4.12 Parent ensuring secure family

The respondents believe that the parents should be responsible, patient, love by keeping their egos aside, by living by their vows, instilling family values, communicating effectively, compromising, understanding themselves and family and trusting them, spending more time with each other and providing equal respect.

4.13 Role of Government/NGO in securing families

Majority believe that the role Government and NGOs play are secondary in nature. They could provide counselling and spread awareness about the importance of family and the impact of divorce on the children.

5. MAJOR FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:

Out of the 20 respondents, all being teenagers, 80% are females. Most of the mothers of the respondents are home makers. 20% of the respondents have parents who live separately. 75% of them have fights in the family. 10% do not have parents who spend quality time with them and only 5% of them have had parents blame them for their fights. 20% of them have had a parent walk out of the family and 75% of them have had friends with divorced families.

100% of them believe that broken families could also be a cause to mental illnesses such as depression, anxiety, etc.

It is important to be seen that even though majority of the families do have fights between them, not all end up in divorces. Arguments usually arise among families and the task lies in handling them. When it is not handled properly or when there is a major mismatch, it results in a broken family.

Even though there are 20% of the parents of respondents who are living separately and have walked out on the family, there is still 90% of parent spending quality time with the child. They spend quality time with their children by talking to them, going on picnics/vacations, taking them to parks, sharing stories, watching movies etc. Whereas 10% of the respondent believe that the parents are busy with their own work.

However, it is the mental impact of the broken family on the child that has to be carefully understood. The ones who have been affected by it and respondents who have had friends who went through it clearly mentions how badly it has affected them. Though it makes them stronger in the long run, it breaks them down emotionally and affects several parts of their lives. They tend to even have mental illnesses such as depression and anxiety to which 100% of the respondents agreed unequivocally.

6. CONCLUSION:

It is detrimental to believe that a broken family can mentally disturb a child. The way it impacts the child's mind are as follows:

1. Health Problems
2. Lack of Self Confidence
3. Irrational Fears and Anxiety
4. Depression
5. Suicidal Thoughts
6. Disrupted Schooling
7. Distrusting Adults
8. Emotional Turmoil
9. Anti-Social Behaviours
10. Losing faith in Relationships
11. Nightmares

It is clear that most of them promote counselling as a therapy not only to the children who are affected by it, but also the parents, the couples who are going through a tough time adjusting among each other. Effective communication can be seen as a way to solve most problems.

There are clearly negative long-term consequences of divorce—children, parents, and society all suffer. Wallerstein's long-term study shows that many children never have full “recovery” as each special event, holiday, or celebration reminds the child of his/her loss. Given these tremendous costs borne by all individuals affected by divorce, as well as the costs to society, it is the responsibility of physicians—especially paediatricians and counsellors, who care for children in the context of their families—to advocate for public health policies that promote marriage and decrease the likelihood of divorce.

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Paper 14

A STUDY ON INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY AND ITS IMPACT ON FAMILY MEMEBERS IN PERLA, KASARGOD

Renin Sebastian* Monteiro Meena **, D'Mello Laveena ***

* II MSW, School of Social Work, Roshni Nilaya, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

** Associate Professor, Social Work Department, School of Social Work, Roshni Nilaya, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail : monteiromeena@yahoo.com

***Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

This study deal with intellectual disability and its impact on family members in Perla, Kasargod D.T, Kerala. Intellectual disability means different things to different people. It is not a simple phenomenon and the lives of individuals who are retarded can be complicated. An intellectually challenged person is whose mental age develops at a slower rate than normal children and does not achieve full intellectual functions of a normal adult. Intellectual disability generally refers to substantial growth and is manifested in inappropriate or immature reactions to one's environment and below average performance in the academic, psychological, physical and social domains. Accepting such children becomes very difficult to parents, family members and care takers. The objectives of the research are: To identify the effect of intellectual disability on the family; And to find out how psychological, physical, economic and social problems affect the family members of mentally disabled children. The study design used is essentially qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative descriptions are based on some quality or characteristic rather than on some quantity or measured value. Descriptive research design is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that is being studied. This methodology focuses more on the of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject. This study reveals that family members face physical, psychological, economic and social problems.

Keywords: Intellectual disability, Intellectual quotient (IQ), Social, Economic, Psychological, and physiological problems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intellectual disability is one of the mental disabilities caused by mental limited capacity of the person. The abilities like reasoning thinking, planning and adjustment. The limited capacity of the mind makes it difficult to know new things or changes in life. The knowledge, skills and information we receive in life with experience and improving our mistakes. We learn new things from observing and watching others. When people lack the ability to learn from various sources, it will effect on his life and creates problems for leading a happy life. There

are multiple reasons for the intellectual disabilities. Like genetic reasons, brain injuries during birth or after the birth, accidents, medical affect, brain development,

2. CLASSIFICATION OF INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY

The classification given by the American Association of Mental deficiency (1977) is mostly adopted as characterized by subaverage intellectual functioning and impaired adaptive behaviour. The test which was developed by Binet and Simon is used for identification of children with intellectual disability (Termar& Merrill, 1973) which is as follows;

Borderline Intelligence (IQ 83-68): An IQ score that falls in the range from 68-70 to 82-83 suggests that an individual of borderline intelligence. These people are not considered as mentally retarded as they do not have impairments in their independent living skills. They are identified by the teachers or educators and slow learners.

Mild Intellectual disability (IQ 67-52): Mild mentally retarded people are indistinguishable from the general population, but they are unable to profit to any great degree from the programme of the regular schools. They are also called as educable mentally retarded having the following potentials of development.

Moderate Intellectual disability (IQ 51-36): The moderately mentally retarded individual is unable to profit from the normal school programme. They are also known as 'Trainable mentally retarded'.

Severe Intellectual disability (IQ 35-20):The severely mentally retarded people may have associate handicaps such as motor problems or significant speech and language deficits. Special school programmes will emphasis basic developmental skills, communication and adaptive behaviour. People who have severe intellectual disability can work in supervised settings.

Profound Intellectual disability (IQ< 20): Individuals under this category require custodial care at the upper limit of this range and life sustaining maintenance at the lower levels. They need care and help at all levels.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jani (1967) indicated that parental feelings were marked by anxiety about future. Also, negative effects towards other siblings, psychological stress, decreased interaction with neighbours and relatives, misunderstandings within family and economic loss were significant factors associated with presence of a child with intellectual disability in the family. Sambhu Upadhyay and Anju Singh (2009) conducted a study to find the impact of level of intellectual disability of children on the perception of psychosocial problems and needs by parents of intellectual disability children in providing care to them. The study was conducted on a purposive sample of 100 parents of intellectually disabled children. Parents of moderately retarded children registered more problems in all aspects compared with parents having mildly retarded children. The needs expressed by the parents of mildly retarded child were more of preventive and adjustment nature whereas parents of moderately retarded children were more concerned with lifelong adjustment and financial security including government help of their child.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Objectives provide direction to the study. On the basis of objectives investigator chooses the areas of data collection, respondents and systematic analysis. The objectives of the research study are; to identify the effect of intellectual disability on the family; to find out how psychological, physical, economic and social problems affect the family members of mentally disabled children.

5. METHODOLOGY

The study design used is essentially qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative descriptions are based on some quality or characteristic rather than on some quantity or measured value. Descriptive research design is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that is being studied. This methodology focuses more on the of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject. The research aims at describing the psycho-social, physical and economic problems of family members of intellectually disabled children. SPSS is used for data analysis and interpretation.

6. MAJOR FINDINGS

This study reveals that the family members of intellectually disabled children have psycho-social, physical and economic problems.

Psychological Problems

Psychological problems	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Blame	49 (98%)	0	1(2%)	0
Upset	41 (82%)	1 (2%)	8 (16%)	0
Limit growth	10(20%)	17 (34%)	23 (46%)	0
Emotional conflicts	38 (78%)	2 (4%)	9 (18%)	0

The above table shows the psychological problems of the respondents. Blame: 98 percent said that they don't blame anybody and 2 percent said that sometimes they blame others for the intellectual disability of child. Upset: 82 percent said that they are not at all upset 16 percent are sometimes upset about it and 2 percent are upset about intellectual disability of the child. Limit growth: 46 percent expressed that intellectual disability of the child sometimes limit the growth of the respondents. 34 percent said that it always limits the growth and 20 percent said not at all limit the growth. Emotional Conflict: 78 percent told

that there is no emotional conflict, 18 percent expressed sometimes there is emotional conflict and 4 percent said there is emotional conflict. From this table it is clear that the majority of the respondents do have psychological problems due to the intellectual disability of the child

Physical Problems

Physical problem	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Physical burden	21 (42%)	8 (16%)	21 (42%)	0
Need help	17 (34%)	19 (38%)	12 (24%)	2 (4%)
Physical strain	17 (34%)	9 (18%)	23 (46%)	1 (2%)

The table depicts the physical strain. Physical burden, need for help and physical strain. *Physical burden:* 42 percent said they have physical burden always and sometimes respectively and 8 percent said that they have physical problem. *Need some help:* 38 percent of respondent said that they need some help to take care the child, 34 percent said no need help 24 said occasionally they need help and 4 percent often they need help. *Physical strain:* 46 percent of respondents expressed that they have sometimes physical strain, 34 percent said they have no physical problems, 18 percent said that often they have physical strain. From the above explanation it is clear that majority of the respondents have physical problems because they need to help children physically such as carry the child and assisting them for their personal needs.

Social Problems

Social problem	Shame	Inferiority	Anger	No feeling
Going for social gathering with the child	0	0	1 (2%)	49 (98%)
Reaction to the comment	25 (50%)	10 (20%)	3 (6%)	12 (24%)
Feeling before friends	1 (2%)	13 (26%)	NO	31 (72%)
Feeling inferiority	1 (2%)	36 (72%)	13 (26%)	0
Child is problem to the family	30 (60%)	1 (2%)	19 (38%)	0
Social Stress	15 (30%)	11 (22%)	24 (48%)	0

The above table explains about different social problems, that the respondents have and they are following. *Going for social gathering with the child:* 98 percent said that they have no feeling and 2 percent said they have anger when people ask about the child. *Reaction to the comment:* 50 percent said that they have shame, 24 percent said they have no feeling at all.

20 percent they have inferiority complex and 6 percent have anger. *Feeling before friends:* 72 percent have no feelings to take the child anywhere as they go for gatherings, 26 percent have inferiority feelings and 2 percent have shame. From above table it is clear that all the respondents face certain degree of social problems. *Feeling inferiority:* 76 percent respondents said that they have inferiority feeling, 26 percent said sometimes and 2 percent said they have no inferiority at all. *Child is problem to the family:* The majority 60 percent said no child is not a problem to the family, 38 percent said child is sometimes problem to the family and 2 percent said child is problem to the family. *Social stress:* The majority 48 percent of the respondents said that they have sometimes social stress, 30 percent have not at all and 22 percent said they have social stress.

Economic Problems

Economic problem	No	Yes	Sometimes	Often
Spend money for education and training	30 (60%)	2 (4%)	18 (36%)	0
Financial burden on treatment	7 (14%)	14 (28%)	29 (58%)	0
Financial burden on the maintenance of the family	12 (24%)	14 (28%)	23 (46%)	1 (2%)

The above table shows the economic problems of the respondents. Following are the main economic problems. *Spending money for the education and training:* 60 percent said they do not spend money for the training and education, 36 percent said they spend sometimes and 4 percent said they spend money for training and education of the children. *Financial burden on the treatment:* 58 percent have expressed that they face economic burden sometimes for the treatment, 28 percent said they have always financial problem and 14 percent said that they don't have economic problem for the treatment of the child. *Economic burden on the maintenance of the family:* 46 percent of respondents viewed that they have sometimes burden on the maintenance of the family, 28 percent totally agreed that they have burden on and 24 percent said they have no burden and 2 percent said that they have often burden on the maintenance of the family. It is clear that majority of the respondents have economic problem due to the child's intellectual disability. They cannot go for the work someone need to take care the child and there are expenses like treatment, education and training of the child. From the above analysis we can conclude that the family members of the intellectually disabled children face physical, psychological, economic and social problems.

7. SUGGESTION

- Respondents have social stigma and social isolation attached to intellectual disability, and it is mainly due to minimum education. Therefore, it is necessary to provide psycho-social education to the families of intellectually disabled children.
- Government can provide education and trainings to the intellectually disabled children, thus can establish special school in that area.

- Government can appoint social workers in the panchayath level to supervise and provide different supports to the families of intellectually disabled children and especially psycho-social support.

8. CONCLUSION

Here the investigator sums up the study on intellectual disability and its impact on family. And this study was conducted in Perla, Kasargod district in Kerala state. Intellectual disability has lot of impact on family members specially those who take care of the intellectually disabled children. The major concern of the investigator is to study intellectual disability and its impact on family members and how this impact can affect family at large. This study leaves behind scope to further study on problems of disabled children and how those children are affected by the problems of family members. Disability has affected family members personal life and professional life. Other important areas of focus are on different services and help that can be provided for the wellbeing of disabled children as well as their family at large.

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ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH: A MODEL FOR CLASSROOM TEACHING

Gururaj Ganapati Gouda 1*, Laveena D'Mello 2**

1*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Email: gururajitgi@gmail.com

2**Assistant Professor, Social Work Department, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: [lavynoronha@gmail.com](mailto:lavyronha@gmail.com)

Abstract

Our senses are natural gifts which transfer information to the thinking brain to understand what is being presented to us in the form of sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste. These senses determine to some extent how we understand the concept being presented and recall instructional contents or information. To this effect, teachers at all levels of educational sector keep these in mind and endeavour to apply the Multi-Sensory Approach in presenting their instructional contents in a classroom situation to take care of the uniqueness of the individual learners and bring the best academic excellence. A Multi-sensory approach is an effective model named "Itagi's Model of Multi-Sensory Approach" developed by Gururaj Itagi. Highlighting various methods, strategies and techniques in teaching process focussing on individual learning style to maximize student's academic excellence. This model is framed based on the different learning style of students. This framework considers integrated phases of teaching such as auditory, visual and kinaesthetic approach. The model focuses on Adolescence (aged 12-18 years) mainly on students with scholastic backwardness.

Keywords: Academic Excellence, Multi-Sensory Approach, Classroom Teaching, Students & Teachers.

1. INTRODUCTION:

A classroom is a place in an educational institution where teaching and learning carried out. Teachers and students engage themselves in the school for academic interaction. The classroom must be equipped with necessary materials which could support quality teaching and best learning. The new Education Policy-2019 which is prepared by Dr. Kasthuri Rangan committee and asked for public opinion recognises, from information received by teachers, students, educational scientists, and educators of different sectors, that the present curriculum content is currently overloaded [1]. Finally, students are most of the time removed from the social support of teachers and are expected to compete rather than cooperate with each other in reading [2]. The modern meaning of "learning style" indicates a much broader look at how a student responds to the learning situations and how a student functions as a learner [3] [4]. School fear (School Phobia) among children is affecting the academic performance of the children and their day today's activities. This is also one of the major reason for children's school dropout. It is highly recommended to expertize the teachers to have an insight into

phobic disorders and their impacts on children [5]. The children with several behavioural problems in the school are not given importance to understand the real cause behind their problems [6].

Need of Student Centred Classroom Teaching for Academic Excellence: Different Committees set up by MHRD proposed “Learning Without Burden” and highlighted the severe need for reducing and revising our overcrowded curriculum content load in favour of a more engaging, holistic, experiential, and analysis-based form of learning [1]. Academic excellence refers to the increased level of learning interest, active participation in teaching and learning process, experiential learning based on individual learning style and Maximized performance in learning and examination [6].

2. OBJECTIVES:

The below objectives are set up with the aim of identifying strengths and weakness of present teaching methodology and explore the effective teaching approach which is mainly focused on the different learning styles of learning individuals in the classroom. The objectives of this study is to understand the different goals of Multi-Sensory Approach Model, to explore the experiential learning through Multi-Sensory Approach Model, to develop the student centred classroom teaching through Multi-Sensory Approach model, and to understand the different benefits from the use of Multi-Sensory Approach model.

3. GOALS OF MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

This particular study also focussing on the classroom approach aiming to teach the individual’s learning needs based on their learning style such as auditory, visual and kinaesthetic learning [7]. The major goals of Multi-sensory approach are as follows.

Visual Learners: Visual means sight. Every human being is unique in learning, some learners are more active and enjoy learning using their eyes and remember information. Visualized teaching in the classroom was found to significantly increase student learning. The Multi-Sensory Approach is aiming to include teaching strategies which suites to the visual learners and prefers visualization of the subject in classroom teaching [8].

Auditory Learners: Auditory learning refers to learning through sound. Individuals under this category are those who use their ears more to learn and remember information presented to them. They are more sensitised through sound and they enjoy listening. The approach describes a possible way of effective teaching in the classroom considering auditory learners to maximize their academic performance as well as their learning interest [9].

Kinaesthetic Learners: In the teaching and learning situation, some of the learners learn and recall information more effectively using their feelings and involving in the learning activities. These types of learners are physically-oriented individuals. So the aim of the multi-sensory approach is to fulfil the gap in encouraging the students with kinaesthetic learning style in teaching-learning process at the classroom and enhance their understanding ability to maximize their academic performance [10].

So considering learner’s learning capacity the Multi-Sensory Approach brings a new strategic model which helps the teachers to reach every individual in the classroom with different learning style and maximize their active participation in teaching and learning process, increase their academic performance [10].

4. EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Experiential learning exists when a personally responsible participant cognitively, effectively, and behaviourally processes knowledge, skills, and attitudes in a learning situation characterized by a high level of active involvement (Hoover and Whitehead 1975).

Child-centered ideas in the classroom have to be planned in teacher-training programs and school with the intention of creating more child-friendly, democratic learning environments and teaching based on student's learning demands focusing on their learning style may enhance better academic output [11].

Figure-1: Human learn through sensory organs

Information obtained through senses such as hearing, seeing, touching, tasting, and smelling all contribute to the way in which people experience their external world. When an individual witness a situation he receive information through his multi-sensory organs. When an Individual see something happening, hear the sound produced and physically involve in the same situation will have a better understanding of what he saw, heard and involved. The message received on any one situation, through multi-sensory organs will enhance the long term memory. It has a quality of personal involvement and being present in the learning event [12] [13].

Multi-Sensory Approach model outlines the manner in which learners gain knowledge and understanding through experiences [14]. Students should have frequent and multiple opportunities to read, write, listen, see, speak and involve in the teaching and learning process. Lesson activities can be modified more appropriately to meet the student's learning needs and abilities. A multi-sensory approach is not only offering participants to have structured experiences but also a reflection upon these experiences in order to learn from them, to link them to their own lives and to experiment with this new knowledge in the following activities and in their daily life which also contains long term memory [15]. Due to inappropriate teaching approach of the teachers in the classroom, many students just don't value their education. The Multi-Sensory Approach in classroom teaching focuses on the learning demands of the students and encourages the students to have experiential learning in the classroom [16].

5. DEVELOPING A STUDENT- CENTRED CLASSROOM TEACHING THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Most teachers and students at all levels of education have gone without fully understanding and using their potentials and unique nature as intelligent and creative individuals. Most people have not realised these unique qualities of the individual which made us use a single method of teaching and learning, considering human beings are the same and ignoring the unique nature of man. This might be a reason why most of our academic strategies are ineffective. A combined method that will sensitise most of the sense organs in individual learner becomes an ideal strategy to achieve effective teaching and learning in the classroom [17].

Classroom teaching based on student’s learning style thrives on several benefits. First, the teacher does not hold all of the power to control were students feel helpless. Instead, students share responsibilities and understand their capabilities as learners. Second, students are motivated to think critically and question the presented material. Third, teachers are also learners and they seek to be taught as much as possible, themselves, may teach. Fourth, students have insight and control of their learning. Which even helps the teachers to get reduced burden of working with scholastic backward students. Teaching and learning effort to be conducted in a more interactive manner, questions will be encouraged, and classroom teaching will contain more creative, collaborative, and exploratory activities for students for deeper and more experiential learning [18] [19].

Figure-2: Multi-Sensory Approach Model

Approach for Auditory Learners: Auditory learner depends on remembering information taught through sounds. Who is doing the speaking is not a matter for the auditory learner, it may be a recording, and Teacher's talk or even himself reading. Auditory learners naturally focus on sound patterns, they benefit more when classroom teaching happens by using sound patterns rather than the written patterns. Because these type of learners depend more on their auditory memory. It is a responsibility of teachers that they adopt an effective teaching method as explained below [20].

- (a) **Talk:** the teacher in the classroom teaching should be well trained in effective communication and be capable to pronounce the words fluently and melodiously. So that the students who are auditory learners enjoy their teaching and have a better understanding of the concept taught in the classroom.
- (b) **Audio Aids:** In the process of teaching teachers can also use different audio gadgets such as speakers, audio player, and mike etc. teachers can record teaching and help the students who would like to listen to it whenever they want. Teachers also can play melodious background music which when they have a session in the classroom.
- (c) **Musical Instruments:** Using different musical instruments to play the music in the classroom will influence the auditory learners towards paying attention and active involvement in the teaching and learning process.
- (d) **Question and Answer Method:** Students must be encouraged and given the opportunity to ask the questions and give answers. If the teachers make their session as most interactive one students will defiantly have to enjoy learning and improve their academic performance.
- (e) **Group Discussion:** Even auditory learners enjoy having more discussion in the learning and teaching process. Teachers must encourage the students to have interaction between teachers and students and students and students. Teachers also can divide students into multiple groups and encourage them for group discussion.

Approach for Kinaesthetic Learners: The kinaesthetic learners engage themselves in debating, discussion, role-playing, demonstration, and many other learning activities for the concepts they are learning in the classroom to understand and retain as long term memory. Careful planning by the teacher in classroom teaching with kinaesthetic learners will enhance student's capacity in learning and maximize their academic performance because kinaesthetic learners acquire information by sharing and cooperating with teacher and peers [21] [3].

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- (a) **Read and Write Practice:** Teachers can encourage students with a kinaesthetic learning style to have repetitive reading and writing practice. So that students will get engaged both physically and mentally in the teaching and learning process.
 - (b) **Activities:** Different activities planned by the teachers in classroom teaching also will encourage the students to get physically involved in the learning process. Roleplay, Drama, Indoor and Outdoor activities, research projects, experiments etc are the best methods to influence the students with kinaesthetic learning style towards better learning.
 - (c) **Practical:** Use of laboratories, indoor and outdoor experiments, demonstration related to the lesson will help the kinaesthetic learners to enjoy learning and have increased understanding.
 - (d) **Group Discussion:** Students with a kinaesthetic learning style must be encouraged for the group discussion so that they actively involved in clarifying doubts and sharing information.

Approach for Visual Learners: Visual learners enjoy receiving information through their eyes. Visualization of lessons in classroom teaching will enhance visual learner's active participation in the teaching and learning process. Displaying videos, writing on white or blackboard, effective use of the digital board, teacher's body language etc are the effective methods through which visual learners enjoy learning and increase their academic performance [22].

- (a) **Body Language:** Body language is one of the effective methods for effective communication. Visual learners understand better when teachers use body language along with classroom teaching. Facial expressions, body movements and actions will effectively pass the messages to the learners. But most of the teachers in Indian schools even don't move from one place when they are in classroom teaching.
- (b) **Demonstration:** Teachers can convert any lessons into the demonstration. Using a few students or he or she can put themselves to present the demonstration on any decided concept. More than orally explaining the lessons converting them in a visualized method of demonstration is better for visual learners to have an effective understanding and maximized academic performance.
- (c) **Video Aids:** Different technologies such as Digital boards, TV, Video projectors etc can be used effectively in classroom teaching so that the visual learners can experience and have improved understanding of the lessons taught in the class. Teachers can plan their subject teaching as a visualized method of teaching using power point presentation, Sowing related videos, short films, animated videos which even influence more for the visual learners for better learning.
- (d) **Material Display:** In the process of teaching, the teacher can display any materials or things related to the lesson. For example, a teacher would like to teach about triangles or any others shapes so she can use a triangle made in wood or any other materials to the students so that the visual learners have visualized learning about the triangle.
- (e) **Use of White and Black Board:** Every classroom has a chalkboard that may be blackboard or whiteboard, these boards must be used effectively. Teachers must use the boards for writing the concept planned to teach. Drawing, writing title, an important point, mind map, calculation, tables, map or any other diagrams are the effective methods presenting on board to teach visual learners effectively.

6. BENEFITS OF MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Poor teaching in the classroom has a more direct impact on the reading performance of children [23]. Multi-Sensory Approach has the capacity to help the student with different learning style to have an efficient and effective understanding and realisation of the importance of teaching-learning objectives. Therefore, the individual's brain has evolved to develop, learn and operate optimally in multisensory environments [24]. Organizing teaching-learning activities in the classroom that helps the teaching in making the total unit of learners quite clear to their learning ability. It will also help students in acquiring all the learning experiences widely through effective involvement and cooperative learning [18].

Students gather sensory stimuli for three modalities such as vision, touch and audition that seem to fit best with the desired learning. This helps the learners to develop ideas about the different ways in which an experience can be acquired on the subject taught in the classroom [12]. The Multi-Sensory Approach Model makes its primary focus on engaging students in a process that best enhances their learning capacity. Learning will be conceived as a continuing reconstruction of learning experience [25]. We are living in a multi-sensory environment. The brain also involved to learn and operate in classroom environments in which an integrated model of Multi-Sensory Approach is been carried out. However, Multi-Sensory-Approach strategies can better approximate natural settings of teaching and are more effective for learning [26].

Figure-3: Memory Benefits from the Multi-Sensory Approach [27].

Students learn more when the content of teaching is presented in their best modality seems to be supported by classroom experiences, and offers the hope of maximizing each child's learning by planning different lessons and generalizing them for each type of learner. It also increases student's understanding of necessary skills, a variety of media and methods are incorporated while presenting the lesson in the classroom teaching [10]. The utilization of the Senses of Sight, Speech, hearing and touch of the individual in order to learn will enhance their learning ability and maximises there learning interest. This model is also helpful for children, as well as those with learning disabilities, children learn more effectively using their multi senses [1]. When students were taught with Multi-Sensory Approach resources, (although initially through their most preferred learning modality), increased performance in academic as well as active participation in the learning process can be seen. This is a powerful tool for reinforcing our classroom teaching in three important ways. First, it helps get the information across through multi senses. Second, it helps the students to process the

information received. And, third, it helps students more freely reclaim information already learned from teachers. Using a variety of senses simply opens up more doorways into the brain [28] [3]. There are no spirits than the motivation to influence an individual towards achieving their learning goals. The greatest achievers always lay down behind the inspiration of one or another person's, situations or by the stories of success. Motivation is an important aspect behind life leaving of each mankind. The presented model plays a major role in the creation of great hope and motivation among students in classroom learning [29] [30].

8. CONCLUSION:

Our senses are natural gifts which transfer information to the thinking brain to understand what is being presented to us in the form of sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste. These senses determine to some extent how we understand the concept being presented and recall instructional contents or information. To this effect, teachers at all levels of educational sector keep these in mind and endeavour to apply the Multi-Sensory Approach in presenting their instructional contents in a classroom situation to take care of the uniqueness of the individual learners and bring the best academic excellence [31]. This model must be adopted as a value addition to the formal education system of the country to build effective teaching and experiential learning in the classroom for maximizing the academic excellence of the students.

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Paper 16

STUDENT ENRICHMENT INITIATIVES FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

Harinakshi¹, Pradeep M. D.² & Mithun Chandra R. K.³

¹Faculty, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

³Faculty, Department of Business Management, University Evening College, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India Email: mithoonchandra008@gmail.com

Abstract

Education plays a great role in our life. It is an important medium of acquiring knowledge. Today knowledge is power and society accept that people with more knowledge is more empowered. India was known in the world for its few oldest Universities including Thakshashila University, Nalanda University and Ujjaini University etc. India is considered to be the hub of higher education after US and China. Higher education is a level of education obtained by students after completing secondary education. Since the globalization, industrialization and advancement of Information Technology, the Higher Education System of many countries experienced several changes during the last few decades. Preparing students to face competitive world has become a challenge to the teachers. Along with the knowledge gained from books, teachers need to train students with live examples. Various strategies such as presentation, group discussion, industrial visit, etc. are added to the curriculum. Students are allowed to have contact with the external world. The traditional teaching method of chalk and talk is replaced by other methods to learn and experience the outer world to enrich their knowledge. Bringing changes based on the present requirement is the need of the time.

Keywords: University, Higher Education, Changes, Knowledge, Teaching Methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teacher in higher education helps to develop student's way of thinking, behaviour and approach towards their field of study and practice. Student's performance gets affect by various factors including pedagogy used for teaching, student's self-discipline, teaching environment, resources available, etc. This study aims to study methods adopted by the teachers of higher education in order to suggest strategies to improve the overall performance of the students. The innovative pedagogies will certainly improve the quality of educational system of the country. This study is done through conducting extensive literature review upon various journals, texts, articles, websites, blogs etc.

2. PEDAGOGIES USED IN HIGHER EDUCATION

(a) Pedagogies for Effective Teaching: Lecture is the primary method of teaching which could even be supported with interactive sessions by conducting group discussion. The

lecture cum demonstration method can be performed through role play, brain storming, case studies, case presentation, games, field application etc. Student Centric Teaching Method has shifted the focus from teacher to students in the education system. By giving autonomy to students, the traditional method of teacher centric teaching practice was eliminated[1]. The learner centric classrooms operates by providing Smart Classrooms, projector based teaching, audio visual aids etc [2]. Guest Lecture delivered by eminent academic and industrial experts provides opportunity for the students to interact with such experts to provide insights to understand leadership roles, team work, interpersonal skills and right attitude to chase success. Soft Skill Training will provide competitive edge to distinguish them from other candidates with similar qualification. Remedial classes are conducted to revise the curriculum at the end of semesters will help the slow learners in the class to perform better in the semester examination. Special classes can be conducted for the slow learners to bring them to the mainstream by improving their learning speed. One to One teaching pedagogy allows communication and feedback based on the learners needs with undivided attention.

(b) Pedagogies for Effective Learning: The differing learning abilities of students are taken into consideration during the teaching learning processes [3]. Learner Centric Approach along with Information Communication Technology enabled methodologies are adopted to equip learners to compete with the tech-savvy environment [4]. This up gradation has increased the speed of learning. Technology has improved the speed of learning process through the internet [5]. Technology based learning stimulates younger generation to learn skills in the light of global competition existing in the employment market. Participatory approach encourages active student participation in the learning process [6]. Participant will become active learner rather than a passive receiver of information. These approaches provide deeper knowledge and enhance their learning skills. Students are encouraged to participate in the tasks of speaking, listening, writing, argument, performing, countering with other students [7]. Experimental learning with “do it and learn policy” provides learning through first-hand experience. It includes the provision for fellowships to provide financial aids to support their life during the period of study. Field work permits the students to practically apply the theoretical knowledge in the field of study. Internship exposes the students into the work culture, employee relations, leadership traits, organisational profile etc. Attending workshops provides specific knowledge on a particular theme. Group Discussion encourages active participation [8] through exchanging ideas. It improves student presentation and listening aptitudes [9]. Class room presentation enrich confidence and communication.

(c) Supplementary Enrichment Programmes: Higher education Institutions are offering ‘Earn while Learn’ Programmes to support financial backward students with part time employment and saving to enriching their personal expertise for final placement. The technology based Massive Open Online Courses provided through EPG Patshala, NPTEL, SWAYAM, Edx etc. provides ample opportunity to explore blended learning with diversified courses. Industry visit will deliver understanding on the practical working environment among the student community. Project Works are assigned in the last semester trains students to identify the problem exist in the real world and find the solution for the same. Case Studies performed under the guidance of faculties will build analytical and conceptual skills among students. Extra Curricular Activities helps to develop physical, intellectual and social habits among the students. It includes participation in sports, cultural, games, art, social services activities. Classes on Yoga will them in knowing and regulating self by balancing body and mind by improving concentration thereby boosting their performance. Motivation Sessions on setting goal, self esteem, grooming and personality development will create greater

impact. Providing printed study materials will help in boosting performance of students in the examinations. Customised assignments with specified marks for internal assessment will give internal urge in searching more relevant information and present with content. College fest permits the student to showcase Team work, Management, Leadership and interactive abilities. The institutions are providing placement assistance, certificate courses, mock interviews, campus drives etc. Constitution of incubation Centres in the Campus will encourage students and staffs to take up minor and major research projects benefitting the Society.

(d) Pedagogies for Evaluation System: Learning environment provides relevant content, clear learning goals and feedback, opportunities to build social skills and strategies to help students succeed [10]. Student counselling and Mentoring Services provides opportunity for the students to share their problems to seek guidance to overcome it. Receiving feedbacks from all stakeholders enable the higher education institutions to study their strength and weaknesses to further improve the system [11]. The family members of the students should actively engage in the orientation, evaluation and grievance handling tasks of their ward by meeting the faculties occasionally. National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) insisted on framing Internal Quality Assurance Cell to maintain quality and standard in education. The grievance related to employer, employee and students shall be redressed through formal mechanisms.

(e) Administrative Pedagogies: Government initiatives on new educational policies, employment guarantee programmes, skill development projects, scholarships, fellowships, research, vocational courses plays a vital role in improving the education system. Development of Educational infrastructure including classrooms, laboratories, play ground, sports and games equipment, sanitation are crucial elements to improve student admission ratio. The New Education Policy, regulatory mechanisms of University Grants Commission (UGC), All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE), Professional Councils, National Board of Accreditation (NBA), National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) will influence the quality of higher education [12]. Financial grants by the government and University Grants Commission will improve the quality of education. The Management of Higher Education should always develop and preserve their Intellectual Property through publication of books, journals, magazines, patents, trademarks etc.

3. CONCLUSION

The education sector significantly affects the economic, social, political system of the country. Higher education is the crucial player in building India to be a super power in the World. Higher education essentially imparts knowledge, values and skills facilitating growth and productivity in the nation. Modern world caused higher education system into varied challenges. Teaching, Learning, Evaluation and administrative initiatives will build quality in education. Any innovative strategy adopted by the higher education institutions shall add value to the educational system by providing avenues for further exploration for good.

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Paper 17

NATIONAL ACADEMIC CREDIT BANK – A GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

Keerthan Raj & Dr. P.S.Aithal

College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575
001

2keerthanraj@gmail.com

Abstract

The higher education in India is poised on an agenda of change towards the movement from Credit Based Choice System (CBCS) to National Academic Credit Bank (NACB) as proposed by the UGC. If the Union government is able to formulate a policy, this will mark the beginning of a new phase in the Indian Higher Education System. This would allow the students to pursue their higher education from different universities and earn a degree from another university. Credit transfers are prevalent in many countries and its success is ensured by the creation of an online repository of students looking for potential credit transfer opportunities. Though it requires a vast amount of ground work and pathways created, once implemented, the NAC Bank would help students plan their objectives and their pace. This paper we study the modus operandi as the scheme and its existence in different countries and its implications on the student fraternity.

Keywords: Academic, credit, transfers, online

1. Introduction

Technological advances in fields of communication and transportation have increased educational opportunities for post-secondary education students across the globe. Individuals as well as information now travels quicker and cheaper between countries and continents. The institutions offering post-secondary education no longer have a local, jurisdictional or even domestic focus; their vision is global. In spite of India developing a lot of higher educational institutions we are not on a global list of students aspiring to come to study in India and academic credit transfers could also be one of the lacuna that is seen. In addition the advantages add to, governments and employers recognizing that the workforce of the future must well-trained, globally aware professionals with international work experience who can solve economic and social problems. At the same time, students and faculty are becoming increasingly interested in spending time in different academic environments, often in foreign surroundings. The length of stay amongst these programs can range from one semester to the pursuit of a full academic credential. If there is a mechanism or a proper procedure that is designed to recognize previous academic performance, this would ensure that a full range of student mobility is created. It is for this reason that credit transfer and student mobility are linked. Credit transfer systems provide the lubricant to ensure seamless academic mobility.

Understanding the academic credit system?

An academic credit system is a standard used by universities to measure and assess students' work and effort during their programme. It's important to understand how credits work and how credit points from one academic system are converted to credits from other credit systems, if possible. Sometimes students need to take preparation courses in order to meet starting credit requirements needed for university admission. Academic credit transfer systems offer the following advantages to the institutions and nations offering the same -

- Facilitate inter institutional cooperation - there is greater inter institutional cooperation amongst the various universities/institutions at conjoint with each other.
- Student mobility - It facilitates greater student mobility between nations which also paves the way for fostering economic growth.
- Enhance quality of higher education
- Increase global competitiveness – The curriculums will be designed at global standards, increasing the standards of education
- Establish a standard for quality assurance and accreditation - It sets standards for quality assurance amongst institutions.

2. International Credit Systems – Some of the most relevant academic credits for international students are:

a. **ECTS - European credits** -The European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) is a tool of the European Higher Education System for making studies and courses more transparent. It helps students to move between countries and to have their academic qualifications and study periods abroad recognised. ECTS allows credits taken at one higher education institution to be counted towards a qualification studied for at another. ECTS credits represent learning based on defined learning outcomes and their associated workload. ECTS enhances the flexibility of study programmes for students. It also supports the planning, delivery and evaluation of higher education programmes. European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits are a standard means for comparing the "volume of learning based on the defined learning outcomes and their associated workload" for higher education across the European union and other collaborating European countries. For successfully completed studies, ECTS credits are awarded. One academic year corresponds to 60 ECTS credits that are normally equivalent to 1500–1800 hours of total workload, irrespective of standard or qualification type. ECTS credits are used to facilitate transfer and progression throughout the Union. ECTS also includes a standard grading scale intended to be shown in addition to local.

For each course a person takes during the degree studies, they will earn a number of credits. Assessment are done in terms of the amount of knowledge and skills that is achieved once the course is completed. Common forms of assessment are a combination of:

- actual attendance

- tests taken during the course
- projects/research work
- oral/written examination

Mainly, each course is worth a certain number of credit points, determined by different criteria including student's workload, learning outcome and contact hours. Usually, the more work and effort a student is required to put into a course, the more credits that course is worth.

b. Academic credit systems in Australia

Australian universities do not have a unified credit system. Each university in Australia calculates the credits according to workload and number of study hours per each course.

Credit transfer is available for both undergraduate and postgraduate study programmes and it is established and coordinated by the Australian Qualifications Framework.

Universities in Australia (as well as individual faculties or departments in a university) have different rules regarding independent study and transfer credit.

In Australian universities, each subject usually has a value between 6 and 8, but there may be some exceptions and find credit points below or over this average. Normally, during a semester, you would study 4 subjects. Each university may decide how many subjects students are allowed to choose for each semester.

According to the academic credit system in Australia, Bachelor degrees require completion of 144 credit points (for 3 years Bachelor degrees) and for completing a postgraduate degree, you would need 96 credits. Credit assessment may take up to three months and costs vary depending on the number of qualifications assessed. Students may apply for assessment online. A number of credits are awarded as a result of the assessment process. Universities decide if the student meets their academic requirements after evaluating the results of the assessment.

c. Academic credit systems in the U.S.

In the U.S., students receive semester credit hours, which are based on the number of contact hours accumulated during one semester. Mainly, a student would have to take around 5 courses each semester, where each course is worth 3 semester credit hours, the equivalent of 45-48 contact hours. All these would add up to 30 credits per year, the required number to successfully complete a degree in the U.S.

d. Korea's Academic Credit Bank System

This has been the most widely appreciated and well regarded academic credit transfer system in the world, the Academic Credit Bank system (ACBS) is an open educational system which recognizes diverse learning experiences gained not only in-school but also out-of school. When the learner accumulates the necessary ACBS-approved credits, he/she can be awarded a degree. The Academic Credit Bank System, a central agency for continuing education, aims to provide all citizens with greater access to a variety of educational opportunities and to foster a lifelong learning society. This program aims at

innovating, diversifying and maximizing the educational opportunities for both students, studying at post-secondary institutes, and adults, seeking additional education and training. This is a unique system where credits are given for job periods as well, hence benefitting adults as well.

The ACBS is intended to benefit the following groups:

- Students and adults who could not continue their education.
- High school graduates who were previously unable to attend post-secondary institutes.
- Workers who hold professional certificates but did not acquire a university degree.
- College or university graduates who wish to commence studies in a different field.
- People who wish to acquire formal credits for knowledge and skills gained through self-instruction and workplace training and experience.
- People who have studied at private institutes or junior colleges and wish to transfer into the university system.

Credits are acquired primarily through education and job training institutes, part-time enrollment, certificate acquisition, and passing the Bachelor's Degree Examination program for self-education. The ACBS also grants recognition to a learner's diverse learning experiences, including prior course credits and various forms of learning.

Educational institutes are formally evaluated to be an ACBS-accredited institute offering courses which can be counted as university or college equivalent credits.

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MEST), the National Institute for Lifelong Education (NILE), and Provincial Offices of Education are involved in the administration of the Credit Bank. The Korean academic credit model is very well studied and the model has been adopted by several countries.

3. The major benefits of the academic credit transfer systems are analysed and put forth herewith-

- Credits support your entry to a higher education programme
- They keep track of student progress and determine when he/she has met study requirements
- They estimate the workload of a programme
- You can transfer to another university programme while keeping part or all previously earned credit points
- Use the credit you earned to study abroad – academic credit is used and recognised internationally
- Academic credits act as proof of previous studies when looking for a job
- Some universities use academic study credits to set degree costs

The advantages of the academic credit system are various in terms of giving better opportunities to students to garner the requisite skills to pursue further studies and combine the pursuit of education with academic goals. Even institutions benefit by developing a very good academic standards and having best in class students pursuing education.

4. **Strategies Used to Maintain Academic Standards** – In India, as envisaged if the academic credit transfer system has to be a successful model, lot of learnings from the existing credit transfer models have to be adopted and it is imperative that the strategies mentioned herein has to be adopted for the success of the model. In the first instance, the national adoption of a consistent education profile is a necessary prerequisite for effective credit transfer system in place, there needs to be a monitoring authority to govern the credit transfers and institutional set up. Simultaneously, the organizational policies and procedures should make it conducive to accreditation and building a national policy.

Strategies	Necessary Conditions
National adoption of a consistent education profile	Credit transfer between education providers needs to have a monitoring and governing body
Organizational accreditation or national recognition of education provider Program accreditation/approval process	Helps to verify a bonafide education provider Institutional committee to peer review internal standards Professional/industry bodies to ensure curriculum enables desired educational outcome
Organizational policies and processes to recognize prior learning and number of credit transfers acceptable for any degree program, conditions and circumstances	Overall organizational policy determining acceptable standards (viz., not more than 50% of credits obtained at another education provider to be recognized)
Quality assurance framework	Establishing min acceptable non disputable scores (eg., IELTS) pertaining to Indian requirements

The strategic advantages far outweigh the disadvantages associated with the gradual motion to a credit transfer system, this foresees enormous benefits for the society and the broader education scheme as a whole, it definitely has far-reaching impacts and will be a move in the correct direction for the Indian greater education system.

5. Conclusion

The Indian higher education system though very vibrant, poised for growth and expansive still has very large scope for improvement. Even if we were to compare the Indian education system with global educators, we see a dearth wherein Indian institutions are not

figured amongst the top rated in the world. Through a movement to the national credit transfer system there will definitely be a possibility of being one amongst the globally recognized portals of higher education.

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THE USAGE OF MOBILE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN CLASS ROOM - 21ST CENTURY

Madhushree L. M¹, Pradeep M. D² and P. S. Aithal³

¹Research Scholar, College of Business Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – India

²College of Social Science and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore – India

³College of Business Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – India

E-mail: madhushreemraju@gmail.com

Abstract

The uses of smart phones and other gadgets in the university class room is becoming a culture in the modern age of technology. Some students are using this technology for the purpose of information only. However, it was distinguished that others use mobile phone to receive messages over different applications such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Viber. It is so significant to understand the impacts of their behaviour. On the other hand, the use of mobile technology effects the teaching strategies. Teachers need to adopt new teaching methodologies to make sure that educational objectives and student's deep learning could be achieved together. It is therefore critical to adopt a balance approach. This paper focus on the use of mobile technology in class room learning and to identify how these technologies are playing role in education for upgrading students' knowledge.

Keywords: Information Technology, Mobile phones, Class room learning, Teaching, and Students, Educational objectives.

1. Introduction

The use of internet in education is important because it offers instant access to available information around the world. Traditional learning and teaching procedures are changing due to the excess of information available through internet resources. Teachers and learners both have instant access to the information on virtually any subject. The fast development of internet resources and its accessibility to conduct learning in virtual environment and it leads students and teachers to adopt new devices and techniques during the process of learning and teaching. In many classrooms across universities and colleges students fetching and using their gadgets and mobile phones in learning processes. It is understandable that learners may use the technology for information related purposes during learning processes in the class rooms. However, some students may use mobile technology and other gadgets to communicate with friends and families through available social applications and other networking sites. Due to this, the author of this research became interested in findings the behaviours of the students in the class room environment. It is interested to find out that how the use of mobile technology and social networking applications effect student's learning process. Research has shown that the use of mobile technology is a great experience for students during the provision of teaching. Mobile technology could be used for efficiency and

effectiveness while collecting information from the web. So, students could use mobile technology for audio recording purposes in the class room. This is how they record teacher's lectures and this further helps students to learn in effective ways. Mobile technology is a great tool for the live polling, if the class room strength is heavy. This will help teachers to understand student's thinking and effective teaching could be delivered through this process.

2. Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the use of information technology and its applications in education especially in the class room environment.
- 2) To identify the benefits of mobile phone technologies in classroom learning.
- 3) To study the new teaching methodologies that can help to balance learning and teaching processes through the use of information system and technology and its available applications.
- 4) To know the how to use of mobile technologies in classroom learning.

3. Research Scope and Limitation

The conducted research will be useful for the education industry as it will help teachers to adopt new teaching techniques and methodologies in the class room environment and to balance to use of information technology and systems. The research is also beneficial to understand the behaviour of the students due to the impacts of the technology and information systems in education.

The scope of the research could be measured through the scope of information technology and its use in the educational environment. Time and available resources could be the possible limitations of this research. From academic and educational point of view, the research will provide a comprehensive approach adopted to understand the use of mobile technology and its role in the education especially in the class room environment. From social aspect, the research will provide an opportunity to understand the behaviour of students and its relationship with technology during the provision of teaching and learning. The scientific value of the research will be the outcomes in the form of recommendations that would be helpful to balance the use of mobile technology and new teaching methodologies to achieve educational objectives

4. Conceptual Framework/ Theoretical Frame work

5. Benefits of using technology in the classroom

It is important to acknowledge that students are already interested and engaged in using technology, this creates many amazing opportunities for schools and teachers to benefit from integrating some forms of technology in the classroom and to make teaching and learning more effective. Here are some of the main benefits of using technology in the classroom.

A. Improves engagement

When technology is integrated into lessons, students are expected to be more interested in the subjects they are studying. Technology provides different opportunities to make learning more fun and enjoyable in terms of teaching same things in new ways. For instance, delivering teaching through gamification, taking students on virtual field trips and using other online learning resources. What is more, technology can encourage a more active participation in the learning process which can be hard to achieve through a traditional lecture environment.

B. Improves knowledge retention

Students who are engaged and interested in things they are studying, are expected to have a better knowledge retention. As mentioned before, technology can help to encourage active participation in the classroom which also is a very important factor for increased knowledge retention. Different forms of technology can be used to experiment with and decide what works best for students in terms of retaining their knowledge.

C. Encourages individual learning

No one learns in the same way because of different learning styles and different abilities. Technology provides great opportunities for making learning more effective for everyone with different needs. For example, students can learn at their own speed, review difficult concepts or skip ahead if they need to. What is more, technology can provide more

opportunities for struggling or disabled students. Access to the Internet gives students access to a broad range of resources to conduct research in different ways, which in turn can increase the engagement.

D. Encourages collaboration

Students can practice collaboration skills by getting involved in different online activities. For instance, working on different projects by collaborating with others on forums or by sharing documents on their virtual learning environments. Technology can encourage collaboration with students in the same classroom, same school and even with other classrooms around the world.

E. Students can learn useful life skills through technology

By using technology in the classroom, both teachers and students can develop skills essential for the 21st century. Students can gain the skills they will need to be successful in the future. Modern learning is about collaborating with others, solving complex problems, critical thinking, developing different forms of communication and leadership skills, and improving motivation and productivity. What is more, technology can help develop many practical skills, including creating presentations, learning to differentiate reliable from unreliable sources on the Internet, maintaining proper online etiquette, and writing emails. These are very important skills that can be developed in the classroom.

F. Benefits for teachers

With countless online resources, technology can help improve teaching. Teachers can use different apps or trusted online resources to enhance the traditional ways of teaching and to keep students more engaged. Virtual lesson plans, grading software and online assessments can help teachers save a lot of time. This valuable time can be used for working with students who are struggling. What is more, having virtual learning environments in schools enhances collaboration and knowledge sharing between teachers.

6. Mobile phones in classroom learning

Allowing mobile devices to be used inside the classroom is still a debateable issue surrounding schools in the Philippines today. School administrators, faculty as well as parents opposed the idea of utilizing mobile devices in the classroom. Though, some schools do allow their students to use this provided that it will be used for instructional purposes only. Students today have their own ways of learning using technology.

From taking notes to creating their own digital magazines is their own way of dealing with lessons. Major adjustments must be made by teachers who are non-digital natives. Efforts must be exercised to come up with the demands of time. We can never come back but instead look forward and look for other opportunities' technology could offer. Effects of Texting, Twitter, and Message.

Because mobile technology is becoming so prominent in children's lives, many schools are attempting to use it for teaching and learning. The report included information about activities intended to develop critical thinking skills, master literacy, learn world languages, and improve skills in mathematics, engineering, technology, and science. Some of these

examples of mobile learning utilized the standard features of mobile devices, while others used new innovative features.

7. Content on Student Learning:

Many teachers today are facing the dilemma whether they integrate mobile devices in their lessons or not. It is a common knowledge that our students today are already glued in using mobile phones for personal usage or for school works.

Teachers need to exert more effort in making the students remain interested in the lesson in spite the many challenges that they are facing in today's generation of learners. Effects on the use of mobile device in the classroom may vary depending on how students will be utilizing it. We must consider new possibilities which we have at our disposal.

Teachers can gain valuable real-time insight into the knowledge of their students and the effectiveness of their teaching. It's about time that we adopt new revolution in the classroom. On the other hand, students alike may get positive results in their learning. Choosing the best options on how to integrate mobile devices in the teaching and learning process can help a lot of ways to improve students' academic performance.

8. Efficiency VS Effectiveness

In education, lecturers can prepare PowerPoint presentations and upload to a Learning Management System rather than have to print a copy for each student. Students can read their course materials on their smartphones even while in bed, rather than have to go to the computer labs on the campus before having access to the materials. As explained previously, all these only speaks of an efficient use of technology.

This means that whereas technology use in education is increasing, several students and teachers only use technology to make them efficient and not necessarily effective. Technology provides a whole new opportunity for doing things in a different way. The powerful features of the mobile technology should be creatively used to make our work effective and to achieve high results. Lecturers must not simply add technology to make learning efficient, they must plan for the creative use of these technologies in the classroom.

9. 5 Ways to Use Mobile technology In the Classroom

Technology is powerful and it can be used in several great ways to make teaching and learning powerful. What can be done and what cannot be done is limited, basically by the creativity of the user. So, the more creative and innovative we get, the more results we'll see with using technology in class. However, I will provide a few examples just to help you get an idea of what an effective use will look like.

1. Use of Audio Recording Feature:

Students often require personal and quality feedback on the work they turn in. Lecturers can make use of the audio recording feature built into most smartphones to provide these personal and yet quality feedback to all students. Research has proven that students not just liked feedback given this way, but even preferred it.

2. Live Polling Tools

Live digital polling/quizzing tools can be used both as welcome and exit tickets in the classroom for formative assessment. Lecturers can use these tools (many of which are free) to determine what students already know and what should be concentrated upon. This can also provide insight into individual student strength and weakness and help give personalized instruction when needed.

3. Creating of Videos

Rather than have students write a 2000-word essay after researching on a topic, where several of them would simply copy and paste paragraphs without necessarily understanding the content, lecturers could ask students to research and create 5 minutes or less video or audio recording of what they had researched about.

4. Chat and Online Discussion Forums

Lecturers can exploit the group chat features of mobile devices to create an online discussion forum to encourage class participation on content topics, even outside the classroom. Students can chat and discuss (with or without the lecturer) while at home or over the weekend on a subject in class to increase understanding of concepts.

5. Use of QR Codes

Quick response (QR) codes are another great way to use mobile technology in the classroom. Links to further resources, complex diagrams and images, solutions to tasks could be coded and made available to students.

There are several more ways by which both students and lecturers can creatively use mobile technology in the classroom. Again, technology is powerful and its benefits go beyond just making our work efficient. It can increase productivity and help us achieve greater results in our work, thereby making us effective.

10. There are also five predominant challenges facing mobile learning today.

1. **Negative Implications:** Some mobile devices may contribute to unethical behavior by students or distraction in the classroom. Mobile devices may also compromise the physical health and privacy of students.

2. **Cultural Norms:** Most teachers and parents currently consider cell phones to be a distraction in school.

3. **Theory of Learning:** At the time of publication, there is no accepted theory of learning for mobile technologies.

4. Differentiation: Mobile technologies are diverse, which presents a significant challenge for teachers.

5. Limitations: Some mobile technologies feature poor designs with usage limitations that may adversely affect learning.

In spite of these challenges, there are several market trends that improve the usefulness of mobile technologies in education. For example, most cell phones include features that were once expensive luxuries. Many cell phones also include GPS technology, and it is now possible to use a large number of software applications on devices from different manufacturers. Finally, many mobile devices now include a touch screen, which improves the way students interact with them.

11. Given all of this information, there are five main goals to which educators using mobile technologies in the classroom should aspire.

1. Educators must seek to understand that mobile language is unique for educational reform. This segment of education requires much research and support from both the public and private sectors to succeed.
2. Educators must develop interventions for mobile learning to promote public understanding of the technology's ability to improve education for children of all ages. One way to accomplish this is by creating examples of mobile technology in education and presenting them to the public.
3. Educators must actively promote the use of mobile technologies in the classroom to the public and to educational policymakers.
4. Educators must prepare for the use of mobile technologies in the classroom by training colleagues to use and incorporate mobile devices into learning.
5. Educators must seek support from the country's leadership for the educational use of mobile technologies.

Mobile technologies are unlikely to depart from children's lives any time soon. The potential of these devices for educational use cannot be ignored. While the debate has always been whether or not these devices have a place in the classroom, educators should now focus on how they can be used.

12. Conclusion

The use of mobile learning technology effects students' knowledge improvement in academic performance. Alternatively, the educational objectives got a direct link between with the use of mobile technology in the class room environments. It is impossible to stop students from using mobile during the course of lecture deliver and therefore teachers need to adopt new techniques and methodologies to balance this and overcome issues raised due to the use of mobile applications. It is equally important to look on the students learning capabilities and teachers who use mobile technology during the course of their lecture delivery for the better educational improvement. Finally, am going to conclude that using mobile technology in class room learning will make students to act smart in all stages.

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Paper 19

NEW APPROACHES TO TEACHING AND LEARNING THROUGH ONLINE EDUCATION AND EVALUATION METHODS

Krishna Prasad K.

College of Computer and Information Sciences,
Srinivas University, Mangaluru-575001, Karnataka, India
E-mail: krishnaprasadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Abstract

As literacy increases in youth, the dream of acquiring university degree and getting a job in the same profession remains a constant desire of those who attend regular courses in various universities of the globe. As the world is continuously changing, the online education system and evaluation methods are also changing at the same speed in order to meet the demand and changing requirements of the aspirants or youth. Due to many constraints people not able to continue classroom-based teaching and learning and want to acquire the same amount of knowledge and experience through online education. Online learning is the greatest revolution for interested learners; otherwise, they have to pay lacks of the amount to attend a prestigious institution for traditional classroom or school-based degrees. Due to the increasing demand for online education, there is a great necessity for new approaches to improve the quality of online education in terms of student engagement and practical experience. Swayam Prabha, Swayam NPTEL, EDX are some the best online education platforms which have taken some new approaches like continuous assessment through regular assignments, quizzes, student feedback, video lecturing, and mock tests. The evaluation systems are very important to scale or know the students' knowledge they have acquired through online education and which cannot be fulfilled with a merely final examination. For the continuous evaluation, there is a great necessity of changes or new approaches in the existing online education evaluation system and which will help to make more students turn to the online education system. This paper discusses various new approaches for teaching and learning, through online education and evaluation methods with its pros and cons. Some of the new approaches for online education are ICT enabled mobile learning, animated video lecturing.

Keywords: ICT, Evaluation Methods, Mock Test, Online Education, New Approaches, Teaching and Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

A healthy education has been a well-defined method of teaching that promotes knowledge, helps to learn, acquires unique values, beliefs or practices, and leads to a person's general personal growth. Presently, without going to visit the classroom, people can learn innovative ideas and sit anywhere and anytime or omnipresent with the aid of advanced developments in IT [1-2]. Pedagogical technology leads to increasing efficiency via its use and governance of

technological equipment or procedures or resources in a number of areas, such as learning theory, computer-based education, online learning and m-learning [3-5]. In classroom based education system means that students don't even have the right to change the content of the curriculum or topic instantly and that teacher passes knowledge to students of a constrained classroom. Mobile teaching or m-learning is not effective or successful due to various constraints, such as: (1) small screen size, (2) low teachings quality; (3) limited teaching bandwidth, (4) high communication expenses, (5) poor learning and certificate methods; (6) lack of technical capabilities, (7) lack of integrated room and unavailability of one-to - one communication or verbal communication. As the world is changing constantly, online education and evaluation procedures are changing at the same speed to fulfill the changing requirements of the aspirants or teenagers. Due to many constraints, people could not continue teaching and learning based on the classroom or traditional learning and wants to learn the very same amount of information and experience through online training.

There is a high necessity of new approaches to teaching and learning to overcome the existing problems of online education system. In this way massive open online courses are introduced like EDX, NPTEL, SWAYAM, and these portals have made online education dynamic and active through video sessions and

2. EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Technology in education is service concepts like technology in transport, technology in services with the aid of special hardware, software, or system which improves the overall performance or effectiveness of education [6-8]. A good Education is a well-defined process of acquiring skills, facilitating learning, obtaining special values, beliefs or habits, which results in overall individual growth of a person. Nowadays a student can learn new concepts without actually visiting the traditional classroom and sitting anywhere, anytime, or ubiquitously with the aid of advanced developments in Information and communication technology. Normally educational technology can be classified as Hardware approach, Software approach, Systems approach. Hardware approach uses some special physical equipment like microphone, which is essential to make voice audible to a big crowd or audience and helps the teacher to make his teaching very effective. In these context audio-visual aids such as slides, charts, models, graph, and some of the electronic gadgets like radio, television, filmstrips, projectors, video, and high-speed computers are successfully used in order deliver educational contents to the audience or students and to make the teaching very effective. The second type of educational technology is mainly based on behavioral sciences and this type of technology adopt process based techniques with an ultimate intention to produce high-quality teaching-learning content or material, special teaching or learning strategies or assessment technologies. The third type of educational technology is based on computer engineering and usually referred to like the system. Educational Technology is usually classified into two as;

1. Technology of Education
2. Technology in Education

3. TECHNOLOGY OF EDUCATION

It is inherent or natural in education itself which is not derived or exported from any external source. It refers to behavioral science and applications of teaching and learning practices used

by the teacher to deliver the content in more understandable way to students. It focuses on solving the educational problems and the different techniques used in teaching learning problems with an ultimate goal to make the students understandable in more effective and easily [9-12]. Not only the teaching but also the techniques of planning, financing, and administration are also included in technology of education. Techniques of curriculum planning, teaching, learning, and evaluating also come under technology of education. The technology of education generally includes or covers following techniques;

Planning and Analysis or Examination of Instructional problems

- Selection of instrument or process or special methods for evaluation
- The various strategies adopted to obtain desired result from the teaching learning process.
- The behavior of the teacher
- Programmed learning techniques
- System analysis

4. TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Technology in education involves the use of special implements, tools, machines, or computer systems as like we use these for the cultivation and development of agriculture, industry, or day to day life with an intension to reduce human interaction and to fill the gap between scientific technology and education. Technology in education includes electronic media projector, film, radio, teaching machine, computer, TV and Internet. Technology in education is the application of engineering principles and various types of technologies which work together to attain some goals in education. The origin of technology in education lies in physical science or engineering principles, whereas technology of education lies in behavioral science. The table 1 shows differences between Technology of education and Technology in education.

Table 1: Differences between Technology of Education and Technology in Education

Areas	Technology of Education	Technology in Education
1. Basis	Based on the physiological behavior of the teacher.	Based on the principles of physical science and engineering technology and smart machines
2. Approach	The approach is usually logical in nature and also can be identified as software approach	The approach is physical in nature which we can see and feel and also can be identified as hardware approach
3. Origin	Its origin is based on application of behavior science based problems	Its origin is based on physical science and engineering to education.

4. Examples	Textbook, Workbook, newspapers, evaluation software	TV, Projector, Computer, OHP, Filmstrips, Video, Models.
5. Relation	It's related to learning aids and which helps to improve learning efficiency.	It's related to teaching aids and which helps to improve teaching efficiency.
6. Requirement	In order to handle this approach does not require skilled persons.	In order to handle this approach require skilled persons unlike software approach
7. Flexible	This approach not more flexible in nature	This approach is more flexible in nature
8. Type	Here constructive educational technology is utilized	Here relative educational technology is utilized.
9. Application or Contribution to educational system	This approach is very helpful in understanding the need of the learners or students and educating them based on their ability	It is applicable in mass education programmes and can be reached to large audience.
10. Cost	This approach is less expensive	This approach is expensive.

5. WHY STUDENTS NEED TECHNOLOGY IN CLASSROOM?

Following are the various reasons in support of use of technology in classroom [13-14].

- Nowadays smart mobile phone comes with various applications or apps which helps and assists the students in teaching and learning process. The challenge is to monitor the usage of mobile phones because lot of non-educational contents also delivered through mobile devices.
- Integrating technology with classroom makes students all over the world single group with students of various learning styles and behaviors.
- Technology in education helps the students in team management, team building by interacting with their classmates and instructors.
- Using technology in classroom makes or builds a platform for teachers and all other types of faculty members to enhance and develop student's eco-friendly, paperless digital content development skills. At the same time usage of mobile devices monitored and controlled safely, correctly and responsible way.
- Integrating technology with education makes the students more engaged because all the students' community has been engaged in using mobile phones most of the time.
- Integrating or combining classroom with virtual reality is a live example to demonstrate how the technology influences and enhances the teaching learning experience of both students and teachers and creates new opportunities.

- Through Wi-Fi enabled classroom and mobile technology students can able to access most updated information
- Through the adoption technology in education traditional passive learning model is vanished and teacher becomes only encourager, guide or a coach.
- Technology helps the students to become more creative, interactive, responsible, and connected.

6. CUSTOMIZED AND UBIQUITOUS MOBILE LEARNING (CUML)-SYSTEM

The system has four components as Server (video lecturing provider), Client (Learners), Content Provider Engine and Sensor Network. Each component has different tasks.

Server

This component provides permission or privilege to video lecturing provider to access CUML-system services. It permits authorized video lecturing provider to upload the video classes' content, SMS and send announcements using WiMax.

Client (Learner)

This component is related to the registered learners who have privileges to use the system. The learner can connect to server in order to access multi disciplinary subject's video lecturing classes. Following are the some important function of client component.

- Once registration is approved by the server, learner can login to the CUML system with valid user name and password.
- Receive the SMS from server informing new video lecturing class in respective field
- Learner can request for video lecturing class which includes duration of 1hour or more in multi disciplinary subjects
- User can change the password whenever required
- Learners can give feed back to the video lecturing class provider through server.
- Learners can discuss about particular video lecturing class through server.

Content Provider Engine

This component is useful, when the server is not able to find video lecturing class file requested by the client, server passes this request to content provider engine. Content provider engine search for the file in Web and finds the file. The new file is stored in database, so that when user requests for the same file, server process the request by retrieving the file from its database. Following are the some important function of content provider engine component.

- Successfully search the video lecturing class file from the web, when server is not able to locate.
- Store the new content in server local database

- Provide the content in one standard version or format.

Sensor Network

This component is used to automatically sense the user personal and environmental situations. Following are the some important function of Sensor Network component.

- Identify the learner's location so that location specific video lecturing is provided to user
- On-body sensor can identify level of heartbeat and blood pressure in order to provide some video lecturing class related to that
- Environmental sensor includes temperature, humidity and air ingredients using that system is able to find situations or parameters around the sensor and to provide specific video information to user.

7. LOCATION BASED ADAPTIVE MOBILE LEARNING–SYSTEM

Location information of the user is highly important data in Location Based Adaptive Mobile Learning (LBAML). This can be one of the key attributes to change the content of a material or to add more information to the already existing content. In this model, we will be using GPS device, especially GPS receiver to track the geographical position of the user and to provide content based on this data. The task of the GPS receiver is to track latitude, longitude and altitude coordinates of the user, who is trying to access the content of the respective material. Once the location sent by the particular user is processed by the server, he will be able to access modified content of the material from geographically dispersed locations. One user can select more than one location at the time of registration. In registration process the user has to register location information along with his/her personal information. The user gets access to material after evaluating User-id, password and location information. The important information about the user like username, password, location information and other personal information's are stored in a cloud database. The system has four components as Server, Client (Learner), Location Tracking System and Content Provider Engine. Each component has different functions

8. CONCLUSION

M-learning provides great flexibility and freedom for the learners to learn anytime, anywhere, without any restrictions to physical barrier. The learning utilizes different hardware and software technologies and there is complete freedom of the learners to exist different location than the teacher. The evaluation systems are very important to scale or know the students' knowledge they have acquired through online education and which cannot be fulfilled with a merely final examination. For the continuous evaluation, there is a great necessity of changes or new approaches in the existing online education evaluation system and which will help to make more students turn to the online education system. This paper discussed various new approaches for teaching and learning, through online education and evaluation methods with its pros and cons.

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Paper 20

EMPOWERING WOMEN THROUGH EDUCATION IN INDIA

Pradeep M. D.

Assistant Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University,
Karnataka, India

Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

Abstract

Education spreads along our lives from birth to death which fills our action with values, dignity, ethics and virtues. Human civilization moves along social, moral, cultural attributes. University Grants Commission (UGC), National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) regulates women education in India. Women Study Centers conduct studies on status, problems and issues on women education. Women illiteracy makes them deprived. Social, economic and political empowerment of women through education is the need of the day. This paper reviews various legislative and policy framework on women education in India.

Keywords: Education, Knowledge, Skills, University, UGC, Empowerment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is an instrument for self-reliance and selflessness. Aristotle said that education sound mind in a sound body to experience the power of supreme truth, goodness and beauty [1]. It provides women with knowledge, skills and self-confidence [2]. Empowerment challenges patriarchy to prevent discrimination [3]. Integration of women in economic development indicates improved social status [4]. The literacy rate of 82.14% among men and 65.46% among women created huge gap. Women literacy is low in rural. Illiterate women are subjected to divorce, desertion, domestic violence, child marriages, dowry, poverty, discrimination, abduction, rape, molestation etc. Women are constrained to domestic affairs but country demands their equal participation. The modern initiatives on Free and compulsory education, freedom to hold high offices, political rights has created changes. There is a need for encouraging women education in health care, nutrition, legal education, family welfare, self employment, vocational training suitable to the present requirements. Educating mothers is very important as they nourish, nurture and mould the character of the next generation.

2. POLICIES ON WOMEN EDUCATION

Government of India oriented on 'Promotion of welfare', 'Development' and 'Empowerment' philosophies. It initiated [5] University Education Commission, Secondary Education Commission (1952-53), The Central Social Welfare Board (1953), Condensed and Vocational Training Courses [6], University Grants Commission (1956), National Committee on Women Education (1958-59), Condensed Course for Adult Women (1958), Committee on

differentiation of Curriculum for Boys and Girls (1961), Correspondence Courses (1962), Committee to study the Public Support for Women Education (1963), Education Commission (1964-66), Committee on Status of Women (1971-74), Integrated Child Development Services (1975), Assistance to Voluntary Organisation (1982), The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 1985, Department of Women and Child Development (1985), National Policy on Education (1986), Constitution of University at Puna, Padmavathi University at Tirupathi, Womens University Bijapur [7], National Literacy Mission (1988), 597 districts were covered under Total Literacy Campaigns [8], Mahila Samakhya Programme (1988), Introduced Legal education [9], Joint Council for Vocational Education (JCVE 1990), Programme of Action (1992), The Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS) was established impart vocational training [10], Teachers Education (1995), National Council for Teachers Education was constituted under National Council for Teacher Education Act, 1993 on the 17th August, 1995, Open and Distance Learning (ODL) and Teacher Education Institution are made to get Compulsory Accreditation in every 5 years from NCTE [11], The National Plan of action for the Girl Child (1991-2000) to prevent female foeticide, infanticide, discrimination, assault and abuse [12], Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2000-2001) imposed moral obligation of providing primary education upon the parents, teachers, educational administrators and other stakeholders [13], Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (2004) were constituted, National Curriculum Framework 2005 introduced three language formula for teaching regional, mother tongue, Hindi and English along with teaching through work by making teacher a facilitator with continuous appraisal system, Model School Scheme (November 2008) with special emphasize on health education, health checkups, special teachers, educational tours and NCC training to the students [14], Incentives to Girls for Secondary Education (May 2008) was introduced, National Means cum Merit Scholarship Scheme (May 2008) to be disbursed through the State Bank of India directly into student accounts on quarterly basis [15], Saakshar Bharat (September 2009) to build critical consciousness to face deprivations and disabilities [16], Right to Education (April 2010) through the Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 inserted Article 21-A into the Constitution to provide free and compulsory education for all children between 6 to 14 years as a Fundamental Right, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (2016) policy was constituted.

3. WOMEN EDUCATION POLICIES FOR MINORITIES

National Institute of open Schooling (November 1989) was constituted. Open Basic Education by way of distance or continuing educational programme started. The Government initiated centrally sponsored School-based vocational education in 1988. National Commission for Minorities Educational Institutions (NCMEI 2004) was constituted with head quarters in Delhi. Nai Roshni The Scheme for Leadership Development of Minority Women (2012-13) scheme was started to benefit Muslim, Sikh, Christian, Buddhist and Parsi women notified under section 2 (c) of the National Commission for Minorities Act, 1992. Maulana Azad National Fellowship for Minority Students to provide integrated five years fellowship in the form of financial assistance to 756 students from minority communities with 30 per cent reservation to minority women every year notified by the Central Government to pursue M.Phil and Ph.D courses. UGC will select the candidates for award of scholarship in a transparent manner. UGC shall disburse the fellowship amount to the candidates through electronic clearance system (ECS) wherever feasible. The income ceiling of the parents/guardians of the candidate for this scholarship will be Rs.2.5 Lakh per annum. The quantum of fellowship for JRF and SRF will be at par with the UGC fellowship as amended from time to time. Maulana Azad National Scholarship Scheme for Meritorious Girl

Students of Minority was constituted to provide Scholarship to students passed S.S.L.C. exam and taking admission to 11th standard after declaration of 10th standard result for that year. Educational Loan from National Minorities Development Finance Corporation extends educational loans to facilitate job oriented education for the eligible persons belonging to Minorities. Maximum amount of Rs. 10 Lakhs is available at the rate Rs. 2 Lakhs per annum for technical and professional courses of durations not exceeding five years and Rs. 3 lakhs is for short duration cost intensive skill development training upto 01 year. Further for courses abroad, a maximum amount of 20 lakhs is available at Rs 4 lakhs per annum for any course with duration of maximum 5 years. Funds for this purpose are made available to the State Channelizing Agencies at an interest of 1% per annum to lend to the beneficiaries at 3% interest per annum. The loan shall be payable within five years after completion of the course.

4. CONCLUSION

It has recognized that sustainability in economic growth can be attained only through the equal participation of women in the development process of the country. The government began to direct its effort towards mainstreaming of women into the national development process by enacting various legislations to install equality, social justice and fraternity in the society [17]. The legislative and policy framework on education has facilitated the spread of education in the country. Gender disparity in literacy rates declined by 5.34 % points from 21.59 % prevailed in 2001 to 16.25 % in 2011 [18]. Gender equity can be promoted by changing the interaction at home, school, college, university and workplaces by creating favourable environment fostering the equality. The Ministry of Women and Child Development Government of India jointly instructed the Universities to implement 'Gender Champions' programme to recognize the leadership among women by the end of 2015. Extensive reforms in judicial mechanisms for responsive, sensitive administration of justice need to be attained. It is also very important to treat the loopholes of the related laws and check the execution procedures in detail.

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CURRENT SCENARIO AND CHALLENGES IN FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

Mr. Sagar Srinivas

Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: sagarsrinivas@ymail.com

Abstract

Indian Food Processing Industry is the world's second-largest producer of food next to China and has the potential of being the biggest in the food and agriculture sector. The Indian food industry is poised for huge growth, increasing its contribution to world food trade every year. In India, the food sector has emerged as a high-growth and high-profit sector due to its immense potential for value addition, particularly within the food processing industry. Accounting for about 32 percent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MOFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 percent export oriented units. The Indian Food Processing Industry with its vast potential has emerged as one of the major drivers of economic growth and development. India has been and is one of the world's major food producers but accounts for less than 1.5% of international food trade. This indicates vast scope for both investors and exporters. India's increased urbanization, improved standards of living and the convenient need of dual-income families point out to the major market potentialities in the food processing and market sectors. Being one of the world's largest producers of food grains, India has been ranked second in the world for the production of fruits and vegetables and regarded first in milk production providing much-needed food security to the nation.

Keywords : Collaborations , Industrial licenses, Immense potential, Investors, Urbanization.

1.Introduction

The Food processing industry is poised for huge growth, increasing its contribution to world food trade every year. In India, the food sector has emerged as a high-growth and high-profit sector due to its immense potential for value addition, particularly within the food processing industry. Accounting for about 32 per cent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 per cent export oriented units. Food processing is the transformation of cooked ingredients, by physical or chemical means into food, or of food into other forms. Food processing combines raw food ingredients to produce marketable food products that can be easily prepared and served by the consumer. As per Ministry of Food Processing of India (MOFPI), the term 'food processing'

is mainly defined as a process of value addition to the agricultural or horticultural produce by various methods like grading, sorting and packaging. In other words, it is a technique of manufacturing and preserving food substances in an effective manner with a view to enhance their shelf life; improve quality as well as make them functionally more useful. It covers a wide spectrum of products from sub- sectors comprising agriculture, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries. It also includes other industries that use agricultural inputs for manufacturing of edible products.

Accounting for about 32 per cent of the country's total food market, The Government of India has been instrumental in the growth and development of the food processing industry. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MOFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. India's food processing industry received 43% higher foreign direct investment (FDI) in the fiscal 2016-17 on the back of favourable policy measures. The food processing industry plays a vital role in the economy of any country because it links agriculture to industry. The food processing industry is responsible for diversification of agriculture, improvement of value-added opportunities, and creation of excess that can be exported. The food processing industry of India is one of the largest in the world in terms of manufacture, use, export, and development. The sector has immense potential to contribute to growth and employment opportunities of the country. The food processing industry in India has players from private, public and cooperative sectors. The Food Products Order (FPO) of 1955, Meat Food Products Order (MFPO) of 1973, and Food and Standards Act of 2006 ensure that the food items made after processing in India meet international standards of hygiene and quality.

2.Opportunities in Food Processing Industry

There are abundant opportunities for food processing companies in India. The demand for various products of food processing industry is on the rise because of the increase in per capita income of the Indians which results in higher spending on value added foods. In terms of volumes of production, India ranks amongst the highest in the world in some of the food products. The table below shows areas of Food Processing in India which have considerable output.

Table No-01

Food Processing Category	Amount Annually (in Tonnes)	Processed (in Million)	Rank in the world in terms of production
Milk and milk products	88		1st
Fruits and Vegetables	150		2nd
Rice	132		2nd
Sugarcane	289		2nd
Fish Production	6.3		3rd

Wheat, Groundnuts, Tea, Coffee, Spices, Sugar, Eggs and Oilseeds	-	Amongst the top five producers in the world
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This shows that a lot of supply is available for processing in India. The opportunity emerges when we analyze the percentage of volume that is processed to the volume that is produced. In India around 2% of fruits and vegetables are processed, 37% of milk is processed 1% of meat and poultry is processed and 12% of fish is processed. Comparing this to 80% quantity produced being processed in developed countries; we realize that a massive opportunity exists in the food processing business in India.

3.Reasons to invest in food industry

- 1) India ranked 12th in the World in exports of food and food products in 2017
- 2) Major industries constituting the food processing sector are grain milling, sugar, edible oils, beverages, fruits & vegetables processing and dairy products.
- 3) The contribution of the food processing sector to the Gross Value Addition (GVA) in 2014-15 amounts to USD 22 billion at 2011-12 prices. In 2016-17, GVA in food processing grew by 5.78%
- 4) Food processing industry is one of the major employment intensive segments contributing 11.69% of employment generated in all Registered Factory sector in 2017.

4.Issues/ Challenges of Food Processing Industry

- Indifference of policy makers as very little outlays are allocated in Five Year Plans. In the XI FYP, an outlay of Rs. 4000 crore was earmarked out of which significant proportion was not spent
- The legislation's like APMC Acts, Essential Commodities Act, etc restricts free movement of commodities
- Very poor infrastructure i.e. near absence of technologies, incubation facilities, pre-cooling chambers, irradiation facilities, etc
- High tariffs in the form of high excise duties as well as import duties
- Non-tariff barriers in the form of stringent regulation of laboratory testing, grading, sampling and packaging.
- Lack of entrepreneurship, as 70% of the total value of food processing items manufactured in India is dominated by the unorganized sector
- Lack of training facilities related to this industry
- Indian agriculture focuses on traditional crops rather than market-oriented agriculture with diversified commercial crops.

5.HR Challenges in the Food Processing Industry

1. Access to labour with the right skills and talent retention poses a big challenge in workforce management
2. Access to specialized employees in specialized fields like Food Science is difficult
3. Attracting talent is a challenge as employees do not see this industry as a job seeking opportunity
4. The industry is vulnerable to litigation by consumer groups and hence employee training on quality, food safety and compliance is critical
5. Generating Statutory Compliance and HR Reports of different locations.

6.10 Measures to ensure Food security

1. Education and literacy

Role of education in improving farm efficiency and technology adoption has been well established. As agriculture transformed from subsistence to commercial level, farmers seek information on a wide range of issues to acquire knowledge or upgrade their skills and entrepreneurial ability. Literacy emerges as an important source of growth in adoption of technology, and use of modern inputs like fertilizers and machines.

2. Crop diversification

Food availability is a necessary condition for food security. India is more or less self sufficient in cereals but has deficit in pulses and oilseeds. Due to changes in consumption patterns, demand for fruits, vegetables, dairy, meat, poultry, and fishery products has been increasing.

3. Tackling climate change

Food security in India can be achieved by paying higher attention to issues such as climate change, limiting global warming, including the promotion of climate-smart agricultural production systems and land use policies at a scale to help adapt and mitigate ill effects of climate change.

4. Integrated water management

India needs to produce more crop per unit of land and water resources. Improved management of irrigation water is essential in enhancing production and productivity, food security and poverty alleviation. Agriculture is the biggest user of water accounting for over 80 percent of the water withdrawals. It has been projected that availability of water for agriculture use in India may be reduced by 21 percent by 2020, resulting in drop of yields, especially rice, leading to price rise and threat to food security of the poor. Modern methods of irrigation like sprinkler, drip irrigation, fertigation, among other water efficient tools need to be adopted on larger scale.

5. Integrated nutrient management

Attention needs to be given to balanced use of nutrients. Phosphorus deficiency is the most wide spread soil fertility problem in both irrigated and non-irrigated rainfed areas. To improve the efficiency of fertilizer-use, what really needed is enhanced location-specific research on efficient fertilizer practices, improvement in soil testing services, development of improved fertilizer supply and distribution systems and development of physical and

institutional

infrastructure.

6. Improved varieties

In several regions, farmers are not able to get information about the availability of new and improved varieties and some are not having access to quality seeds of these varieties, resulting in lesser yields. This situation has to be corrected by developing a national-level network to monitor and coordinate the activities with the various State government functionaries working in the area of crop production.

7. Improved technology adoption

Adoption of technologies like integrated nutrient management, integrated pest management and integrated weed management need to be made available for adoption to ensure higher production and sustainability of production base.

8. Awareness on population growth

The awareness of the pressures of increasing population growth and consumption patterns on ecosystem functioning should be created to sensitize farmers on adoption of sustainable crop cultivation and management practices.

9. Focus on small farmers

Increase in food production in the country does not necessarily ensure food security, if the poor do not have the buying power. Therefore, participation of small farmers in food production is essential to achieve food security. Most of them being illiterate and having failed earlier either in adopting new technologies or repaying the loan provided under various development schemes. They need support not only to procure inputs but also to gain confidence.

10. Agricultural research education

The agricultural education in India is facing one of the biggest challenges. It has to identify its role in equipping the human resources for enhanced agricultural productivity and sustainable use of natural resources. Agricultural colleges and universities were initially assigned to disseminate scientific knowledge and skills to the farming community and to train them to use such skills for better output.

7. Conclusion

Food processing is typically a mechanical process that utilizes large mixing, grinding, chopping and emulsifying equipment in the production process. The food-processing sector is crucial for the India's development in the era of globalisation, to not only do well on the international front but also to achieve self adequacy on the domestic front. It establishes a vital link between agriculture and the consumer, hence ensuring the manifold growth of the economy. India is the world's second largest producer of food next to China and holds the potential to acquire the numero uno status with sustained efforts. The food processing process introduce a number of contamination risks. food processing include toxin removal, preservation, easing marketing and distribution tasks, and increasing food consistency. In addition, it increases yearly availability of many foods, enables transportation of delicate perishable foods across long distances and makes many kinds of foods safe to eat by deactivating spoilage and pathogenic micro-organisms. the future of the food processing industry is dazzling, with food safety, quality assurance and hygiene norms gaining

importance. The stringent rules laid by the government are sure to take this industry to global standards.

Though there are many promising dynamics which support good growth of food processing industry, there are still some significant constraints which, if not addressed sooner, can impede the growth prospects of the Food Processing Industry in India. One of the biggest constraints is that this industry is capital intensive. It creates a strong entry barrier and allows limited number of players to enter the market. Players mean competition which reduces efforts to improve quality standards. Major challenges faced by the Indian food processing industry include: educating consumers that processed foods can be more nutritious; dealing with low price elasticity for processed food products; need for distribution network; development of marketing channels; streamlining of food laws; improving food quality standards and strengthening food testing network; strengthening institutional framework to develop manpower for improving R&D capabilities to address global challenges. These challenges must be addressed to achieve full potential of the Indian food processing industry.

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INNOVATIVE TEACHING LEARNING METHODS

V. T. Shailashri

Associate Professor, School of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University,
Karnataka, India.

Email: shailashrivt@gmail.com

Abstract

The education sector is changing and making an over haul change in the way it is disseminated to the present generation. Technology has crept into every aspect of teaching–learning process and tried to eradicate rote learning. With the advent of technology students are actively engaging in learning, and education has become more customized to the students. Teachers are becoming more of a facilitator and finding more time towards research as most of the repetitive tasks are done using technology As educators the primary focus is to ensure that students experience positive learning outcomes. Research, however, has shown that there are differences in students’ learning styles and that these differences will have an impact on the overall learning process. One way of ensuring that these positive outcomes are achieved is by identifying the different learning styles. Learning Style Inventory and provides various teaching methods to address the different students’ learning styles in order to enhance the learning process. Each of the Innovative methods of teaching to the students is examined based on the Learning styles adopted by students.

Keywords: Learning style, Innovative Teaching Methods, Technology, Creative Environment

1.Introduction

As we enter the third millennium, education via the internet, intranet or network represents great and exciting opportunities for both educators and learners. Educators have witnessed the rapid development of computer networks and improvement in the processing power of personal computers. In addition, the internet and World Wide Web (WWW) have made the computer a dynamic force in distance education, providing a new and interactive means of overcoming time and distance to reach learners (Wagschal, 1998)[1]. Electronic learning (e-learning) is an evolving, dynamic and rapidly changing educational opportunity that is a product of the advanced information technology environment. E-learning is essentially the network-enabled transfer of skills and knowledge (Anon, 2006)[2]. The internet is the largest, most powerful computer network in the world. It encompasses several million computers with internet addresses that are used by millions of people around the world. As increasingly more colleges, universities, elementary and secondary schools, companies and private citizens connect to the internet, more possibilities are opened for distance educators to overcome time and distance to reach students.[3] Through the internet, all sources of information on different subjects are available anytime, anywhere.

2.Objectives

1. To identify the learning styles by students
2. To identify some Innovative methods of teaching methods to enhance learning

3.Learning Styles

Several classifications of learning style and related concepts have been developed through the years. These classifications include Solomon's Inventory of Learning Styles, the Meyers-Briggs Type Indicator, Howard Gardner's multiple intelligences, McCarthy's 4-Mat system, and Honey and Mumford's (1986) social approach to learning. Perhaps the most widely known approach to assessing learning style, however, is that of David Kolb (1984).[4]

According to Kolb (1984) individuals learn in four stages or modes: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. However, in different learning situations individuals often use different combinations of learning modes; hence no one mode clearly identifies an individual's learning style. The combination of learning modes forms four quadrants reflecting four learning styles: Accommodator, Diverger, Assimilator, and Converger.[5][6]

As indicated above, there is a need to accommodate different learning styles and modes. This accommodation requires more than recognizing the students' learning styles, however. Not only does learning style and mode vary by individual, but teaching style varies as well. Ebeling (2000) suggests that there is evidence most instructors use a teaching style that is comfortable to them and this is often the way they themselves learn best. According to Taylor (1998) all instructors need to be able to address a variety of learning styles and Kay (1998) proposes communication is improved by understanding how people learn. There is research to support varying teaching style to match learning style. Roach et al. (1993) examined alternative teaching styles in marketing classes. Filbeck and Smith (1996) looked at both teaching and learning styles along with age and gender. Borg and Shapiro (1996) studied teaching styles in economics classes. Hayes and Allinson (1996) analyzed 19 studies, which examined matching learning style to learning method and found support in 12 for improved learning performance. Dunn et al. (1995) discuss research showing higher grade point averages resulting from closer matches between teaching and learning styles.[7][8] Finally, Tomlinson (1996) emphasizes the need for instructors to be aware of and adapt to student learning styles.

It is also important to recognize that teaching style often determines course delivery methods. According to Mumford (1995) many activities fail to achieve their potential because they concentrate only on one stage of the learning cycle.[9][10] For example, lectures or books focus on delivering information while ignoring time to act practically on the information. Thus, we see that course delivery methods may impact course effectiveness as well as the differences in student learning styles.[11]

- Concrete experience (feeling): Learning from specific experiences and relating to people. Sensitive to other's feelings[12].

- Reflective observation (watching): Observing before making a judgment by viewing the environment from different perspectives. Looks for the meaning of things.[13]
- Abstract conceptualization (thinking): Logical analysis of ideas and acting on intellectual understanding of a situation.[14]
- Active experimentation (doing): Ability to get things done by influencing people and events through action. Includes risk-taking.[15]

Depending upon the situation or environment, the learners may enter the learning cycle at any point and will best learn the new task if they practice all four modes.

Learning Style	Description
Diverging (concrete, reflective)	Emphasizes the innovative and imaginative approach to doing things. Views concrete situations from many perspectives and adapts by observation rather than by action. Interested in people and tends to be feeling-oriented. Likes such activities as cooperative groups and brainstorming.
Assimilating (abstract, reflective)	Pulls a number of different observations and thoughts into an integrated whole. Likes to reason inductively and create models and theories. Likes to design projects and experiments.
Converging (abstract, active)	Emphasizes the practical application of ideas and solving problems. Likes decision-making, problem-solving, and the practical application of ideas. Prefers technical problems over interpersonal issues.
Accommodating (concrete, active)	Uses trial and error rather than thought and reflection. Good at adapting to changing circumstances; solves problems in an intuitive, trial-and-error manner, such as discovery learning. Also tends to be at ease with people.

4. Innovative methods to accommodate various styles

Educators may not be able to accommodate the learning styles of each student; however, they can design their courses and use a variety of teaching methods to ensure that learners benefit from a comfortable and rewarding experience. Many researchers have suggested that students should be encouraged to use all four learning styles instead of relying on one style. In addition to the usual lecture method, several other pedagogical vehicles can be considered to address the different learning styles.

Computer-based simulation exercises - Simulation exercises are available for several disciplines and have been used quite extensively as a tool to enhance the learning process. In essence, users learn by simulation. Exercises or games are developed to simulate real situations or scenarios and require users to use various skills, and knowledge and often require them to take risks and to experiment with things. The power of simulations is that they engage students more and students are more likely to learn from them as compared to the standard lecture (Andrade, 2007). Simulation, therefore, would be a desirable tool to use to stimulate the interest of accommodators. According to Kolb (1984) accommodators learn primarily from hands-on experience and intuition rather than from logical analysis.[16][17]

Projects/summer internship – projects are widely used where individuals are encouraged to work either on a topic chosen by the instructor or one chosen by students where they are expected to generate a wide range of ideas and gather information. This process requires them to become creative and view situations from different perspectives. This vehicle would enhance the learning process of divergers

Case Analysis – This is another popular tool used to develop analytical thinking. Students are required to use the information presented and to be able to put information into concise and logical form, which is consistent with case studies. Strength of assimilators is their propensity to define problems and this is quite relevant to the case study method.

Z to A approach is experiential learning. Experiential learning is inductive, learner centered, and activity oriented. Personalized reflection about an experience and the formulation of plans to apply learning to other contexts are critical factors in effective experiential learning. The emphasis in experiential learning is on the process of learning and not on the product. Experiential learning can be viewed as a cycle consisting of five phases, all of which are necessary:

- Experiencing (an activity occurs);
- Sharing or publishing (reactions and observations are shared);
- Analyzing or processing (patterns and dynamics are determined);
- Inferring or generalizing (principles are derived); and,
- Applying (plans are made to use learning in new situations).

5. Conclusion

From the above discussion it is seen that there are different learning styles that can be best suited to get oneself involved in the teaching learning process. Accordingly a number of innovative methods can be adopted to enhance the learning process. It is necessary to understand the audience and choose the best suited method of teaching so that the learning environment is creative and both the parties benefit from this.

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EVALUATION APPROACHES FOR OUT COME BASED EDUCATION

Subrahmanya Bhat B

College of Computer and Information Sciences
Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka,
itsbhat@gmail.com

Abstract

Evaluation is the process which determines the level of understanding on a specific course by an individual. Traditional evaluation methods adopted by majority of the higher educational systems in India focus mainly on theory examinations at the end of the course and based the marks scored by an individual. But such systems have failed in really measuring the outcome of a given course. These days where outcome based education has been getting popular among the higher education systems, institutions needs to adopt new evaluation strategies so as to measure the outcome of a given course by an individual. Various evaluation approaches could be considered during the course time mainly, Entry Test, Summary Sessions, Presentation assignments, Case study along with Application of the course concepts by using available software tools. This paper will discuss on these evaluation processes and also correlate its results on the outcome of a given course.

Keywords: Evaluation, Outcome Based Education, Entry Test, Summery Sessions, Case Study.

1. Introduction

Course Design is the process by which the raw data about a learning need is interpreted in order to produce an integrated series of teaching-learning experiences. Presently majority of the institutions among themselves stressing more on outcome based education. For the successful implementation of an outcome based education one needs to design the course accordingly and also system need to adopt a suitable evaluation practice to full fill such outcome based education[8]. Over a period, evaluation process is a traditional method by making students face examination at the end of the course period. Based on the individual's performance in the examination at the end of the course, students learning outcome will be estimated by correlating to his marks. But such systems fail in measuring the outcome of a given course, as majority of the students could able to reproduce the course content without actually knowing the course content. Thus evaluating the students based on marks obtained at the end of the course period can no more reflect the course outcome. Hence, institutions need to adopt some new approaches during the course period to evaluate as well as measure the outcome of the course. New evaluation approaches like Entry Test, Summery Sessions, Case Study, Presentations, Participatory Learning and Application of Software Tools, etc. need to be considered and it has to be done continuously over the course period[9].

2. Limitations with Traditional System

The traditional evaluation methods like examination at the end of the course will finally results with students memorising the course contents rather than getting knowledge. Two or Three hours of examination will lead to judge a student's ability under set conditions and limited time[8]. Many cases a student who actually good may get anxious and confused under because of strict exam conditions and fail to perform better in terms of scores. Faculty as well as students will be sticking to a curriculum focussed on passing or aiming to get high score in a specific exam. This will limit the curriculum to a set range of knowledge and skills and such practice does not provide educational benefits. The faculty will have his eye on the examination, and his teaching will be more of coaching in nature and finally fails in making the students apply their mind. Students, rather than assimilation of knowledge, concentrate more on reproducing course content.

3. Entry Test

This is an assignment to the students to know about the sessions content in advance to the class session. It has been found that sessions will be of more effective if the students attend with little ground working about the session topic. This helps the students to have some base knowledge on the session topic. In addition, these practices help in building interest among the students on the session topic and ultimately improve the knowledge gain. Hence, the faculty should adopt this practice by giving the next sessions topic in each session and asking the students to come with little home work on the given topic. At the beginning of the session, if a test is given to students by means of a quiz and record the performance of each student. At the end of the course period, these performances can be compiled, and it provides a basis for continuous evaluation of a student. This also improves the knowledge base among the students community.

4. Summery Sessions

Similar to the entry test discussed in section three, at the end of the session a summary test can also be considered by the concerned faculty. This summary test should covet major portions of the current session and measure the learning out come of the session. This also can be easily carried by means of conducting a quiz or MCQ method. Such performance also needs to be compiled, and it also can be a basis for continuous evaluation of the student. In addition, it improves the learning outcome among the students community.

5. Case Study and Presentations

Case study and Presentations will help in developing the students learning out come as well as their presentation and communication skills. By assigning independent case studies among the student community, individual students are made to learn about a given company or product or any special scenario in the real world. This makes the individual students to know more details about the given case and come up with detailed facts about the given case. By making him to present the case study among the group of audiences, one can improve on his presentation as well as communication skills. Performance of the students in these case study needs to compiled by the faculties and it also makes a basis for measuring the learning out of a course.

6. Participatory Learning

Participatory Learning is a process where a student is made to involve in some activities that will improve the knowledge base among the student community. At the institution level various activities and events can be conducted under the student leaderships. This will make the student learn about the event management aspects and develops leadership skills. Various groups among the students can be formed and they are made to work in team to coordinate among each team. Faculties have to encourage students participations in such kind of events and their performance needs to consider as a basis for outcome evaluation.

7. Application of Software Tools

In case a course concepts are made to apply on available software tools, then it will greatly improve the learning outcome of that course. This method will make the student actually understand the course content and apply it on some available software tools. For example courses on Networks can be made to deploy over some simulation tools like GNS3, NCTUns[9] or Routerism[10] etc, then students will learn more on that course and it gives them some hands on experience. Similarly, a course on E-commerce is deployed using WordPress tool, then it makes the students better equipped with course concepts rather than a traditional method of class room teaching. More courses need to be designed as of this kind by the faculty team and students performance needs to record periodically. Compiled students performance on usage of such software tools will serve the basis to measure the outcome of the given course by an individual student.

8. Conclusion

Evaluation of a student is a process of assessing the level of learning outcomes on a given course which needs to be carried out on a continuous manner during a course period. Traditional evaluation methods like theory examinations at the end of the course and the marks scored by an individual student cannot be a good scale to measure the learning outcome on that course. A proper evaluation has to be done on the continuous basis throughout during the course period by adopting various methods as discussed in this paper. It has been found that practices like Entry Test and Summary Sessions will greatly improve the learning outcome of given course. Case Study and Presentations will result with additional knowledge gain in addition to improving the overall presentation skills. Participatory Learning approach will greatly improve the learning outcome on a given course apart from building the team work. Application of course concepts using some available software tools will give hands on experience to students which makes the course more interesting and also improves the learning outcome.

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STUDENT CENTERED LEARNING IN CLASSROOMS: A STRATEGY FOR INCREASING STUDENT MOTIVATION AND ACHIEVEMENT

Vaikunth Pai T.

College of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore-575001, India

E-mail: vpaistar@yahoo.com

Abstract

In facing challenges such as rapid globalization, tremendous impacts of information technology, international transformation towards knowledge-driven economy, strong demands for sustainable societal developments, and international competitions in the new century, numerous educational reforms and changes have been initiated in the different parts of the world. Policy-makers and educators in most countries have to think how to reform their education and prepare next generations for meeting challenges of the future (Cheng, 2003a, b; Hirsch & Weber, 1999; Kogan & Hanney, 2000; Mingle, 2000). Student-centered learning is an approach to learning in which learners choose not only what to study but also how and why. At the heart of the learning environment are learner responsibility and activity, in contrast to the emphasis on instructor control and coverage of academic content found in conventional, didactic teaching. Student-centred learning, as the term suggests, is a method of learning or teaching that puts the learner at the centre (cf. Mac Hemer et al, 2007, p.9; Boyer, 1990). With the application of an SCL approach in higher education, there is necessarily a shift in focus from academic teaching staff to the learner. This approach has many implications for the design and flexibility of curriculum, course content, and interactivity of the learning process. The fact that conventional teaching predominantly places its focus on the design, organization and follow-through of the perspective of the academic teacher has made it difficult to determine what students see as constituting SCL, because often they have never been asked. This paper elaborates why and how Student-centered learning is needed to re-conceptualize the practices of action learning to enhance multiple thinking and creativity in learning.

Keywords: Globalization, Knowledge-driven economy, Higher education, Policy makers and educators, Educational reforms etc.

1. Introduction

India has the second largest educational system in the world. A focus on quality, access and relevance of education to achieve the required social transformation for sustainable economic development of the country has been the national priority.

The educational system of the future must embrace a learner-centered perspective to maximize high standards of learning, motivation, and achievement for all learners--for both students and their teachers. The learner-centered perspective begins with a focus on knowing and understanding each learner in the context of a deep understanding of the learning process itself. It couples a focus on knowing and respecting individual learners with the best available

research and practitioner experience about learning. This paper reviews a number of approaches to the learner-centered classroom and provides a synthesis.

There has been increasing emphasis in recent years on moving away from traditional teaching toward student-centered learning. This paradigm shift has encouraged moving power from the instructor to the learner, treating the learner as a co-creator in the teaching and learning process (Barr & Tagg, 1995). Instructors who deliver student-centered instruction include the learner in decisions about how and what they learn and how that learning is assessed, and they respect and accommodate individual differences in learners' backgrounds, interests, abilities, and experiences (McCombs & Whistler, 1997). The role of the instructor in student-centered classrooms is to encourage learners to do more discovery learning and to learn from each other; the instructor focuses on constructing authentic, real-life tasks that motivate learner involvement and participation (Weimer, 2002).

2. Meaning of Student-Centered Learning

Student-centered learning has been defined most simply as an approach to learning in which learners choose not only what to study but also how and why that topic might be of interest (Rogers, 1983). In other words, the learning environment has learner responsibility and activity at its heart, in contrast to the emphasis on instructor control and the coverage of academic content found in much conventional, didactic teaching (Cannon, 2000). Additionally, learners find the learning process more meaningful when topics are relevant to their lives, needs, and interests, and when they are actively engaged in creating, understanding, and connecting to knowledge (McCombs & Whistler, 1997).

The paradigm shift away from teaching to an emphasis on learning has encouraged power to be moved from the teacher to the student (Barr and Tagg 1995). The teacher-focused/transmission of information formats, such as lecturing, have begun to be increasingly criticized and this has paved the way for a widespread growth of 'student-centered learning' as an alternative approach. However, despite widespread use of the term, Lea et al. (2003) maintain that one of the issues with student-centered learning is the fact that 'many institutions or educators claim to be putting student-centered learning into practice, but in reality they are not' (2003:322).

3. Objectives of the study:

- To give an overview of the various ways student-centered learning is defined,
- To suggest some ways that student-centered learning can be used as the organizing principle of teaching and assessment practices,
- To explore the effectiveness of student-centered learning and
- To present some critiques to it as an approach.

4. How can you implement student-centered learning?

Learning is often presented in this dualism of either student-centered learning or teacher-centered learning. In the reality of practice the situation is less black and white. A more useful presentation of student-centered learning is to see these terms as either end of a continuum, using the three concepts regularly used to describe student-centered learning. (See Table 1).

Tab. 1: Student-centered and teacher-centered continuum

5. Implications for teaching/learning methods

The University of Glasgow (2004) identified four main strategies in a study on student-centered learning practices in their University. The first strategy was to make the student more active in acquiring knowledge and skills and might include exercises in class, fieldwork, use of CAL (computer assisted learning) packages etc. The second strategy was to make the student more aware of what they are doing and why they are doing it. A third strategy is a focus on interaction, such as the use of tutorials and other discussion groups. The final strategy is the focus on transferable skills. This last strategy is not mentioned in other definitions of the student-centered learning but does look beyond the immediate course requirements to other benefits to the student in later employment. Table 2 highlights a sample of student-centered learning/teaching methods and includes some ideas for lecturers both within (more teacher-centered) and outside of the lecture format. You may consider, however, in striving to reduce the amount of lecture contact hours for more student-centered formats, where possible.

Implications for assessment practices

Outside of the lecture format	In the Lecture
Independent projects	Buzz groups (short discussion in twos)
Peer mentoring of other students	Pyramids/snowballing (Buzz groups continuing the discussion into larger groups)
Debates	Cross-overs (mixing students into groups by letter/number allocations)
Field-trips	Rounds (giving turns to individual students to talk)

Practicals	Quizzes
Reflective diaries, learning journals	Writing reflections on learning (3/4 minutes)
Computer assisted learning	Student class presentations
Choice in subjects for study/projects	Role play
Writing newspaper article	Poster presentations
Portfolio development	Students producing mind maps in class

Tab. 2: Examples of student centered learning/teaching methods

6. Why do we want to promote student centered teaching? What are its benefits?

Student centered teaching helps us design effective instruction for every member of the classroom, no matter what his or her diverse learning needs. By its nature, student centered teaching is adaptable to meet the needs of every student. In order to design any lesson, the teacher must first think of the students, rather than the content, and so we are assured that the students’ needs are being considered.

- Student centered teaching has been proven effective in its ability to teach students the material they need to know. There are site numerous studies that followed students who were taught in the student centered approach that found that not only does student motivation increase, but actual learning and performance do as well. Students taught in a student centered classroom retain more material for longer periods of time. In order to learn, the brain cannot simply receive information; it must also process the information so that it can be stored and recalled. The active nature of the student centered approach helps students actually work with information, and therefore learn it and store it.
- For foreign language students, especially, the student-centered method has special benefits. When students use the language, they retain it more than if they would hear it. They get practice in actively producing meaningful conversation and they take a more direct route to fluency than they would take, for example, if they filled out worksheets with sentences created by the teacher.
- Even beyond learning what they need to know, students benefit from a less academic side effect of student centered teaching -- they learn how to feel good about themselves. As they take on new responsibilities and succeed with these responsibilities, they come to gain confidence in themselves as competent problem-solvers. Even more, research shows that students have higher achievement when they have confidence in themselves and when they attribute success to their own abilities and not to luck or help. In a student centered approach, it is the students themselves who are responsible for the success of a lesson and therefore they tend to feel more responsible for the success of their own learning.

7. Teacher-centered vs. Learner-centered paradigms

Comparison of Teacher-centered and Learner-centered paradigms (Learner-Centered Assessment on College Campuses by Huba and Freed 2000)	
Teacher-Centered Paradigm	Learner-Centered Paradigm
Knowledge is transmitted from professor to students	Students construct knowledge through gathering and synthesizing information and integrating it with the general skills of inquiry, communication, critical thinking, problem solving and so on
Students passively receive information	Students are actively involved
Emphasis is on acquisition of knowledge outside the context in which it will be used	Emphasis is on using and communicating Knowledge effectively to address enduring and emerging issues and problems in real-life contexts
Professor's role is to be primary information giver and primary evaluator	Professor's role is to coach and facilitate. Professor and students evaluate learning together
Teaching and assessing are separate	Teaching and assessing are intertwined
Assessment is used to monitor learning	Assessment is used to promote and diagnose learning
Emphasis is on right answers	Emphasis is on generating better questions and learning from errors
Desired learning is assessed indirectly through the use of objectively scored tests	Desired learning is assessed directly through papers, projects, performances,

	portfolios, and the like	8. How can we create student centered teaching?
Focus is on a single discipline	Approach is compatible with interdisciplinary investigation	
Culture is competitive and individualistic	Culture is cooperative, collaborative, and supportive	
Only students are viewed as learners	Professor and students learn together	

In order to allow students to gain this power in the class, teachers cannot simply lecture and let students take a passive role. They must design activities that let students take initiative and that let students discover meaningful information for their own lives. They must also get to know the students on an individual basis so that they can better respond to the individual needs and interests of the students. In general, teachers need to focus on the student's needs, abilities, and interests -- they need to "look at how students learn, rather than at what there is to teach.

9. Moving from a teacher/expert approach to a student-centered approach

Although an educational shift, from a teacher/expert approach to a student-centered approach, maybe associated with positive consequences, it nonetheless requires teachers and students to respectively modify their thinking and actions towards education.

First, teachers will need to change their role as professionals, to develop competence programs, to adapt their lectures to include interactions with the class, to consider students' prior knowledge and background (impact of cultures), as well as orient and guide students in their learning process (Frenay et al., 1998). In other words, teachers will need to accept that the relationship between teaching and learning is now different (Tagg and Barr, 1995). Second, students will be required to participate in their own learning process; that is become active learners, and focus on transferring information and knowledge to other disciplines and to real life situations (Frenay et al., 1998).

In sum, a change in approach signifies that both teachers and student change their attitudes and behaviors to education. The already existing normative structure in terms of education needs to be modified in order to support a new way of conceptualizing education. This is precisely what our Normative Theory of Social Change attempts to do. First, our Normative Theory of Social Change offers a theoretical framework for understanding people's reaction in face of dramatic social change that affects the normative structure of a group. Second, our Normative Theory of Social Change proposes a concrete solution designed to facilitate the shift from a teaching/expert approach to a student-centered approach: minority influence.

10. Assessment of Student Centric learning

In a student centered classroom, students are encouraged to participate actively in learning the material as it is presented rather than being passive and perhaps taking notes quietly. In the

student centered classroom students are involved throughout the class time in activities that help them construct their understanding of the material that is presented. The instructor no longer delivers a vast amount of information, but uses a variety of hands-on activities to promote learning.

Four aspects of Creative thinking are involved in Student centered learning. They are:

Inquiry: It is closely associated with science, inquiry or research is the task of acquiring knowledge pertaining to empirical questions. Students should know the language of science like theories, laws, hypotheses etc. and principles of scientific method. They can be taught and instructed to evaluate the credibility of information sources.

Reasoning: Commonly also called inference is the relatively overt mental process which helps us to reach conclusions on the basis of evidence, lies at the heart of higher-order thinking as reasons can be communicated to others.

Inferential errors: It is a means of inoculating people against mistakes.

Argumentation: Students should develop skills of argumentation by constructing and analyzing arguments which also plays a key role in purporting creative thinking.

11. The effectiveness and critiques of student-centered learning

The use of student-centered learning appears to be reflective of today's society where choice and democracy are important concepts, however is it an effective approach to learning? Lea et al. (2003) reviewed several studies on student-centered learning and found that overall it was an effective approach. A six-year study in Helsinki, which compared traditional and activating instruction, found that the activating group developed better study skills and understanding, but were slower in their study initially (Lonka and Ahola 1995). Equally, Hall and Saunders found that students had increased participation, motivation and grades in a first year information technology course (1997). In addition, 94% of the students would recommend it to others over the more conventional approach (Hall and Saunders 1997). Students in a UK University elaborated on the impact of student-centred learning on them, i.e. they felt there was more respect for the student in this approach, that it was more interesting, exciting, and it boosted their confidence (Lea et al. 2003).

Student-centered learning, despite its popularity, is not without its critics. The main critique of student-centered learning is its focus on the individual learner. In addition, there are some difficulties in its implementation, i.e. the resources needed to implement it, the belief system of the students and staff, and students' lack of familiarity with the term. Another concern regarding student centered learning is the belief that students hold in relation to their learning. Students, who value or have experienced more teacher-focused approaches, may reject the student-centered approach as frightening or indeed not within their remit. Prosser and Trigwell's work in higher education emphasizes the different belief systems held by staff and students (2002). They found that lecturers with a teacher-centered approach to teaching held views that students should accommodate information rather than developing and changing their conceptions and understanding. The reverse was true for those with more student-centered approaches to their teaching. Perry's work on the development of University students highlights how students move from a dualistic view that knowledge is right or wrong to a relativist view that all answers are equally valid (Perry 1970). This study highlights that even

during the University years, students can change their view on learning and as they move through the years so to may their views on student-centered learning change.

12. Conclusion

The ultimate goal for student-centered classrooms is for students to gain independent minds and the capacity to make decisions about their life-long learning (Brown, 2008). —What makes learner-centered education transformative is that meaning is co-constructed and that self-regulation occurs through interdependence, with a focus on being and becoming fully functioning (McCombs, 2009, p. 7).

To achieve successful social change in terms of education, there are two necessary steps in order to maximize the likelihood of constructive change in education. First, a student-centered approach needs to be clearly and simply articulated. Second, mechanisms are needed that allow for every stakeholder in the education process to be fully informed about the processes arising from educational reform. For example, schools, institutes and universities need to develop a common identity and sense of belonging to the broader reform-minded community. Since traditionally the Ministries of education have been the major source of power in education, they need to take a leadership role by publicizing new programs and emphasizing a unified philosophy of education.

Student-centered learning is not without some criticism but in general it has been seen to be a positive experience, for example, Edwards (2001) emphasizes the value of student-centered learning: 'Placing learners at the heart of the learning process and meeting their needs, is taken to a progressive step in which learner-centered approaches mean that persons are able to learn what is relevant for them in ways that are appropriate. Waste in human and educational resources is reduced as it suggested learners no longer have to learn what they already know or can do, nor what they are uninterested in'. (Edwards 2001:37).

Technology can play an interesting and essential role in an institution's centralized approach to teaching and outcomes-based handling of student learning. For example, faculty may be required to use e-learning platforms such as Black Board or Web CT. This process-painful though it may be for many individuals-typically forces teachers to think more reflectively about course design, delivery, and assessment. It can stimulate creative new ways to engage students and to incorporate highly contemporary materials, while sensitizing faculty to the range of new challenges and possibilities inherent in the application of educational technologies.

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VIRTUAL PLACEMENT CELL FOR HEI

Varun Shenoy* & Dr. P. S. Aithal**

College of Management and Commerce*, Srinivas University**

City Campus Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575001

varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

Abstract

Placement Assistance is one of the most important services that HEI's (Higher Educational Institutions) provide to their students. This assistance however will be active only if there is a constant interaction between the placement cell and students on continuous levels. Between, placement seeking students require 24/7, 365 days counselling guidance on clearing the interview considering today's market scenario and securing the job where manpower-based placement cell at HEI's following college timing may not cater. Therefore to bridge this gap and ensure full time assistance to students and alumni even when they are at home, we envision a concept of Virtual Placement Assistance online imparting every nut and bolt essential for the true blue placement, from basic Group Discussions tips to Aptitude Tests or Pros and Cons of Interviews as well as scheduling interviews both online and offline for the student candidates round the clock.

Keywords : Virtual Placement Cell, Virtual Placement Office, Virtual Placement Assistance, Virtual Placement Support.

I. Introduction

Not all students are intellectually competent in academics and that is why they undertake tutorials and tuitions outside of the college hours. Similarly, not all students are skill-full in clearing campus interviews and are shrewd job hunters at the campus opportunities advanced to them during the academic season. Now, if the academic tuition taking students outside college hours depend on online learning to supplement or aid their studies in college for better academic performance, similarly then weak students with poor employability skills can also depend on 'technology' to strengthen their professional confidence & abilities. A non-location of literature work in this regards and direct interactions with select Job Seeking students helped to determine the research problem. Therefore, we propose a sustainable 'virtual placement assistance cell' like an *online virtual assistant software* for students to understand the methodologies of job hunting and attending interviews at campus for their first entry level jobs.

II. Objectives

The Primary objective of this concept is to assist & satisfy the student population access placement assistance anytime anywhere 24/7, 365 days. The paper also aims to bring in most modern cutting-edge technologies in the area of Graduate Placement Assistance and Administration at Higher Educational Institutions HEI.

III. Research Methodology

Through Brainstorming methodology and rigorous thought process the conceptual idea is propagated. A theoretical and descriptive method of idea generation has been adopted here to explain the concept.

IV. Concept of Virtual Placement Cell

Virtual Placement Cell refers to the process of providing a range of options through the use of various types of technology to job seeking students and graduates in order to connect them with employment related services. It is managed through self-service platforms where placement professors can put data directly into them and skip the process of going through a manual action. Virtual HEI Placement Cell is expected to be practiced due to its cost reduction impact, to gain competitive advantage and to share risks of miscommunication. It is network-based structure initiative built on partnerships and mediated by information technologies to help the HEI acquire, develop, and deploy employment & job related intellectual capital.

Proposed Phases in Virtualization :

(1) Virtualisation of HEI Placement Cell takes place through installation of a 'Chat Bot' through suitable tracking systems using AI, Automation & Robotics Technology to answer and guide job seeking students on College Whatsapp Chat Channels, College Social Media, College Blogs, College Mobile Application, College Website, College SAS post completion of college timings or even during the college time anything and everything on placement campus interview, training and job search related doubts. A 'Chat Bot' is known as an artificial conversational entity (ACE) which is an AI Computer Program that simulates human conversations, texts and provides relevant information and guidance through Natural Language Processing (NLP). In industry, this concept is reminiscent with Robotic Process Automation (RPA). Robotic process automation (RPA) is performing rules-based, highly transactional processes in the HR department that require little or no human judgment. RPA works by having a AI software "bot" take over high-volume, repetitive operational tasks from HR employees, often improving the accuracy and speed of data processing—such as payroll, benefits enrolment, on-boarding and compliance reporting that all require a significant amount of manual, repetitive labour otherwise. It can also navigate ERP Systems and Service Management Software tools using the applicant's user interfaces just like a human operator that too faster!

(2) To have 24/7 access to a cloud-based document library, where job seeking students can download placement notices and job descriptions, including letters and reports that have been drafted specifically for them.

(3) Connect with recruiters HRMS online to use a common platform via cloud or related technologies. This shall help in stakeholder resource integration and sharing of hiring information directly to job seeking students by the recruiters.

Figure 1 : Flow Diagram of Virtual Placement Cell System in HEI's

Thus, Virtual HEI Placement Cell = Application of Robotics/AI + Cloud/ICT + Integration of HRMS that is expected to be compatible across various software platforms for user access and ensured data security with strong encryption and a policy of data protection in place for stakeholder benefit.

Perceived Advantages and Benefits of HEI Placement Cell Virtualization :

- (1) Increased access to the college placement services 24/7, 365 days anytime anywhere leading to student satisfaction.
- (2) 'ChatBots' dependency can bring in student delight as their new e-friend or e-guide for securing placements.
- (3) The concept shall lead to better internal processes leading to a good quality IQAC or NAAC Gradings in HEI Placement Services.
- (4) Better Student Fraud Detection or their intention to deceive.

Forecasted Challenges in HEI Placement Cell Virtualization :

Despite all the benefits, the integration of virtual mobility into HEI placement cell, either as a complete alternative or as a support mechanism, remains challenging. There are several points of interest both at an organisational, pedagogical and technological levels. Conducting virtual placement assistance work requires a mix of technical tools and processes that stimulate emotional connections among students and graduates.

V. Conclusions

We have discussed a workable concept of HEI Placement Cell Virtualization in this paper. A feasibility determination test is hoped through gathering feedback about the new concept

from the appropriate and relevant stakeholders. Writing a proposal to business organizations for implementation of this concept as a commercial service to HEI's is also in contemplation. AI-based applications have strong potential to raise graduate student productivity and help them become new age professionals thus become knowledgeable job seekers that can boost employability. Applications empowered by AI have an ability to analyse, predict, diagnose and become more powerful and capable resources.

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For Details Contact

THE SECRETARY

A. Shama Rao Foundation

G.H.S. Road, Mangalore – 575 001.

Phone: 0824 – 2425966, 244891 Fax: 0824 – 2442766

Email: info@srinivasgroup.com

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A Unit of A. Shama Rao Foundation's Srinivas Group of Colleges

Srinivas Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001. Phone:

0824-2441022, 2411383; Fax: 0824-2426766

E-mail: principalsims@srinivasgroup.com

www.srinivasgroup.com

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